

2nd European Carbon Farming Summit

Dublin, March 4-6, 2025

Organisers

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

In partnership with

An Roinn Talmhaíochta,
Bia agus Mara
Department of Agriculture,
Food and the Marine

**Fáilte
Ireland**

Leading sponsors

Agricarbon

We create chemistry

Supporting sponsors

Summit organisers

Daniel Zimmer (Climate KIC)
Saskia Keesstra (Climate KIC)
Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (SAE Innova)
Mathieu Mal (European Environmental Bureau – EEB)
Hannes Mollenhauer (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ)
Kaj Granholm (Baltic Sea Action Group – BSAG)

Scientific committee

Daniel Zimmer (Climate KIC)
Saskia Keesstra (Climate KIC)
Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (SAE Innova)
Mathieu Mal (European Environmental Bureau)
Hannes Mollenhauer (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ)
Kaj Granholm (Baltic Sea Action Group – BSAG)
Clara Diebolt (Association des Chambres d’agriculture de l’Arc atlantique – AC3A)
Dimitra Perperidou (AgroApps)
Tatiana Bullová (Bioeconomy Cluster – BEC)
Juan Sagarna (Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España – COOP)
Maria Fantappiè (Council for Agricultural Research and Economics of Italy – CREA)
Pilar Andrés (Centro de Investigación Ecológica y Aplicaciones Forestales – CREAM)
Monica Miguel-Lago (European Association of Remote Sensing Companies – EARSC)
Julio Román (European Conservation Agriculture Federation – ECAF)
Hugh McDonald (Ecologic Institute)
Vasileios Aschonitis (ELGO-DIMITRA)
Constantin Muraru (European Agroforestry Federation – EURAF)
Gerry Lawson (European Agroforestry Federation – EURAF)
Julia Grimault (Institute for Climate Economics – I4CE)
Hui Xu (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food – ILVO)
Andrea Ferrarini (Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore – UCSC)
Gerald Jurasinski (University of Greifswald – UG)
Paulina Rajewicz (University of Helsinki – UH)
Jonathan Atherton (University of Helsinki – UH)

Collaborators

Mary Brown (Climate KIC)
Colombe Ivernel (Climate KIC)
Dora Geczinger (Climate KIC)
Seth Armstrong-Twigg (Climate KIC)
Leandro Trupp (SAE Innova)
Yolanda Martínez Hernández (SAE Innova)

Overview of sessions, contributions, and recommendations

Editors

Daniel Zimmer, Seth Armstrong-Twigg, Leandro Trupp

Graphic design

Yolanda Martínez Hernández

Contributors D4.2 Project Credible

Dominika Skonecka-Guillamón (coordination), Tatiana Bullova (review), Kaj Granholm (review)

Contributing organisations

4per1000, Aeco, Agreeana, Agri Marketplace, Agricarbon, Agrifood, Agrimercarb, Agroinsider, Agroscope, Agrosolutions, Association des Chambres d'agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique (AC3A), BASF, BETA Technological Centre, Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG), Bioeconomy Cluster, BlueBiloba, Boerenbond Projects, Bord Bia, Carbery Farmers Cooperative, Carbon Capture Company, Carbone farmers, Carboneg, Caritas, Cà Colonna srl, Centre d'Études Spatiales de la BIOSphère (CNRS-CESBIO), Cesefor, CinSOIL GmbH, Climate Cleanup, Climate KIC, Commonland Foundation, Consulai, CoopsAgroES, CREA-AA, CREAM, DEAFAL, DELOITTE, Deutscher Fachverband für Agroforstwirtschaft (DeFAF), Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM), Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC), Earth Observation Association, ECS Climate Solutions, EIT Food South, ELGO-DIMITRA, Eleks, Environmental Protection Agency, European Space Agency Stakeholder Engagement Facility (ESA SEF), European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), European Conservation Agriculture Federation (ECAAF), European Environmental Bureau (EEB), European Landowners' Organization (ELO), Eurosite, Farmers, FiBL, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Friesland Campina, French Agricultural Chambers, GMV, Green Restoration Ireland, GreenO, Heavy Finance, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Institut de l'Élevage (IDELE), IFOAM Organics Europe, Institute for Climate Economics (I4CE), Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), Integrated Carbon Observation System – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ICOS-ERIC), Interreg NWE Smart Carbon Farming project, International Emissions Trading Association (IETA), Irish Cooperative Organisation Society, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Lakeland Dairies, Land Life, Livelihoods Funds, Mars Inc., Nataïs, National Association of Producers for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture (Produttori AOR), National Economic and Social Council, National Parks and Wildlife Service, Netcarbon, Peatland Finance Ireland, Philip Lee LLP / Hutchins Climate Capital, Preferred by Nature, Proba, Rabobank, Re-Cord, ReGeneration, Reframe, SAE Innova, SAS, Scave World, Seqana, SLM Partners, Social Carbon Foundation, Soil Capital, Space4Good, Tgo AG/ECN, Teagasc, Terre Inovia, Tetis Institute S.r.l, Thuenen Institute, Tierra Sphere, Trinity College Dublin, UCLouvain, University College Dublin, University of Cordoba, University of Florence, University of Greifswald, University of Helsinki, University of Pisa, Università degli Studi di Genova, Walton Institute, Wageningen Environmental Research, Wetlands International, Yard Stick PBC, Zuidelijke Land- en Tuinbouworganisatie (ZLTO).

Table of contents

Executive summary	7
The second Summit in numbers	9
Key outcomes	10
List of acronyms and abbreviations	11
Plenary sessions	12
1: Opening by the Government of Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) and the state of affairs in policy related to Carbon Farming (and beyond)	13
2: Technological pathways and user engagement approaches to a European MRV system	17
3: Paving the way towards climate positive agriculture: The role of innovating farmers	20
4: Policy areas relevant to Carbon Farming – Synergies and trade-offs	23
5: The way ahead from a systemic transition approach with speakers from science, policy, farmers organisation and industry	26
Parallel sessions	30
1: Scaling up resilient and inclusive agricultural value chains – From policy to financing adoption of new practices	31
2: Low hanging (tree) fruit – Reaping forest-based carbon removal potential, identifying challenges and gaps to open doors to forest management solutions	33
3: Income opportunities from peatland rewetting: Carbon credits, ecosystem service payments and paludiculture value chains	37
4: Exploring Carbon Farming approaches: Integrating circular solutions from biomass production & treatment to soil health and carbon sequestration	40
5: Bringing Carbon Farming from science to organic and regenerative farms: Challenges and solutions across research, markets, farmer-led models and policy	43
6: Carbon Farming, assured profitability? How to ensure the long-term sustainability of practices	45
7: CRCF business models	48
8: Making Carbon Farming work for regions – Outlining adaptation needs and opportunities	50
9: Farmers’ prospect: How does Carbon Farming affect crop production, and farm biodiversity and profitability?	53
10: The future of regional small-scale Carbon Farming projects: Discuss bottom-up experiences and align farmer and market perspectives	56
11: The role of advisors in climate action in Europe	59
12: Ensuring sustainability outcomes from Carbon Farming: Recommendations for the CRCF and voluntary carbon markets	62
13: Global or local? Carbon certification centralisation level: what implications for stakeholders?	64
14: The value chain challenge: Scaling scope 3 solutions	67
15: Insetting for Carbon Farming: Turning challenges into opportunities for farmers, food companies and policymakers	69

16: Unlocking the potential of soil biodiversity: Sustainable land management, restoration, and revenue generation	72
17: Multi-stakeholder networks and participatory approaches for successful Carbon Farming and soil health monitoring – Opportunities and challenges	75
18: Co-designing future services and a policy framework on Carbon Farming	83
19: Overcoming barriers to Carbon Farming projects financing: Bridging the gap between farmers and buyers through adequate framework and MRV tools	86
20: Financing models for a sustainable future	89
21: Paving the way for cohesive action on soil carbon sequestration: The role of International Initiatives in the development of MRV frameworks that meet European Carbon Farming challenges	90
22: Monitoring and verification of peatland condition and improvement: Remote sensing, AI and beyond	92
23: MRV agroforestry	94
24: Carbon Farming challenges in Mediterranean agriculture: resilient project solutions and certification pathways	101
25: Opportunities and challenges in proximal sensing–based monitoring for Carbon Farming	104
26: Integrating MRV methodologies and Incentives to reduce N ₂ O emissions in Carbon Farming	106
27: Unlocking data for MRV: Data sharing for effective Carbon Farming	109
28: Baseline approaches for monitoring soil carbon removals: Public – private synergies	112
29: (Non)-permanence and time dependency of carbon sequestration in Carbon Farming – Current accounting approaches and ways ahead	116
30: Addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking in Earth Observation-based MRV systems for Carbon Farming	119
31: Earth Observation for Carbon Farming: exploring existing solutions and future user needs	122
32: Real-life MRV challenges and solutions for the EU CRCF	124
33: How technology and AI is supporting the growth of efficient, high-integrity Carbon Farming markets	129
34: Rewarding mechanisms: Insights from farmers, agri-food companies and researchers for a successful approach	131
35: Learning from research and feedback from the field: How to put in place Carbon Farming on a farm? What levers and barriers?	133
36: What is the farmer’s opinion on Carbon Farming?	137
37: Ireland: An innovative, context specific, approach to Carbon Farming...?	139
38: From peatlands to policy: How praxis can guide EU CRCF certification	140
39: Legal opportunities for Carbon Farming: From creation of a registry to the necessary streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework	143
40: Why do we need direct measurement to secure Europe’s Carbon Farming future?	146
41: Setting the Gold Standard: Delivering shared value from reduced agricultural emissions	148
Posters	149

Executive summary

The 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit took place from 4–6 March 2025, at the historic Dublin Castle in Ireland. Organised by EU-funded project *CREDIBLE: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible Carbon Farming in the EU* (Grant Agreement 101112951) in partnership with the Government of Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, the summit brought together over 1,000 participants, including farmers, foresters, policymakers, researchers and businesses, to shape the future of Carbon Farming across Europe.

Following the success of the inaugural summit in Valencia, the 2025 edition shifted from theory to practice by involving a large array of stakeholders, including farmers. Its primary goal was to operationalize Carbon Farming by moving beyond high-level theory and focusing on practical strategies, tools, and frameworks that enable credible, scalable, and inclusive uptake of Carbon Farming across diverse European contexts.

As a multi-stakeholder event, the summit was designed around co-creation and dialogue. An open call for sessions and contributions allowed participants to shape the agenda, which featured five plenaries and over 40 breakout discussions covering topics such as monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), financing, policy alignment, landowner engagement, and biodiversity.

A defining feature of this year's summit was its farmer-centred approach. Farmers and land managers were invited to actively contribute and co-lead sessions. This reflected a clear recognition that those working directly with the land must be at the heart of the Carbon Farming transition. From peer-to-peer learning and lived experiences to practical barriers and incentives, the summit made space for their voices, challenges, and innovations.

Hosted in Ireland, a country emerging as a leader in regenerative agriculture, the summit also showcased the development of a national Carbon Farming framework that integrates carbon sequestration with broader environmental and social benefits. It provided a valuable case study for the rest of Europe and reinforced the importance of aligning EU policy, national action, and local practice.

The summit underscored the need for further research into multi-benefit Carbon Farming metrics, locally tailored MRV methodologies, and governance models that support flexibility while maintaining integrity. There is a pressing need to operationalise farmer-centric innovation systems, encourage peer-to-peer learning, and link practices with ecosystem-level monitoring. These insights suggest a rich research agenda that integrates social science, agronomy, remote sensing, and systems thinking.

Practitioners, meanwhile, are encouraged to adopt modular and inclusive approaches – designing schemes that can adapt to different geographies and farm types while aligning with evolving EU policy frameworks. The summit also made visible the need for new platforms to share success stories, coordinate initiatives, and prevent duplication of effort.

The summit highlighted the importance of policy coherence and integration. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation was welcomed as a step forward, but participants stressed that it must align with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), biodiversity, climate, and soil strategies. National governments and the European Commission were urged to reduce fragmentation, support multi-benefit schemes, and ensure Carbon Farming is embedded not only in food system transitions, but also in broader landscape strategies that include forestry, rewilding, and non-food bioeconomy sectors – such as the alternative use of rewetted organic soils. These insights are relevant across all eight Mission Soil objectives, particularly those addressing sustainable soil management, ecosystem services, and robust monitoring frameworks. At all levels, policies must enable long-term investment, differentiated approaches, and inclusive engagement with those managing Europe's land.

The 2025 Summit was a demonstration of how Europe's Carbon Farming transition can and must be designed: inclusively, systemically, and in partnership with those who steward the land. It brought the realities of farmers, the insights of scientists, and the levers of policy and finance into active dialogue. As Europe moves forward with Carbon Farming regulation and soil strategy implementation, the summit's outcomes will serve as a foundation for action, feeding directly into CREDIBLE's final year of activity and the shaping of a durable, post-project roadmap.

The second Summit in numbers

Key outcomes

A holistic approach

- 🌱 Landscape-level approach
- 🌱 Systemic transformation

While carbon sequestration remains a key goal, the summit confirmed that an overly narrow focus on soil carbon risks sidelining broader benefits. Attendees called for a shift toward landscape-level approaches that integrate biodiversity, water management, rural livelihoods, and ecosystem resilience. Carbon farming must be designed as a tool for systemic transformation, not just climate accounting.

Scaling with support

- 🌱 Public + private capital
- 🌱 Farmer guidance and tools
- 🌱 Close the support gap

Participants agreed that blended finance – combining public and private capital – is essential to make carbon farming viable and scalable. However, financial innovation must be accompanied by robust advisory networks to help farmers navigate complex requirements and access funding. The summit highlighted the implementation gap around farm-level support, which risks leaving many farmers behind.

Local leadership matters

- 🌱 Participatory design
- 🌱 Grounded in local realities
- 🌱 Builds trust and adoption

The summit itself demonstrated the power of participatory design, from its open-call structure to the central role of innovating farmers. Farmers must be treated not just as beneficiaries, but as co-designers and leaders of the transition. Building systems that reflect on-the-ground realities will be key to credibility and uptake.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AFOLU: Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use

AI: Artificial Intelligence

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CF: Carbon Farming

CO₂: Carbon Dioxide

CRCF: Carbon Removal Certification Framework

CSRD: Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive

DG AGRI: Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development

DG CLIMA: Directorate-General for Climate Action

DG ENV: Directorate-General for Environment

EC: European Commission

EEF: Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers

EIP-AGRI OG: European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability Operational Group

EO: Earth Observation

ESABCC: European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change

ETS: Emissions Trading System

EU: European Union

EUSO: European Union Soil Observatory

FSC: Forest Stewardship Council

GHG: Greenhouse Gas

ICVCM: Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market

LTM: Long-term Monitoring

LULUCF: Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry

MRV: Measurement, Reporting and Verification

NbS: Nature-based Solutions

NGOs: Non-governmental Organisation

PACM: Paris Agreement Crediting Mechanism

PEFC: Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification

RS: Remote Sensing

SCF: Smart Carbon Farming

Soil Carbon IRC: International Research Consortium

VCM: Voluntary Carbon Market

VVBs: Validation and Verification Bodies

Plenary sessions

Plenary 1: Opening by the Government of Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) and the state of affairs in policy related to Carbon Farming (and beyond)

Organisers: DG Clima, DG AGRI, JRC, Climate KIC

Objective: To highlight the current policy landscape for Carbon Farming in Europe and explore how evolving agricultural and climate frameworks – particularly the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) – can support an inclusive and credible transition toward regenerative land management.

Panellists:

- **Christian Holtzleitner:** Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals at the Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), European Commission. Since 2022, he has led the EU's work on sustainable carbon cycles and the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF). He has worked in the European Commission since 2012 in various policy development roles including ETS and state aid.
- **Eric Soubeiran:** CEO of Livelihoods Venture, which mobilises industrial investors to support rural energy, mangrove restoration, agroforestry, and smallholder farming projects in the Global South. Former Chief Sustainability Officer at Danone, Eric also serves on boards such as Gold Standard and The Carbon Trust.
- **Bill Callanan:** Chief Inspector at Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM). He oversees scientific advice on agriculture and environment, including climate change, biodiversity, livestock breeding, horticulture, pesticide regulation, and nutrient management.
- **Jocelyn Gainche:** Farmer and manager of GAEC des Belles Filles, a collaborative farm in western France producing cereals, pork, and beef. Jocelyn uses the farm as a testing ground for innovative practices aligned with Carbon Farming. He also brings international farming experience, including time spent in Poland.
- **Daniel Zimmer (moderator):** Director of Sustainable Land Use at Climate KIC. Daniel is a climate policy expert and researcher focusing on sustainable land use and long-term resilience. He leads major initiatives such as the Climate Smart Forest Economy Programme, which aims to scale up sustainable alternatives to fossil-based materials.

Summary of the session

The first plenary session of the summit opened with remarks from Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (Project CREDIBLE), who provided a short look back on the past year of the CREDIBLE project. After this, Saskia Keesstra introduced the logistics and began with some general questions to the in-person and online audience using Menti, regarding their country of origin and stakeholder category (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Results of the Menti questions during the Plenary 1 session.

The keynote address was delivered by Christian Holzleitner (DG CLIMA), who provided an overview of the EU's strategic direction on agriculture in the climate transition and shared updates on the CRCF, designed to reward land-based carbon removals through a robust, science-led certification framework.

Facilitated by moderator Daniel Zimmer, the panel brought together European, national, industry, and farming perspectives to respond to two key topics: the transformation of agri-food systems and the design of credible Carbon Farming mechanisms. Audience interaction through Mentimeter helped surface diverse stakeholder perspectives and catalyse co-

creative dialogue. Menti questions were gathered from the audience and a selected number of questions were asked to the panellists.

The first discussion explored the political and practical context of the agri-food transition. Bill Callanan outlined Ireland’s approach to balancing biodiversity, emissions reductions, and farm viability, calling for fairness and trust in implementation. Eric Soubeiran emphasised that sustainable agriculture must be both economically competitive and aligned with long-term value chain commitments. Jocelyn Gainche, speaking from farmer experience, urged policymakers to reduce red tape and invest in advisory services to empower change at the ground level.

The second discussion focused on CRCF implementation. Panellists acknowledged the CRCF’s value in creating a credible and harmonised approach but flagged concerns around MRV complexity, accessibility for smallholders, and the need for coherence between EU-level regulation and national systems. Audience responses reflected both hope for the CRCF’s impact and concern over practical barriers to farmer participation.

The panel ended with some final comments from the panellists on what they expect to get out of the summit. The same question was asked to the audience via Menti. The results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Replies of the question “What do you bring to the summit that you want to share and what do you expect to get”, asked to summit participants through Menti.

Key learnings

- **CRCF is an important step, but must be grounded in reality:** While the framework introduces much-needed legitimacy and consistency to Carbon Farming, its success will depend on simplicity, flexibility, and local alignment.
- **Farmer engagement is both essential and fragile:** Without trust, fairness, and support, farmers are unlikely to engage in Carbon Farming schemes – particularly given current frustrations with bureaucracy and market volatility.
- **The agri-food sector must balance multiple pressures:** Climate ambition must go hand-in-hand with economic viability, especially for small-scale producers. This requires clear incentives, transparent governance, and value chain support.
- **Policy coherence is vital:** Fragmentation across EU and national policies risks undermining impact. Effective integration – between CAP, CRCF, and biodiversity strategies – is needed to enable a joined-up, systemic approach.
- **Advisory and knowledge systems are key enablers:** Capacity-building, technical advice, and farmer networks must be resourced and strengthened if Carbon Farming is to move from policy concept to widespread practice.

This session effectively set the tone for the summit, reinforcing Carbon Farming as not just a climate mitigation tool, but a lever for wider agricultural transformation – grounded in collaboration, trust, and practical implementation.

Plenary 2: Technological pathways and user engagement approaches to a European MRV system

Organiser: Hannes Mollenhauer (UFZ)

Objective: To explore technical, financial, and practical challenges in building a robust and harmonised European MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) system for Carbon Farming—while identifying solutions that reduce complexity, ensure credibility, and align with certification needs across ecosystems, scales, and stakeholder groups.

Panellists:

- **Tessa van der Voort:** project manager at NMI, where she specializes in soil carbon, data analysis, and sustainability. She earned her PhD in soil science from ETH Zurich and combines biogeochemistry with data science to advance carbon sequestration research.
- **Greet Ruyschaert:** Senior Researcher at ILVO. She holds a PhD in agricultural sciences and specializes in sustainable soil management, carbon sequestration, and soil health monitoring. She also coordinates MARVIC project on GHG balance and Carbon Farming systems.
- **Edouard Lanckriet:** Strategy Director and Head of the Low-Carbon Agriculture Division at Agrosolutions, spearheading their carbon-farming and MRV initiatives. An agronomist-engineer with a Master's in Environmental Management and a PhD in development socio-economics, he has led international projects (China, Brazil, Africa) and plays a key role in EU initiatives like MARVIC.
- **Ahmad Al Bitar:** Head of Development at CESBIO (CNRS), leading the AgriCarbon-EO tool. A remote sensing specialist with a PhD in environmental modelling, he has contributed over 95 scientific publications and plays a key role in satellite-based agricultural and hydrological monitoring.
- **Liv Toonen:** Technical Project Lead at Space4Good, leveraging her aerospace engineering background to apply remote-sensing and geospatial technologies for social and environmental impact, including deforestation monitoring and ESG reporting.
- **Véronique Chauvin:** Head of the Trees & Biodiversity Service at the Chambre d'Agriculture Pays de la Loire. Since 2018, she has overseen energy-environment missions and biodiversity initiatives, including agroforestry and hedgerow programs.
- **Roberta Mac Donald:** Head of Programme at Agreena, where she leads the development of high-integrity soil carbon certification projects. With a PhD in agricultural science and a background in sustainability leadership, she drives Agreena's strategy for Verra-verified Carbon Farming.

- **Marco Alves:** Programme Modelling Lead at Agreeena, where he develops models to quantify soil carbon and greenhouse gas emissions. He holds a PhD in agricultural sciences and has a background in climate impact research and regulatory affairs.

Keynotes:

- Monitoring, Reporting and verification in Europe – In the framework of the CRCF regulation. Tessa van der Voort – *NMI Wageningen*
- Agreeena’s Approach: Calculation Soil Carbon Change. Roberta McDonald & Marcos Alvez – *Agreeena*

Summary of the session

This panel discussion brought together experts from remote sensing, agricultural consultancy, data science, and farming practice to examine how carbon flows can be effectively tracked and verified within the European context. Moderated in a dynamic, solutions-oriented format, the session delved into approaches for addressing current data gaps, reducing the burden of MRV on farmers, and harmonising methodologies across land types and use cases.

Discussions highlighted the complexity of implementing advanced monitoring systems while ensuring they remain affordable and usable by farmers and cooperatives. There was also strong emphasis on aligning MRV tools with certification frameworks like the EU’s CRCF, so that data gathered can serve multiple purposes—compliance, incentives, transparency, and long-term ecosystem monitoring. The speakers emphasised the importance of cross-sector collaboration to break silos between researchers, practitioners, and policy implementers.

Key learnings

- **Data quality and accessibility remain a critical challenge:** Speakers agreed that meaningful carbon accounting begins with robust, ground-truthed data – but that such data is often inconsistent or unavailable across regions and ecosystems.
- **MRV systems must be scalable and cost-effective:** Overly technical or expensive systems are unlikely to see uptake, particularly by smallholder farmers. Simplification, user-friendliness, and local context were identified as key design principles.
- **Standardisation without rigidity is essential:** While different ecosystems require tailored approaches, stakeholders need harmonised protocols that enable comparability, transparency, and integration with broader EU policies.
- **Co-benefits tracking is gaining momentum:** Carbon sequestration alone is no longer enough. MRV systems are evolving to include metrics on biodiversity, soil health, and water retention to reflect the broader value of Carbon Farming practices.
- **Scenario modelling can complement measured data:** Validated, science-based models can help forecast carbon outcomes and inform planning but must be used in conjunction with reliable field data.
- **Integration with certification frameworks is vital:** To minimise duplication and maximise value, MRV tools should be interoperable across schemes and geographies – enabling “measure once, report many times” functionality.
- **Farmer-centric design and training are needed:** Farmers must be equipped and supported to engage with MRV systems. Without adequate advisory support and digital literacy, even the best-designed systems risk underutilisation.

This session underscored that the future of MRV is not just technological, but also deeply social and systemic. Trust, usability, and collaboration will be just as important as sensors and algorithms in building a functioning Carbon Farming ecosystem in Europe.

Plenary 3: Paving the way towards climate positive agriculture: The role of innovating farmers

Organiser: [Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris \(SAE Innova\)](#)

Objective: To spotlight pioneering farmers who are leading the transition toward climate-positive agriculture, unpack their motivations, challenges, and experiences, and explore how they can act as “lighthouses” to inspire broader systemic change.

Panellists:

- **Sheila Damos:** third generation farmer and a social entrepreneur in the agri-food sector and civic engagement field in Greece. Her key focuses lie within her lived physical and social environment, namely the farming and rural communities, and thus a systemic approach to enable transitions towards regeneration in a holistic way. Her dedication to soil and ecosystem restoration translates into her dedication to transforming the farming sector in Greece through the initiative “Regenerative Farming Greece”.
- **Mateusz Ciasnocha:** farmer from Poland on the mission of building a farmer-centric bridge between agricultural and climate policy. He lives his call to action through two businesses: the European Carbon Farmers and the Farm of Francesco. Mateusz is an

Advisory Board member for the Foundation of the Economy of Francesco, the Laudato Si Action Platform at the Holy See and the EU Soil Mission.

- **Iain Tolhurst:** farmer at the forefront of the UK organic farming movement for almost 50 years. His 8-ha farm has won many awards, for its innovative approach to crop production utilising biodiversity at its heart to develop soil health and fertility. Long term monitoring of carbon and soil has shown the benefits of this system. The integration of crops, a systems approach to pest and disease management and biodiversity makes for a fascinating and durable agricultural system.
- **Rob Smith** (Moderator): broadcaster and host, having worked as a journalist and presenter on TV and Radio with the BBC in the UK for over 25 years. He is a passionate advocate for environmental protection, hosting the Talk on the Wild Side podcast that explores how we can balance human needs with sustainable practice.

Summary of the session

This energising roundtable placed farmer voices at the centre of the summit, amplifying real-world perspectives on regenerative agriculture. Moderator Rob Smith steered a grounded, values-led discussion between three innovative farmers from across Europe who each shared not only their practices but also their personal journeys into climate-positive farming.

Mateusz Ciasnocha (Poland) stressed the need for decision-makers and researchers to “visit the farmer,” underlining the gap between policy discourse and on-farm realities. He argued that every farmer is already a carbon farmer by nature of their role in the carbon cycle, and pointed to soil health – not carbon metrics – as the true heart of transformation.

Sheila Damos (Greece) reflected on the disconnect between farmers and institutional structures. She emphasised that impactful change often happens outside of EU programmes and schemes, and called for a deeper immersion into rural life to identify authentic leverage points. The term “Carbon Farming,” she noted, is largely unintelligible or irrelevant to many farmers in her region – advocating instead for a holistic, ecosystem-centred framing.

Iain Tolhurst (UK), a veteran of agroecological practice, championed biodiversity as both a guiding principle and a source of learning. “Let yourself be infused by biodiversity,” he urged – recounting how his long-term relationship with soil life, such as earthworms, shaped his understanding of sustainable farming. For him, biodiversity is not a co-benefit – it’s central to the system.

The panel also explored their experiences with carbon footprint tools, reflecting both the empowering potential and the current limitations of such systems. Complexity, lack of farmer input in design, and insufficient advisory support remain barriers.

Finally, the session engaged with the Law of Diffusion of Innovation, noting that Carbon Farming is still in the innovator phase. Early adopters – like the farmers on stage – are not primarily driven by market signals or carbon pricing, but by a philosophy of stewardship and

a desire to “do what is good for the planet.” Any system that fails to meet these innovators on their terms risks losing momentum before mainstream uptake can begin.

Key learnings

- **Farmers are change agents, not policy recipients:** Their leadership, lived experience, and experimentation must be recognised, resourced, and reflected in policy and market frameworks.
- **Motivations go beyond money:** For innovators, regenerative practices are driven by ecological values, community health, and long-term resilience – not just financial return.
- **Language matters:** Terms like “Carbon Farming” may alienate some farmers. Communication should reflect the diversity of motivations, and place ecological integrity at the centre.
- **Early adopters need targeted support:** Innovators often operate without safety nets. Systems must value their risk-taking and contributions – not just through subsidies, but through visibility, validation, and peer learning.
- **Biodiversity and soil health are core to transformation:** These are not side benefits but fundamental drivers of successful regenerative agriculture.
- **We’re still early in the adoption curve:** Policymakers and designers must build systems attractive to innovators first – price alone won’t drive uptake.

This session powerfully illustrated that climate-positive agriculture begins not in Brussels boardrooms or satellite data, but in the hearts, hands, and fields of farmers. Their courage, insight, and commitment are already laying the path – now the rest of the system must follow.

Plenary 4: Policy areas relevant to Carbon Farming – Synergies and trade-offs

Organiser: Mathieu Mal (European Environmental Bureau)

Objective: To examine the effect of the introduction of a new policy, the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming regulation, and its interactions with different policy areas that intersect with Carbon Farming in the EU, including climate, agricultural, and nature policy, as well as financing and business regulation. The session aimed to explore how the different policies and instruments can learn or borrow from each other to maximise synergies and avoid tensions, resulting in a coherent policy mix that is conducive for robust Carbon Farming at scale.

Panellists:

- **Lucia Perugini:** Expert on Carbon Farming Certification and LULUCF at the European Environment Agency. PhD in forest ecology with scientific background in forestry and climate change. She worked at CMCC, Italy (2013-23), and was involved in several national and European research projects related to the LULUCF sector, carbon markets and relevant links between the scientific and policy communities. She was the Italian delegate at the UNFCCC negotiations (2003-23) dealing on issues related to CDM, agriculture, LULUCF and REDD+.
- **Hugh McDonald:** Senior Fellow at Ecologic Institute, applying an environmental economics lens to Carbon Farming and climate policy. His work focuses on nature-based climate mitigation, market-based instruments, and biodiversity finance. Within the CREDIBLE project, his work has focused on Carbon Farming and sustainability.
- **Andrew Voysey:** Chief Impact Officer at Soil Capital, the agronomy firm that launched a regenerative agriculture transition programme certifying its climate impact in 2020. It is the longest running such programme in Europe and is designed to enable food and beverage firms to deliver proven Scope 3 reductions and more resilient supply chains. Concurrently, Andrew is on the Supervisory Board of the Cool Farm Alliance and a Strategic Advisor to the Sustainable Soils Alliance in the UK. Previously, he led the sustainable finance practice at the University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership and was an advisor on climate change to the Bank of England.
- **Alan Matthews:** Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy at the University of Dublin Trinity College, Ireland. He is a former President of the European Association of Agricultural Economists and has been a member of Ireland's Climate Change Advisory Council.

Summary of the session

This high-level panel brought together leading voices in policy, science, and sustainable agriculture to unpack the interconnections, and sometimes tensions, between various legislative and market-based instruments relevant to Carbon Farming. As Carbon Farming gains traction in EU climate and agricultural policy, the need for policy coherence becomes increasingly urgent.

The session opened with a keynote speech by Alan Matthews who presented the potential for Carbon Farming under the current Common Agricultural Policy, the EU's leading land management policy that drives agricultural practices across the continent with about a third of the total EU budget.

Hugh McDonald stressed the need for mandatory sectorial climate targets to catalyse action, cautioning that voluntary action will only take us so far. He added that the potential of Carbon Farming to a large extent lies in making supply chains more resilient.

Lucia Perugini warned that the land sink has been on a downward trajectory for the past years, driven by increased harvesting and the effects of climate change that impede forests' capacity to absorb carbon. This stands in stark contrast to the ambitious LULUCF objective of increasing carbon sequestration, which many EU Member States are struggling to achieve. She raised the importance of the CRCF reaching a scale where it can feed into the national greenhouse gas inventories and improve monitoring of land carbon sequestration at national level.

Alan Matthews reiterated the need expressed by Perugini to increase the level of detail in the national inventories so that Carbon Farming can contribute to national targets. He also reflected on the questions around the potential and appropriate combined use of public and private finance.

Andrew Voysey provided insight on the blended finance question by referring to the fact that many countries, through their CAP strategic plans, only provide partial compensation to farmers for certain actions. In those cases, where for example only the capital expenditure has been covered by public funds, private sector funding could complement by covering for operating costs. Andrew also reflected on the promise of digitisation in farming, and the need for special attention for the properties of the units generated by the CRCF, ensuring that they would be suitable for use through different avenues.

Collectively, the panel emphasised that Carbon Farming must be embedded in a broader strategy that aligns policies and instruments by harmonising indicators and exchanging data between systems, making best use of public and private finance, while maintaining ambition and practical deliverability.

Key learnings

- **A binding climate target** for the agriculture sector will allow farmers and the agri-food sector to plan ahead.
- **Carbon Farming must serve a wider agenda:** It should be seen not only as a climate mitigation tool but as a mechanism for holistic change that regenerates landscapes, supports food systems, and strengthens rural economies.
- **Policy coherence is non-negotiable:** Misalignment across CAP, CRCF, LULUCF, Nature Restoration Regulation, Soil Monitoring Law, etc. risks undermining the environmental integrity and credibility of Carbon Farming efforts.
- **Carbon pricing is necessary but insufficient:** Financial incentives must be paired with safeguards to ensure practices deliver long-term climate and environmental benefits. Price premiums for additional sustainability can motivate farmers to take up more activities.
- **We need to build an interoperable system:** Standardisation, data transparency, equitable benefit-sharing, and effective use of public funding must guide how the private sector engages with Carbon Farming.

Plenary 5: The way ahead from a systemic transition approach with speakers from science, policy, farmers organisation and industry

Organisers: Climate KIC and BSAG

Objective: To reflect on the key outcomes of the summit from multiple stakeholder perspectives – including policy, science, industry, and farming – and to identify strategic priorities for enabling a systemic transition to climate-positive agriculture across Europe.

Panellists:

- **Kirsten Dunlop:** CEO of Climate-KIC. Kirsten brings over 30 years of experience in catalysing systemic transformation across academia, consulting, banking, and insurance. She is deeply committed to building a climate-resilient society and serves on multiple advisory boards, including the European Commission’s ESIR expert group on the Economic and Societal Impact of Research and Innovation.
- **Saara Kankaanrinta:** Philanthropist, entrepreneur, and environmental activist. She is former Chair and Co-Founder of the Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG) and Chair of the Carbon Action platform, Vice Chair of Natural Resources Institute Finland (LUKE), and Co-Founder of Soilfood Ltd and Q Power Ltd. She owns Qvidja Research Farm and Gullkrona Harbour in Finland. A nature columnist and co-author of two books, she was awarded an honorary doctorate in science by the University of Turku in 2022.
- **Gustavo Palerosi Carneiro:** Senior Vice President of BASF Agricultural Solutions for Europe, Africa, Middle East, and CIS. With over 20 years of experience across multiple continents, Gustavo is focused on digitalisation, sustainability, and value chain integration. He oversees BASF’s Global Carbon Farming Program, which connects farmers, partners, and certification bodies. He holds an MBA from the University of São Paulo and a Bachelor's in Business from Fundação Armando Alvares Penteado.
- **Bill Callanan:** Assistant Secretary at Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM). He leads on scientific advice for agriculture and the environment.
- **Thomas Duffy:** Irish farmer and former President of Macra na Feirme. An advocate for youth involvement and innovation in agriculture, with a strong focus on sustainable rural development.
- **Valeria Forlin:** Deputy Head of Unit at DG CLIMA since 2024, focusing on the land sector’s contribution to climate action – including emission reductions, carbon sinks, and sustainable food systems. Previously worked at UCLouvain, where she completed a PhD in environmental economics and taught in the same field. She also worked on European space policies, particularly Copernicus.
- **Saskia Keesstra:** Senior Researcher at EIT Climate-KIC and Wageningen University & Research. Her expertise spans soil systems, landscape dynamics, sustainable land

and water management, and policy advice. She contributes to EU-level projects including the Horizon Europe Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe.”

Summary of the session

Overall, the final plenary of the summit brought together a diverse group of high-level speakers to reflect on the three-day event and consider the road ahead. Moderated by Saskia Keesstra, the session framed Carbon Farming not as a stand-alone intervention but as part of a broader systemic transformation in agriculture, value chains, and land use.

Two Mentimeter polls helped guide the conversation (Figure 3). First, participants were asked whether they believed Carbon Farming could meet the needs of all stakeholder groups. This prompted reflections from the panel about the importance of designing Carbon Farming systems that are inclusive, credible, and responsive to ground-level realities.

The second poll asked the audience to rank the greatest barriers to scaling Carbon Farming, distributing 100 points across issues such as policy incoherence, financial risk, lack of advisory support, and data complexity. These results framed a rich discussion on the challenges, and possibilities, of moving from pilot projects to mainstream adoption.

Figure 4. Replies to the questions “Do you think Carbon Farming will deliver on the needs of different stakeholder categories?” (top) and “What is the main barrier to deliver Carbon Farming at scale? (divide 100 points)” (bottom), asked to summit participants through Menti.

Panellists echoed one another on the need for collaboration beyond silos, emphasising that change must involve actors who don't typically work together. From policymakers and researchers to corporations and farmers, all must contribute to – and benefit from – the transition. Kirsten Dunlop underscored the urgency of systems thinking, while Saara Kankaanrinta and Thomas Duffy brought attention to the on-the-ground realities for farmers and land stewards, including their desire for fair market prices over dependency on subsidies.

Gustavo Palerosi Carneiro highlighted the growing commitment of agri-business to support regenerative practices, while Valeria Forlin reassured the audience that the European Commission is taking stakeholder feedback seriously in shaping the future of land-use and climate policy.

Key learnings

- **Systemic thinking is essential** – Tackling Carbon Farming in isolation won't work. Stakeholders must collaborate across sectors and disciplines to drive meaningful transformation.
- **Low-hurdle, fast-action pilots to learn and scale faster, and partnerships to accelerate change** – Engaging large industries and aligning public and private action can scale innovation and impact.
- **Policy is evolving, but needs real-world anchoring** – Institutions like the European Commission are listening, but coherence, clarity, and flexibility are needed to ensure implementation works for farmers.
- **Farmers want value, not dependency** – Panellists stressed that many farmers would prefer fair and stable market prices over increasingly complex subsidies.

- **Trust and legitimacy are non-negotiable** – The Carbon Farming transition must be transparent, fair, and rooted in shared understanding between all actors.

This closing session affirmed the summit’s core message: Carbon Farming is a catalyst for change – but success depends on embracing complexity, listening across boundaries, and designing for impact at scale. A recurring theme throughout the summit, particularly in sessions on farmers, food chains, and MRV, was the critical question of who pays: how to finance Carbon Farming and its associated monitoring systems, and how to justify and allocate those investments. The path forward must therefore be inclusive, science-based, grounded in shared responsibility – and underpinned by clear, fair, and sustainable funding mechanisms.

Parallel sessions

Belowground Biomass

- Approx. 20-40 % of the aboveground biomass [14, 15]
- Substantial, as studies on older hedgerows show [16]
- Root-pruning b/w -farming [17], fine roots die off during tillage, C stored in deeper soil areas [18, 19]
- Allowable functions based on the root-base diameter for few species only, thus limited
- Key figures here are the root-shoot ratios [20]

Calculations should be made with caution

EUROPEAN
CARBON FARMING
SUMMIT

2nd European Carbon
Farming Summit
From theory to practice

The summit is part of a series of events for high-level experts in the field of climate, carbon and nature
learning, research and practice, showcasing the technological advances, knowledge and
innovation, and driving the transition to a climate-resilient Europe by 2050.

Session 1: Scaling up resilient and inclusive agricultural value chains – From policy to financing adoption of new practices

Main organisers: Livelihoods funds, Social Carbon Foundation, Treevaluation

Session description

This session explored strategies to advance resilient, sustainable agricultural value chains by addressing challenges in financing and adopting regenerative farming practices. With several industry leaders from Livelihoods, Equilibrium Lab, the International Platform for Insetting and Social Carbon Foundation identified key barriers, including financial risks for farmers, limited technical support, and unclear market incentives. The session highlighted the importance of systemic change through policy adjustments, financial innovation, and collaborative efforts across the agrifood sector to create inclusive, nature-positive value chains.

Issues

- Overcoming Barriers to Adoption, addressing challenges faced by farmers, agrifood companies, and consumers in adopting regenerative practices.
- Innovative Financing for Sustainable Agriculture, including insetting strategies and payments for ecosystem services integrated into business strategies.
- Strengthening Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) Defining key steps to implement scalable, high-integrity MRV systems across value chains - a case for Nature Stewardship approach

Recommendations

The discussions yielded several key recommendations for policymakers, the financial sector, agrifood companies, and farmers:

1.1: Policy & Governance:

- Establish a long-term policy vision to encourage farmer investment in regenerative practices.
- Stabilize public funding and shift Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) payments to an outcome-based reward system.
- Integrate EU agricultural and environmental policies to minimize project and company risks.
- Drive adoption of the EU Carbon Farming Certification Framework to stimulate demand for insetting.

1.2: Field & Farmers:

- Ensure farmers have a voice in policy and industry decisions.
- Showcase proven business cases to overcome adoption barriers.
- Expand technical support tailored to local farming conditions.

1.3: Financial and Insurance Sector:

- Recognize land and nature as critical infrastructure and investment opportunities.
- Reduce crop- and climate-related portfolio risks by transitioning to nature-positive inputs and practices.
- Implement risk-sharing mechanisms across agrifood value chains.

1.4: Agrifood Sector Companies:

- Integrate regeneratively grown crops into core business models.
- Build long-term supplier relationships for resilient value chains.
- Engage suppliers in long-term sourcing relationships.
- Pool resources for high-integrity insetting initiatives.

1.5: Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV):

- Expand MRV frameworks beyond carbon to reward holistic land stewardship.
- Develop pragmatic, digital MRV systems that improve value chain cost-efficiency.
- Ensure data collection provides direct value to farmers.

Session 2: Low hanging (tree) fruit – Reaping forest-based carbon removal potential, identifying challenges and gaps to open doors to forest management solutions

Main organisers: I4CE, Climate KIC

Session description

The carbon removal potential in our managed forests is important, and the full picture only emerges by integrating forests in a landscape approach among other land uses such as agriculture. We already have almost all the tools needed to realize this potential, and the CRCF regulation is a great opportunity to share a common and high-quality EU standard. However, forestry projects imply specific characteristics (long time horizons, slow growth of trees, strong exposure to natural disturbances...) and so specific concerns in terms of carbon certification. By discussing pioneering projects across the EU, this session strives to bring together the voices of practitioners and carbon markets experts to highlight the forest side critical points to align the supply of forest carbon credits with market demand.

Issues

Baselines are the main risk for carbon finance credibility and the main sources of over-crediting for forest projects come from a bad baseline definition. We need to ensure the robustness of baselines, while being able to adapt to different local contexts. Specific and generic baselines have been discussed a lot.

Forest long term horizon and non-permanence risk : which tools to use and how to ensure a robust market? How to ensure there is demand for forest credits?

Diversity of Improved Forest Management practices in Europe require adapted and tailored certification criteria (baseline...).

Recommendations

2.1: Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: Baseline is the key element for a robust certification framework: It represents the primary source of over-crediting risks and has been at the heart of past controversies in forest carbon certification. Baselines set the context for data requirements and thus for the administrative burden. A key question arises: to what extent can a standardised baseline provide specific parameters to match local conditions?

Recommendation: Methodologies should be prescriptive and standardised enough in terms of baseline and data management to limit the inputs from project developers, while ensuring the use of local data whenever possible.

A key take-away from the session is the need for semantic clarification, where “specific” or “standardised” can refer to different realities according to the stakeholders involved. If the main parameters of baseline are set within the methodologies, it allows to limit bias (information asymmetry between the regulator and project developer) and reduce costs, as it limits the work required from project developers and simplifies audits. However, it still needs to be as adapted to local conditions and rely as much as possible on local data, when they are available, and fulfil necessary criteria such as minimum precision, science based/sourced from acknowledged third parties. High tier project based local data can always be used within a "standardised" way to meet local consistency while ensuring project developers can not pick and choose what/how data is used or making arbitrary assumptions.

There is already very robust data available with strict MRV and 3rd party-verification, in some countries like Austria, Germany, Slovenia or Sweden. Beyond ground-based inventories, some Member States also provide remote sensing data, such as airborne LiDAR which offers detailed three-dimensional information on forest structure. Finally, the inherent risk of windfall effect associated with standardised baselines needs to be addressed. Discount could be applied when useful to limit the overall risk of over-crediting.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.2: Open question

Context: Temporary credits raise doubt about certificates’ attractiveness on the market.

Recommendation: Ensure the attractiveness of “temporary credits”, by 1) changing the name and 2) exploring avenues beyond voluntary funding.

The risk of non-permanence is a crucial risk for forest credits, and CRCF should be transparent about it. However, temporary is not the only criteria to define those certificates, which also have other benefits that permanent certificates might not have: positive impacts on biodiversity, soils, water, lower costs than technological removals. Forest certificates also have a value in terms of carbon: climate change has to be mitigated now, and positive impacts on 30-40 years still have value, even though we cannot guarantee it will last 1000 years. A positive terminology **and a communication strategy** need to be defined to be transparent about permanence but highlighting other benefits, to ensure nature-based projects are actually financed.

High integrity credits provided; appropriate use cases have to be facilitated in corresponding regulations. For example, the new contribution paradigm can be used to stream private funding to Nature based certificates if clearly stated in the Green Claim Directive.

Finally, we doubt that voluntary demand alone will allow to scale those removals, especially nature-based ones, so we need to focus on other sources of funding for natural removals:

public funds, compliance demand. As proposed in the recent report published by ESABCC, specific targets for “Temporary Carbon Credits” should be established.

To whom: CRCF and EC in methodologies development

2.3: Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure funding opportunities adapted to forest projects:

- 1) Address the time lag between investment in forests (e.g., plantation costs) and long-term climate benefits by allowing and encouraging **up-front financing** for the practices that requires it (e.g. afforestation, reforestation, forest restoration). Given the long timeframes inherent to forestry, pre-financing mechanisms should be structured over several decades.
- 2) Ensure the **most performant projects** on sustainability criteria (biodiversity, water, soils...) actually **benefit from a premium carbon price**, to encourage them.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.4: Proposals to improve CRCF

Support a **variety of management options**, especially no regret strategies which provide long-term benefits but also do not imply a huge carbon debt, as well as present benefits for other ecosystem services. Given the diversity of contexts in Europe, there is **no one-size-fits-all methodology for improved forest management**. Biophysical parameters but also socio-economical (active vs inactive forestry and size of properties) are parameters to consider to build targeted methodologies. Options to support methodologies that reward risk-mitigation strategies (e.g., fire prevention, pest control) should be explored, even if they do not result in immediate carbon gains, to enhance long-term forest resilience. Forest methodologies need to take into account the specificities of harvested wood products in order to 1) promote the creation and use of long-life wood products 2) ensure coherence with the methodology ‘carbon storage in buildings’.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.5: Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure attractiveness of CRCF for small forest owners (average private parcel in Europe is 12.7 ha, with many owners with parcels below 1 ha), by providing understandable and easy-to-apply methodologies: a balance is needed between scientific robustness and go-to-market strategy to make it attractive and profitable for forest holdings. Supporting the integration of carbon markets with broader land-use policies to maximize synergies between climate action and sustainable forest management will also help the involvement of stakeholders. There is no need to reinvent the wheel: sustainability criteria already exist in existing regulations (Taxonomy, Nature Restoration Law...) and in sustainable forest management standards (PEFC, FSC).

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.6: Recommendation for action

Context: Forest-based carbon certification in Europe faces diverse biophysical, socio-economic, and institutional challenges. Continuous, cross-sectoral dialogue is essential to co-develop solutions that reflect this complexity. The Carbon Farming Summit demonstrated the value of multi-actor discussions and highlighted stakeholders' desire for ongoing engagement beyond singular events.

Recommendation: Establish a dedicated and recurring forum for forestry stakeholders—public and private forest owners, certifiers, researchers, policymakers, and carbon market actors—to co-develop and test methodologies, share best practices, and align efforts. This space should be structured yet flexible, with thematic working groups (e.g., on smallholder access, buffers, fire resilience) and regular feedback loops to feed into CRCF guidance and methodology development. Such a forum can foster trust, improve implementation, and ensure that forest carbon solutions are grounded in real-world forest management contexts.

To whom: CRCF and EC

Session 3: Income opportunities from peatland rewetting: Carbon credits, ecosystem service payments and paludiculture value chains

Main organiser: Greifswald Mire Centre

Session description

This interactive session explored the income opportunities available to farmers after rewetting or during restoration of drained peatlands on agricultural lands. Farmers, value chain actors and other interested stakeholders were invited to dive into the topic of paludiculture, Carbon Farming ecosystem services payments, and landscape regeneration. Participants explored practical strategies to boost peatland rewetting and paludiculture, to leverage carbon credits and international carbon schemes, and to address challenges and market demand for paludiculture products.

Issues

- Income Opportunities from Peatland Rewetting
- Challenges in Market Development for Paludiculture Products
- Practical Implementation of Carbon Farming and Policy Support

Recommendations

3.1: Establish Financial Support Mechanisms for Farmers

- Governments and financial institutions should provide targeted funding (subsidies, low-interest loans, grants) to support farmers transitioning to paludiculture and Carbon Farming.
- Develop risk-sharing mechanisms, such as insurance for yield losses to provide farmers with confidence in rewetting investments.
- Use early carbon credit revenues to bridge financial gaps until markets mature. For paludiculture to succeed, demand must be stimulated, and farmers need long-term security that someone will buy the biomass.
- Support exploratory rewetting, allowing farmers to reverse decisions after trial periods. This approach has proven effective in increasing participation and helping farmers recognize the long-term benefits.
- Facilitate farmer collaboration of farmers/landowners with private sector peatland restoration project developers who register the project under a carbon standard to generate carbon credits and create payments to the farmers/landowners.

- Provide financial support for testing the viability of Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) schemes (it takes about 4 years to implement 1 pilot scheme)

To whom:

1. National governments and EU policymakers (Common Agricultural Policy, Green Deal initiatives).
2. Ministries of Agriculture, Environment, and Finance.
3. Banks and financial institutions supporting green investments.
4. Private sector through payment for ecosystem services and peatland restoration project developers

3.2: Strengthen Market Development for Paludiculture Products

- Invest in developing paludiculture value chains, ensuring stable demand for paludiculture crops such as cattail, reed, peat moss, and wetland biomass for bioenergy.
- Offer price guarantees and long-term contracts (minimum 10 years) to de-risk investments.
- Support pilot projects that connect farmers with value chain actors to demonstrate the economic viability of paludiculture products.
- Develop standardized peatland baselines to reduce costs, ease the burden on farmers and project developers, and thus support CRCF uptake.
- Encourage the use of existing farming machinery with modifications rather than requiring entirely new equipment, reducing transition costs.

To whom:

1. Agribusinesses, food processors, and bioeconomy industries.
2. Retailers and consumer goods companies.
3. Policymakers working on sustainable agriculture and bioeconomy strategies.

3.3: Improve Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing for Farmers

- Establish farmer training programs to provide hands-on guidance on peatland rewetting, carbon credit certification, and paludiculture best practices.
- Provide subsidies for training of the trainers to teach about paludiculture crops and techniques. Agricultural consultants play a crucial role in supporting the farmers, providing expert advice and services.
- Establish regional knowledge hubs for farmer-to-farmer learning and technical assistance. As there is a lack of practical experience among farmers, good information on best practices is essential for a faster uptake of paludiculture crops.
- Develop decision-support tools to help farmers assess the financial viability of different paludiculture options.
- Strengthen networks between farmers, researchers, and policymakers.
- Increase practitioner involvement in policy discussions to ensure real-world relevance.

- Develop full-scale demonstration farms (e.g., 40 ha) to show paludiculture at commercial scale while also supporting smaller-scale, diverse models.

To whom:

1. Agricultural extension services and advisory bodies.
2. Ministries of Agriculture, Environment, and Finance.
3. Research institutions and universities.
4. Farmer associations, cooperatives, and NGOs.

Session 4: Exploring Carbon Farming approaches: Integrating circular solutions from biomass production & treatment to soil health and carbon sequestration

Main organisers: Agrimercarb, European Compost Network, Re-Cord, TGO AG, TierraSphere

Session description

The session presented different innovative and best-available techniques for transforming organic biomass and biowaste materials into valuable products (insect frass, compost, biochar), while locking carbon into the soil for the long term. The session also highlighted examples of how to integrate recycled materials into sustainable Carbon Farming practices to improve soil health and generate financial benefits for farmers. The discussion focused on the challenges to scale up innovative processes and to reach higher acceptance of the use of these waste-derived materials by farmers and consumers. A critical view of monitoring and verification methods for carbon credits was considered, covering both established and emerging approaches. Based on the discussion, the session provided recommendations on how biomass and biowaste-derived recycled materials can be sustainably used and how their use can be taken into account for restoring carbon under the Certification Framework for Carbon Removals.

Issues

- How to transform organic waste materials into valuable organic products used by farmers?
- How to promote the beneficial use of recycled bio-based materials in Carbon Farming?
- How can these recycled products and processes be integrated into carbon removals practices?
- How can carbon removals be properly accounted for, ensuring the development and implementation of solid carbon credit markets?

Recommendations

4.1. Concrete step for implementation

The black soldier fly (BSF) frass is a nutrient-rich organic fertilizer that improves soil fertility. It also increases soil organic matter and microbial activity. Its rapid decomposition cycle and nutrient retention capabilities make it a viable alternative to synthetic fertilizers. The BSF frass can be integrated into Carbon Farming frameworks by:

- Incentivizing adoption by farmers in the form of some tax exemptions or breaks etc.,

- Focussing on quantifying and certifying the carbon sequestration potential of BSF to increase its recognition in the carbon credit market and importantly,
- Demonstrating farmers how BSF frass can enhance soil organic matter and nutrient cycling.

To whom: Farmers, policymakers and researchers

4.2. Concrete step for implementation

- Incentivise the use of compost by farmers (ensuring that farmers currently using organic fertilisers will not be penalised by the future EU Carbon Farming certification)
- Increase communication on its benefits (communication and transparency from compost producers about the safety of their product despite deriving from waste, and need of support from policymakers to ensure product's compliance with national or EU regulations).
- Setting up quality assurance labels for compost.

To whom: Policymakers, compost producers, farmer advisories.

4.3. Concrete step for implementation

- Create market conditions to stimulate biochar production and use, in combination with compost, by farmers.
- Address both voluntary and obligated (EU ETS) markets.
- Implement solid monitoring actions to ensure product characterization and third-party verification of actual deployment in soil
- Create market instruments balancing offer and demand, ensuring value of BCR (Biochar Carbon Removals)

To whom: Policymakers and regulators

4.4. Lessons learnt

To establish Carbon Farming as a viable, profitable, and scientifically verified climate solution, a holistic Smart Carbon Farming (SCF) model that integrates precision monitoring, scalable sequestration strategies, and financial viability for farmers is proposed:

- Validated Carbon Farming Models for Scalable CO₂ Sequestration
- Precision Carbon Monitoring & Transparent Verification (MRV)
- Monetizing Carbon Farming for Farmers & Market Integration
- Building Trust Through High-Quality Certification & Open-Source Data

To whom: Farmers (Implementation of precision Carbon Farming methods), Carbon markets & financial institutions (Secure long-term value for removals), EU policymakers & CRCF certifiers (Aligning Smart Carbon Farming with EU regulations), Tech & research institutions (Further development of MRV automation).

4.5. Open questions

- Include inorganic carbon in CRCF discussions.
- Incentivize novel, holistic approaches that store carbon durably using residual biomass & waste, beyond current methods.
- Foster open communication to balance trade-offs in biomass use across sectors and carbon methodologies.

To whom: Policymakers

Session 5: Bringing Carbon Farming from science to organic and regenerative farms: Challenges and solutions across research, markets, farmer-led models and policy

Main organisers: FIBL, Justus Liebig University Giessen, ReGeneration, National Association of Producers for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, IFOAM Organics Europe

Session description

As Carbon Farming gains momentum in the fight against climate change, translating Carbon Farming into practical farm-level applications and financing mechanisms remains challenging. This session explored the complexities of Carbon Farming through the lenses of research, market-driven carbon credit systems, and farmer-led initiatives. The organisations presented their work related to Carbon Farming in particular on organic and regenerative farms. In the second part, a panel discussed the challenges ahead for Carbon Farming and potential solutions to support farmers in adopting climate- and eco-friendly farming.

Issues

- Methodological challenges and the way forward, considering differing farming systems, e.g.,:
 - Practice-based vs. measuring-based
 - Alignment of requirements for insetting / offsetting: Full farm approach
 - Methodological inclusion of other
- Considering the previous item from a scientific, market and political point of view
- Alternative solutions to a carbon credit market

Recommendations

5.1. Proposal to improve CRCF

Alignment with the most robust international methodologies to establish a strong framework that meets market expectations and maximizes value for farmers, supporting their transition. This includes:

- **Baseline:** Guarantees equal treatment of project-specific baselines to the standardised baseline, with the inclusion of a provision allowing operators the flexibility to choose between standardised baselines and activity-specific baselines in all circumstances.
- **Offset & Inset Use Cases:** Provide clear guidance for both intervention and inventory accounting to allow carbon unit issuance for various end uses.

- **Activity & Monitoring Period:** The developing methodology should require a minimum permanence period of 40 years (activity and monitoring period combined). Ensure the quality and permanence of carbon credits and allow sufficient time for regenerative farming transitions to deliver tangible benefits.

Other important aspects to consider in the regulatory framework:

- **Co-benefits:** Biodiversity and water (infiltration and pollution) should have their own methodologies and certification to properly value the overall environmental contributions of regenerative farmers.
- **Early adopters:** Create incentives to reward farmers for continuing to store carbon over time, even after sustainable practices have been in place for a long period and carbon storage has reached its maximum capacity.

To whom: EU Commission / Policymakers

5.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

Move towards practice-based compensations (e.g. reduced tillage) instead of result-based compensation (e.g. SOC sampling as baseline and improved practice) which have cross-benefits to other sustainability dimensions (e.g. for biodiversity, reduction of nutrient leakage) to acknowledge the efforts of climate-friendly soil pioneers.

To whom: EU Commission, Policymakers, Voluntary carbon market actors

5.3: Proposal to improve CRCF

Integrate other aspects (such as biodiversity, water management, production and socio-economic aspects) into the CFCR regulation as a tool for farm assessment and monitoring, in addition to soil carbon sequestration. This will allow farmers to have a complete picture of their farms, enabling them to build a solid and robust transition plan towards more climate resilient farming. Sole focus on sequestration can be detrimental to other farm-focuses.

The CRCF should ensure that Carbon Farming contributes to biodiversity and ecosystem protection and ensure that no practices are applied that harm other environmental dimensions. The mandatory co-benefit for biodiversity should either be assessed by several clear indicators for above and below ground biodiversity or by outlining a list of practices and farming systems for which there is clear scientific evidence for the contribution to biodiversity and ecosystem health and exclude practices that harm biodiversity.

To whom: EU Commission / Policymakers

Session 6: Carbon Farming, assured profitability? How to ensure the long-term sustainability of practices

Main organisers: ECAF, EURAF, University of Cordoba, University of Greifswald

Session description

The adoption of Carbon Farming practices is an important tool to combat climate change, improve soil health and promote agricultural sustainability across Europe. However, its long-term success depends on overcoming significant challenges, including economic feasibility, technical complexity, cultural acceptance and policy alignment. The session identified key strategies to ensure the sustainable implementation of Carbon Farming practices across Europe, bringing together different stakeholders (farmers, researchers, scientists, policymakers, NGOs and companies) to co-create actionable strategies to address these challenges.

The session was a co-creation workshop addressing specific issues, such as the lack of clear economic incentives, the complexity of measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration and the lack of technical knowledge among farmers. By bringing together practical experience, scientific evidence and policy perspectives, concrete solutions were discussed on the following topics

- Models for adapting Carbon Farming practices to the diversity of European pedoclimatic zones to ensure their success.
- Economic and environmental strategies to ensure the viability of the implementation of Carbon Farming practices.

Issues

- Long-term success of Carbon Farming practices
- Lack of clear economic incentives
- The complexity of measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration

Recommendations

6.1. Lesson learnt

Incentivising long-term commitment to Carbon Farming

Reversing Carbon Farming practices can quickly undo their environmental and climate benefits. The long-term success of these practices requires financial stability, clear long-term benefits, and consistent support policies. Incentives should not only target new adopters but

also reward early adopters and long-term practitioners to avoid disincentivizing those already engaged.

To whom: Policymakers, public administrations, and farmers and end users

6.2. Lesson learnt

Support economic sustainability through diversified incentives and fair market access

Carbon Farming practices can only be sustained long term if they are economically viable for farmers. Beyond environmental benefits, policies must help build resilient economic models by supporting early adopters, facilitating access to local and regional markets (e.g. for paludiculture or agroforestry products), and combining public subsidies with blended finance mechanisms. Recognising the time and risk investment involved in system change is essential to maintain farmer engagement and ensure long-term sustainability.

To whom: Policymakers, public administrations, and farmer organisations

6.3: Concrete step for implementation

Develop tailored methodologies and remove legal barriers to ensure long-term Carbon Farming adoption

The successful implementation and long-term maintenance of Carbon Farming practices require methodologies adapted to different land uses and regional conditions. Standardized approaches may fail to capture the variability in pedoclimatic zones, land tenure systems, or farming structures. Policies should promote flexible frameworks that allow for local adaptation while ensuring reliable monitoring, reporting, and verification systems. Additionally, legal barriers—such as restrictions on agroforestry integration, land tenure constraints, or limitations on peatland rewetting—must be addressed to enable farmers and landowners to adopt and sustain these practices without complex bureaucratic obstacles.

To whom: Policymakers, regulatory bodies, and land management authorities

6.4: Open question

Establish fair baseline methodologies to accurately measure carbon sequestration and soil health benefits

Measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration for soil health and productivity remains a major challenge. Reliable monitoring, reporting, and verification systems should not only quantify carbon stocks but also assess improvements in soil fertility, water retention, and resilience to climate stress. Additionally, ensuring a fair baseline is critical to avoid disadvantaging farmers who have already implemented sustainable practices. Current methodologies often compare landowners to their own historical data, which can penalize early adopters. A standardized yet flexible approach is needed to provide equitable incentives and facilitate the integration of Carbon Farming into market and policy frameworks.

To whom: Academia, research institutions, and policymakers

6.5. Concrete step for implementation

Improve access to technical knowledge and tools, and strengthen advisory services and peer-learning

The lack of technical knowledge and guidance remains a major barrier to the adoption and long-term maintenance of Carbon Farming practices. Farmers and landowners need continuous support, not only during the implementation phase but throughout the transition process. Policies should ensure the availability of advisory services that assist end users in decision-making, help resolve challenges, and provide technical guidance tailored to regional conditions. Additionally, peer-learning mechanisms should be promoted to facilitate knowledge exchange among farmers, enabling them to learn from both successes and failures in similar contexts.

To whom: Academia, advisory services, and agricultural training institutions

Session 7: CRCF business models

Main organisers: Aggroinsider, Agrosolutions, Carbone Farmers, Reframe, Eleks

Session description

To effectively advance Carbon Farming, business models should be central to the discussion. Farmers can focus on food production, CO₂ retention, fostering nature, or pursuing all the objectives. However, without clear and objective guidelines defining the value of CO₂ or/and nature, meaningful behavioural changes among farmers are unlikely, potentially jeopardizing the success of the European Carbon Farming strategy.

The session aimed to explore the tangible impact of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation on farm business models. How much compensation will farmers receive for the environmental services they provide? Will this value be sufficient to drive motivation, foster behavioural change, and support the transition of farms? What challenges might arise across Europe, considering variations in farm size, location, and production systems?

Issues

- When comparing current food production business models to those centred on CRCF environmental services (CO₂), what strategies can effectively motivate farmers to shift their behaviour toward prioritizing these services?
- How can farms of varying scales (large and small), production systems (dryland and irrigated, organic and conventional), and climates (Temperate and Mediterranean) develop sustainable business models that align with CO₂-related environmental services?
- **Innovative farming business models** are essential to address trade-offs between food production, CO₂, and biodiversity. For example, could selling food with a reduced environmental footprint (in terms of CO₂, biodiversity, and other metrics) at a premium price be a more viable alternative to selling CO₂ credits in the market?

Recommendations

7.1. Lesson learnt

After analysing hundreds of soil samples and conducting tree measurements in an agroforestry system as part of a European project, the following conclusions were drawn:

- i) On average, soil carbon sequestration services can store between 0.5 and 1.0 tons of CO₂ per hectare per year in a Mediterranean climate and between 1.0 and 2.0 tons of CO₂ per

hectare per year in a temperate climate, provided that best agricultural practices are implemented.

ii) On average, forest carbon sequestration services can capture between 2.0 and 5.0 tons of CO₂ per hectare per year.

Considering the current international CO₂ price of 5 to 10 €/ton, farmers could generate 10 to 20 €/ha annually from soil carbon services and 20 to 50 €/ha annually from forest carbon services.

However, when compared to the minimum baseline revenue from food production, which is approximately 300 €/ha annually, it is evident that the current CO₂ price is insufficient to make Carbon Farming and agroforestry systems (CRCF) economically attractive.

To bridge this gap, the CO₂ price would need to rise to approximately 150 €/ton to provide competitive incentives for farmers to adopt these practices.

7.2. Open questions

Small-scale farms face real barriers in entering the Carbon Credits market, from high costs and administrative hurdles to low interest from carbon platforms due to smaller volumes. Often, traditional systems that reward carbon footprint reductions overlook essential regenerative practices, like promoting biodiversity and enhancing soil health, which are core to sustainable farming but rarely credited. We want to explore the limitation of the **Carbon Credit Market as an incentive for small scale farmers to transition to more regenerative practices**, based on the Case Study of Juntos Farm located in Ibiza, and discuss pathways to change.

7.3 Concrete steps for implementation

Clear and verifiable criteria for Carbon Farming practices are required that will qualify for the “Carbon Farming Badge”.

A robust and transparent **certification process** is crucial to build consumer trust and ensure the integrity of the label. This standardisation should also consider variations in climate, farming practices, and regional contexts across Europe.

It is **important to educate consumers** about the benefits of supporting Carbon Farming through their purchasing choices. **Marketing and outreach campaigns** are needed to highlight the environmental and social benefits associated with products carrying the badge.

Training programmes for the farmers, providing technical assistance and ensuring access to relevant information and resources, are important to ensure that farmers have the knowledge to implement Carbon Farming practices. Additional support might include accessing financial resources to cover upfront costs associated with adopting Carbon Farming practices.

Governments must create a **supportive policy environment** for Carbon Farming, utilising financial incentives and robust regulations to ensure fairness, transparency, and consumer trust.

Session 8: Making Carbon Farming work for regions – Outlining adaptation needs and opportunities

Main organisers: Baltic Sea Action Group, BEC Bioeconomy Cluster

Session description

This session drew from regional Carbon Farming initiatives and regional cases through stakeholder discussions and aimed to outline considerations for the European Carbon Farming framework that fits in different regional contexts and supports regional objectives. It emphasized the integration of multiple objectives of food production in the regional context, aiming to connect regional authority, industry and farmer views and interests. Regional initiatives and emerging Living Labs were introduced to provide both priority issues and lessons, as well as concepts and platforms for developing and piloting approaches that align both with local needs and the EU policy frameworks (e.g. CRCF). The session covered the opportunities using the EU EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, project networks and living labs to collect tested best practice knowledge.

Issues

- Best ways to ensure that Carbon Farming schemes take into account and adapt to agronomic and landscape perspectives at regional level and contribute to local and regional objectives.
- Added values from publicly (government) lead initiatives to develop Carbon Farming capacities and knowledge on Carbon Farming scheme development and implementation so that specific regional contexts and needs are incorporated;
- Need to concretize values (economic, agronomic and environmental) for actors and secure needed knowledge and technical capacities.

Recommendations

8.1. Lesson learnt

CFS and national initiatives for carbon removal certification through Carbon Farming must adopt a multi-objective framework that supports sustainability transformation across various environmental, social, and economic dimensions. To achieve these targets, robust implementation and advisory structures are important, providing farmers with the guidance and resources needed to adopt sustainable practices successfully. A good idea is to encourage pioneers who started with CF early to become sample/pilot farms (lighthouses) and develop the mechanism to compensate these farmers for lessons-sharing, demonstration and advice. Learning from existing regional initiatives is essential for refining

Carbon Farming strategies. An inclusive approach that engages food processors, retailers, and policymakers alongside farmers can create sustainable pathways for Carbon Farming that benefit all stakeholders.

For whom: authorities, agricultural AKIS, food industry

8.2. Concrete step for implementation

Instruments like EIP Operational Groups and Horizon Europe Living Labs create valuable opportunities to develop and test pilots that can address specific regional challenges, fostering innovation and collaboration within the agricultural community. They can be used to synthesize knowledge on regionally tested context adapted practices. These can also serve as a starting point for the development of group projects.

For whom: authorities, farmers' associations, research institutes

8.3. Concrete steps for implementation

Leveraging the public, government lead initiatives to develop Carbon Farming scheme capacities can help navigate sub-regional and regulatory diversity and tap into needed implementation and governance capacities. Empowering the local governments and stakeholders to innovate within a supportive national framework is essential for accelerating progress. It is essential to translate the EU Framework into actionable strategies for the regions.

For whom: farmers, Carbon Farming programme developers, carbon market actors, authorities

8.4. Lesson learnt

Communicate with farmers and foresters clearly and transparently the implications of carbon certification contracts and other commitments, such as sustainability incentive programs with the food industry. Selling carbon credits for compensation or to an external buyer voids any contribution to value chain or regional climate targets. Carbon credit markets present a significant risk, especially in the context of supporting local and regional needs and value chains. Very important is to maintain a holistic perspective (regions' and farmers' perspective) and clarify boundaries of the CRCF and define its incremental value.

For whom: farmers, Carbon Farming programme developers, carbon market actors, authorities

8.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Concretize the values (economic, agronomic, environmental, risk mitigation) for the landowners and practitioners to increase interest. Developing standardized methods for assessing carbon sequestration and biodiversity impacts across various agricultural contexts would facilitate greater transparency and trust in Carbon Farming initiatives. Understanding the socio-economic conditions that influence farmers' willingness to engage in Carbon

Farming is crucial for designing effective incentive structures. Knowledgeable and holistic farm management advice can help find optimal way to incorporate Carbon Farming practises in order to maximize their agronomic and economic value.

For whom: agricultural AKIS, advisory services, project developers

Session 9: Farmers' prospect: How does Carbon Farming affect crop production, and farm biodiversity and profitability?

Main organiser: CREAM

Session description

It has often been said that Carbon Farming is at odds with crop and pasture productivity. However, many innovative farmers have taken the plunge of modifying their management strategies to embrace sustainability by sequestering carbon in soils and vegetation. Changes from intensive to sustainable agriculture can be more or less far-reaching, and ranges from adopting single practices (e. g. tillage reduction/elimination, cover crops) or combinations of several of them to modifying drastically the economics, organization structure and social ethics at a scale that exceeds that of the farm. This session dedicated to farmers' view of this debate was organized with farmers and farmer associations to explain their experience with farm productivity and profitability and with conserving or enhancing environmental services in their farms.

Questions brought to the discussion were (a) in which direction science and technology should progress to support farmers in optimizing global environmental and monetary benefits while adopting C farming strategies, (b) what kind of partnerships are needed to optimize the benefits of Carbon Farming for farmers and which stakeholders should be involved? (c) which realistic indicators can be proposed to evaluate success in Carbon Farming adoption at the farm scale?

Issues

- The indicators currently used to evaluate farmer's satisfaction and willingness to adopt C farming are not satisfactory
- Environmental constraints to adopt Carbon Farming are region-specific, as is the effort required to obtain a carbon credit
- Shortage in biomass of good quality can limit Carbon Farming at the European level and, in particular in dry regions
- Carbon Farming practices can be at odds with biodiversity protection at the landscape scale if current demand for animal food remains stable.

Recommendations

9.1. Choose correct indicators to evaluate farmer's satisfaction and willingness to adopt Carbon Farming

Farm profitability (instead of crop yield) and farm global resilience are crucial for farmers to adopt Carbon Farming.

- Profitability must be evaluated under an integrated WEF E Nexus concept. Short term valuations can produce high costs vs long-term evaluations, hopefully profitable (Timeline – local specificity)
- Our focus group strongly advocates for a holistic management plan, covering the period necessary for the adaptation of crops to the new form of management, before the implementation of carbon projects. A correct economic valuation of the farm profitability during this period (including inversions, and yield decline but also savings associated with reduced use of agrochemical and commercial fertilizers will prevent misunderstanding about extra costs in the mid- and long-term.
- It is necessary to finance the transition period from conventional to regenerative management in which losses can occur.
- Carbon sequestration should not be pursued without taking into consideration the effects of the integrated management on biodiversity and environmental services (e.g. water quality, soil protection, etc.) provided by farmlands, that must be evaluated based on specific indicators
- Carbon programs must contribute to increased economic sustainability, not through further spread of subsidies, but through consolidation of the farm business.
- Income security and longer contracts must be guaranteed

To whom: Decision makers, researchers, farmers' advisors

9.2. Consider selective compensation for Carbon Farming depending on constraints

- Farmers implementing C farming under adverse conditions (such as aridity, or soils) incur greater production losses during the period of crop adaptation, and this period lasts longer, than farmers operating under better conditions. In the same line, achieving the same increase in soil C will cost more effort under adverse conditions than under more favorable conditions. This will suggest negative discrimination for farmers operating under adverse conditions if we reward based on outcomes only. C credits should have different values depending on this difference
- Design region-based supporting actions to take into account spatial differences and reinforce training in the most threatening areas.
- It is not enough just to pay for C sequestration; compensations for increased resilience, environmental services (i.e. biodiversity, water retention) should also be used as levers. Actions aimed at C sequestration that have negative consequences on biodiversity and environmental services should be penalized, under the “Polluter pay” principle

To whom: Decision makers

9.3. Be sure that we have enough biomass of good quality to implement Carbon Farming practices on the European scale

- Support policies that facilitate the closing of organic matter loops at the farm and local level, ensuring sufficient biomass availability for Carbon Farming. Incentivize crop rotations, cover crops, animal integration, and agroforestry, with specific training programs for farmers.
- Support the transition to Mixed Farming Systems as a key strategy for organic matter cycling, ensuring a balance between crops and livestock. Develop financial and advisory support to assist farmers in transitioning towards sustainable mixed farming systems.
- Enhance agricultural sustainability and circularity. Invest in technologies for better organic matter management, such as composting innovations and precision nutrient management.
- Foster collaborative initiatives where farmers and stakeholders can share challenges and best practices for managing organic matter locally. Promote regional and cross-sector cooperation to develop local business models for organic matter valorization.
- Adopt a holistic and value chain approach: ensure that policies consider the entire value chain, from production to processing and reuse of organic matter. Address regional gaps where organic matter cycling businesses are lacking, supporting new circular economy initiatives.
- Improve biomass transport and storage efficiency: Support long-term composting to reduce organic matter water content, minimizing transport costs and inefficiencies.
- Align CRCF with organic matter cycling: Ensure that livestock and biomass considerations are integrated into Carbon Farming certification frameworks, addressing current gaps.

To whom: Decision makers, researchers, land managers and planners

9.4. How does the implementation of biodiversity measures affect farm profitability? How to improve it at the EU level

- Farmers are willing to move towards Carbon Farming if there is a demand for regenerative agriculture products. Carbon credits will also help, but farmers do not want their efforts to be sold to the same companies that cause damage to the environment.
- Biodiversity increases profitability in the context of disturbance, strengthens functional redundancy, and reduces risk. The CRCF methodologies should be designed such that they maximise biodiversity gains through Carbon Farming practices.
- Promote the diversification of farm production to increase agricultural biodiversity and help stabilize profitability. Biodiversity in crop types is the best way to have a buffer.
- Seek out policy coherence to enhance synergies between nature conservation and restoration and farm profitability: adapt the legal framework, reinforce CAP measures addressing integrated Eco-schemes.
- Coordinated efforts of the scientific community should be stimulated in order to find measurable indicators applicable to the farm scale.

To whom: Decision makers, land managers and planners

Session 10: The future of regional small-scale Carbon Farming projects: Discuss bottom-up experiences and align farmer and market perspectives

Main organisers: Boerenbond, ZLTO, Bax Company

Session description

While the rules and regulations on Carbon Farming are still taking shape (EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation), there are already many different certificates and certification methodologies in place. Each with their own set of rules and prices. Since 2020 farmers organisations, Boerenbond and ZLTO, are in lead or involved in local Carbon Farming rewarding mechanisms in Belgium and the Netherlands. They shared their field experience from 2 running examples of Carbon Farming projects and collected experience, concerns and solutions from the audience. With a new European certification regulation in development, the results of this workshop aimed to give small-scale initiatives a voice.

Issues

- Experience sharing in the business model for small scale Carbon Farming projects with special attention for the point of view of participating and potential participating farmers as well as the buyers point of view
- Policy recommendations necessary to convince both more farmers and buyers to participate in Carbon Farming (Ensure that CRCF will boost this market, provide clarity about (potential) interfering policies and make sure that first movers are involved and rewarded).
- Concerns and recommendations in regard to CRCF MRV high costs and administration: Make sure that Carbon Farming remains financially feasible by keeping MRV costs low and make it feasible for farmers to meet the reporting demands. Clear recommendation: CRCF should foresee a separate, less heavy (and thus costly) certification system for these local initiatives

Recommendations

10.1. Lessons learnt

FOR FARMERS

Be aware that farmers that are currently active in business cases for Carbon Farming are in it due to different reasons. Foremost due the intrinsic motivation of the benefits for their soils and thus farms. Next to this, farmers that participate in local small-scale collaborations value

the one on one connection with their buyer(s), which creates a better mutual understanding and also a social appreciation. The financial incentive for CF is nonetheless crucial in order to be able to take their actions to the next level and in order to feel supported in their efforts.

In order to scale up the small-cases and to involve more local farmers, the financial incentive might take a bigger role in their consideration.

There is a big question mark and uncertainty in what is the best way to go forward: insetting vs. offsetting. For insetting cases, farmers have the fear that the financial incentive will be only available on a very short term basis and might also be lower in price setting.

FOR BUYERS

Participating buyers have a big appreciation for the local and personal aspect in small-scale Carbon Farming cases. They participate due to the contact they have with the farmers as well as it feels less risky because it is more tangible and nearby.

To whom: Regional and European policymakers and stakeholders in the agri-food chain and abroad.

10.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

1) Ensure that CRCF will boost this market:

CRCF is very welcome to create trust among potential buyers of Carbon Farming credits. If Europe creates this framework, it shows them that Europe believes in this potential. Yet, communication and clarity about the possibilities of CRCF to the industry will be of essence to make CF succeed.

2) Provide clarity about (potential) interfering policies:

Yet, both farmers as potential buyers have many questions regarding (climate) policy. How do the following policy actions and goals interfere with each other and how do we prevent future mistakes and potential penalties?

- Climate target goals for farmers
- Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU)
- CRCF
- CSRD

Is there a difference in potential risk between insetting vs. offsetting?

3) Make sure that first movers are involved and rewarded

CRCF will also need to provide an answer to the following concern at farm level:

Will farmers that have already worked on their soils and pioneered be able to participate in Carbon Farming? This will be very important in order to show to farmers that Europe also values the stored carbon and their past efforts.

To whom: CRCF and European policymakers that work on climate target goals, green deal, CSRD and AFOLU

10.3. Concrete steps for implementation

- Make sure that Carbon Farming remains financially feasible by keeping MRV costs low and make it feasible for farmers to meet the reporting demands
- Many small-scale cases have a big fear that CRCF will lead to high demands in regard to MRV, which will then result in both high costs as well as specific software to report. This will lead to the quitting of small-scale and local examples. Possible solution:
- CRCF should foresee a separate, less heavy (and thus costly) certification system for these local initiatives
- These small-scale initiatives are very valuable and we must prevent them from not being able to continue due to too high costs for MRV and too much administration.
- This separate system should focus on integrity and more room for frontrunners. In small-scale cases farmer and buyer know each other, so there is more transparency and less risk.

To whom: CRCF policymakers/developers and expert group

Session 11: The role of advisors in climate action in Europe

Main organisers: Teagasc, Consulai, Intiasa, ILVO

Session description

Farm advisors are positioned to play a crucial role in the agricultural transition, acting as the vital link between farmers, researchers and policymakers by translating policies and strategies into actionable practices while also providing valuable feedback from farmers to inform policy making and guide new research.

However, they require support and training to effectively fulfil this role, particularly in emerging areas like Carbon Farming and carbon markets, where their current expertise is limited. Trusted by farmers, advisors already recommend climate smart practices but face challenges such as varying levels of knowledge across regions and the need to minimize the burden of data collection by reusing existing data effectively.

This session provided a comprehensive overview of the current role of farm advisors in climate action, while also identifying areas for future development, including advisor capacity building and the availability of user friendly decision support tools.

Issues

- What motivates farmers to climate action?
- How can advisors successfully engage and motivate EU farmers to climate action? What advisory skills are required and what are the training needs of EU farm advisors?
- How can user-friendly, practical and accessible decision support tools be used by advisors and farmers? What are the key requirements of such tools?
- What climate action rewarding mechanisms are currently available? How are these being promoted by farm advisors and used by farmers?

Recommendations

11.1. Lessons learnt

Understanding and Leveraging Farmer Motivation for Climate Action

Understanding the diverse motivations of farmers is key to effective advisory in promoting climate action. Farmers are motivated by a variety of factors, including financial incentives, autonomy, trusted sources of information, firsthand experience, emotional and cultural factors, and social proof through peer learning. Advisors must be trained to recognise and engage with these motivations, tailoring their advice to align with what drives each farmer.

By addressing these motivations, advisors can encourage greater adoption of climate-smart practices and help build long-term sustainability on farms.

To whom: Advisory Services

11.2. Lessons learnt

Strengthening the Role of Farm Advisors in Promoting Climate Action

Farm advisors are key agents in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) for promoting Carbon Farming.

To whom: National/Regional Governments

11.3 Concrete steps for implementation

Strengthening the Role of Farm Advisors in Promoting Climate Action

Advisors need structured training on the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) and relevant regulations.

To whom: National/Regional Governments

11.4. Lessons learnt

What do farm advisors need in order to support farmers with rewarding mechanisms?

- Farm advisors need access to knowledge and capacity building on carbon removal certification and carbon market tools, as well as on other rewarding mechanisms or incentives available to farmers.
- The level of awareness of rewarding mechanisms, the level of economic advisory skills, and the way farm advisors engage with farmers on financial topics vary across EU countries. As a result, the level of investment in capacity building needs to be adapted. In some cases, communication from rewarding entities (governments or value chain actors) should also be improved to make sure farmers and farm advisors are aware of potential funding and support.
- Clarity, transparency, credibility, and fairness are key for farm advisors and farmers to engage with rewarding mechanisms.
- Farm advisors need to be able to explain requirements, risks, and potential benefits linked to each rewarding mechanism, as well as how to use different mechanisms in combination. To do this, they need practical examples and rationales demonstrating clear added value to motivate farmers. They should also facilitate demonstration and peer-to-peer learning.
- In general, farm advisors need to be better equipped to help farmers calculate the cost of inaction, and to assess the economic effects (both positive and negative) of climate adaptation or mitigation measures in the long run, in their local context.

To whom: Advisory services, Governments, Value chain actors

11.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Developing and Deploying Practical Decision Support Tools: Advisors and farmers need user-friendly, practical, and accessible decision support tools.

To whom: Advisory services, National/Regional Governments

Session 12: Ensuring sustainability outcomes from Carbon Farming: Recommendations for the CRCF and voluntary carbon markets

Main organiser: Ecologic Institute

Session description

This session discussed how the Carbon Farming certification can best ensure broader sustainability benefits, including climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation.

Carbon Farming has significant potential to support the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices that contribute not only to climate change mitigation but also other sustainability objectives. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) aims to establish a new high standard for voluntary Carbon Farming actions, including minimum sustainability requirements.

In this session, these minimum sustainability requirements were discussed and recommendations were prepared on how they can best be put into action through the CRCF and in voluntary carbon markets.

Issues

- Enhancing sustainability through certification: How the Carbon Farming certification can best ensure broader sustainability benefits
- Increasing demand for sustainable farming: Is there demand for sustainability outcomes from Carbon Farming and where does it come from
- Supporting farmers through certification: How can certification enable farmers to deliver sustainability benefits alongside mitigation?

Recommendations

12.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Carbon Farming certification must support broad sustainability objectives. Carbon Farming practices do not just affect the climate, they also impact other sustainability outcomes, including biodiversity, soil health, and water.

To whom: Policymakers

12.2. Concrete steps for implementation

To meet CRCF minimum sustainability requirements, farmers should complete a “farm environment plan,” which should be supported by a farm advisor, be low-cost for farmers, and support adoption of sustainable farming practices – without requiring it. In addition, a

negative list of excluded high-risk actions could avoid Carbon Farming actions that pose high risks to sustainability.

To whom: Policymakers

12.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

To incentivise co-benefits beyond minimum requirements, the CRCF should support market price premiums by **creating a voluntary “CRCF Sustainability+” label**, based on farmer self-assessment of sustainability indicators, supported by random third-party audits. Additionally, the CRCF should support the development of robust and low-cost methods for voluntary quantification of sustainability impacts.

To whom: Policymakers

12.4. Proposals to improve CRCF

Consider the six principles for ensuring sustainability in the context of Carbon Farming:

1. **Holistic approach:** Carbon Farming should incentivise a holistic and context-specific approach to farm management that promotes sustainable outcomes and avoids unintended negative sustainability impacts, whilst prioritising climate mitigation.
2. **Accessibility:** Participation costs for farmers must be minimised to ensure that it is financially attractive for farmers to implement sustainable measures. Financial support should be provided to early adopters of Carbon Farming practices, e.g. for advisory services and MRV, or in the form of offtake agreements.
3. **Pragmatism:** A pragmatic approach should be taken to ensuring sustainability through Carbon Farming certification to reduce the barriers to farmer participation and promote farmer uptake, e.g. integrating existing management and monitoring systems.
4. **Incentives:** Farmers should be rewarded for the sustainability impacts of Carbon Farming, which will be enabled by robust monitoring of impacts.
5. **Consistency:** Carbon Farming certification approaches to sustainability should be consistent and comparable to facilitate market demand.
6. **Integrity:** Certification must deliver buyers robust sustainability impact information, using metrics and indicators that are valuable to them. The CRCF must also manage buyer claims, to ensure they align with the sustainability impacts delivered.

To whom: Policymakers

Session 13: Global or local? Carbon certification centralisation level: what implications for stakeholders?

Main organisers: Institute for Climate Economics (I4CE), AC3A

Session description

Numerous Carbon Farming certification schemes are already operating in Europe with stakeholders involved in certified projects. The CRCF is a great opportunity to gather funding for climate-compatible practices in the land-use sector and contribute to the agriculture sector transition. It will help harmonize and improve practices and create a larger market to reward farmers' actions. However, it raises the question of how to bring coherence and improvement at the EU level, while building on what already exists and keep involving the stakeholders who are already implementing Carbon Farming?

This session discussed the results of a survey by AC3A and I4CE to gather feedback from stakeholders on the implications of different scenarios of governance for the future Carbon Farming certification framework. The survey gathered their inputs on what would be the strengths and challenges of different centralisation options (very centralized at EU level, or relying on existing standards at national level or local level), for several certification steps: methodology creation, methodology validation, project validation, audits, GHG assessment tools, registry... It also asked for their general feedback on the conditions on which the CRCF would be attractive to farmers and buyers in those different scenarios.

Issues

Implications of different scenarios of governance for the future Carbon Farming certification framework.

Recommendations

13.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON METHODOLOGIES

1. Set as many rules as possible in the common European methodologies to have them consistent across the EU and to make economies of scale: highly prescriptive methodologies reduce project development and auditing costs and limit the risk of bias and information asymmetry between the regulator and the project developer.

2. To be adapted to local issues/specificities and to have more room for innovation, specific protocols can be proposed by certification schemes but:

- The methodology developer must demonstrate the value of proposing this specific protocol
- Where the schemes operate, Member States have to be involved to ensure the credibility/robustness/independence/coherence with national regulations of the protocols.
- Protocols of different schemes operating in the same Member State must have the same level of requirement to ensure that operators do not play with the rule by choosing the most favorable one.

3. As UNFCCC reporting methodology differs among Member States, allow MS to refine methodologies with models or emission factors that are used in their LULUCF reporting to promote consistency between regulations.

4. As it is not possible to have everything right from the first time, ensure to have frequent review processes of the methodologies, involving independent researchers/ consultants/ experts.

13.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON GHG ASSESSMENT TOOLS

GHG emission tools: Emission reduction calculator using models and parameters provided by methodologies and protocols.

- Tools are regularly audited to ensure that they take account of changes in methodologies and remain consistent.
- Tools are validated by the commission (equity between MS), on condition that sufficient resources and expertise are made available (economies of scale should make this possible), and after consulting the member states (especially for local tools).

13.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON PROJECT VALIDATION

1. The more precise the rules, the lower the validation costs.
2. In this respect, more precise recommendations at the level of methodologies and protocols seem necessary to gain in precision, avoid any confusion and “gaming” and to lower transaction cost by facilitating project development.
3. Case of specific baselines: In the case where standardised baselines could not be implemented in the first years, project developers will use specific baselines and will need to demonstrate the choice of the baseline additionality. This needs more scrutiny from certification bodies. MS could play a role here to define parameters for additionality tests or to provide a list of credible specific scenarios within the country.

13.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATION ON THE REGISTRY

1. A unique European registry fully managed by the EC would allow economies of scale, avoid risk of double counting and facilitate the purchase of carbon credits by trans-EU companies.

13.5. Proposals to improve CRCF

1. It is crucial to dedicate a sufficient budget to remunerate independent experts and consultants who will have to scrutinize methodologies, perform checks on projects and certification bodies (=auditors)
2. There is a need to clarify the different possible processes from the methodology development to certification of removals emission reductions in detail in order to evaluate the feasibility, risk and cost of these options. But also to define the final governance scenario to bring visibility to existing standard

13.6. Proposals to improve CRCF

There is a need to consider the business model of the CRCF in order to refine the governance rules. Assessing the transaction costs of different governance scenarios and certification processes could help to find the right balance between robustness and reasonable administrative burden. Identifying how each stakeholder in the process is remunerated will help to avoid conflicts of interest. Assessing the critical size of a group of farmers, for example, will also help to ensure that group certification is a good option for reducing the administrative burden.

Session 14: The value chain challenge: Scaling scope 3 solutions

Main organisers: Mars Inc., Friesland Campina, Lakeland Dairies, Soil Capital

Session description

It is increasingly clear that unlocking the potential of Carbon Farming will be key for the agri-food value chain to achieve their Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) goals. Carbon Farming contributes to compensating greenhouse gas emissions at farm level by removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and reducing GHG emissions from soils and hence will be part of the solution to achieve those targets. Yet there are still challenges for Carbon Farming and practices contributing to greenhouse gas reduction at farm level to scale.

This session brought together stakeholders from the dairy and cereal value chains that have committed to reduce their scope 3 emissions and are already taking actions to support farmers to achieve their reductions. Its aim was to discuss how a robust policy framework could contribute to further unlock the potential of Carbon Farming in the EU.

Issues

- What are the financial needs and available options for farmers to adopt Carbon Farming, and how can CRCF support this transition?
- What are the additional requirements and benefits from Carbon Farming, including soil health, biodiversity and environmental impacts, and how can these be reported and communicated transparently?
- How can existing and potential new policies and schemes contribute to scaling Carbon Farming (CAP, Green Claims Directive, CSRD, new policies to incentivize climate-change mitigation across the agri-food value chain)?

Recommendations

14.1. Funding of Carbon Farming

- Funding is key for scope 3 solutions to scale: whilst CRCF could help bring additional trust to private funding, it won't be sufficient. Considering public funding, by strategically leveraging CAP's budget from eco-schemes, EIB budget, public procurement will be key.
- Public funding should be designed and deployed to further attract private funding for instance by unlocking public-private partnerships to encourage value chain partnerships
- Moreover, public funds could support farmers in overcoming barriers to access the private market by making MRV and/or advisory services as a public service.

- Private funding would then complement those public fundings by rewarding the outcome.
- It will also be important to expand CRCF to other GHG to address other supply chains (e.g. dairy).

14.2. Improve CRCF and clarify use of certificates

- For Carbon Farming a value-chain approach should be prioritized, aligned with the GHG Protocol.
- Incorporation of the CRCF into existing legislations is needed:
 - CSRD – need to clarify rules for carbon sequestration achieved within value-chain/scope 3, aligning rules with international standard like GHG-Protocol
 - CAP – CRCF could be used as a standard under eco-schemes
 - Green Claims Directive – need to ensure rules are EU harmonized, simple and clear to keep incentivizing the private sector to invest into Carbon Farming.
 - Potentially future legislations (agriETS, mandatory scope 3 targets) should also consider CRCF
- For the purpose of CRCF and Green Claims it will also be important to consider international schemes from outside the EU, beyond CRCF.

Session 15: Insetting for Carbon Farming: Turning challenges into opportunities for farmers, food companies and policymakers

Main organisers: Friesland Campina, ILVO, Rabobank, UCLouvain, ZLTO

Session description

Insetting offers a credible alternative for scaling up Carbon Farming by enabling farmers to adopt practices that enhance soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration. Offtakers integrate the sequestered carbon into the carbon footprint of products within the value chain. While insetting provides income opportunities for farmers, it also faces challenges like financial burden and administrative burdens for farmers and food value chain companies, and lack of market regulation. The European Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) could establish essential standards for insetting, but must address all stakeholders' needs.

This session examined the implications of insetting for SOC sequestration in agriculture, providing a platform to share experiences and understand its practical application. Expert presentations explained insetting, how to engage, and explore the impact of available protocols, policies and MRV systems. It concluded by identifying stakeholder needs, highlighting gaps in the CRCF framework and Scope 3 protocol, and proposing actionable policy recommendations

Recommendations

15.1 Concrete steps for implementation

Companies should set targets and allocate budgets to achieve them, including mechanisms to reward farmers. Companies with voluntary commitments should implement these targets and budgets before project implementation. Standards and protocols could incorporate these criteria as part of the project description document.

To whom: Companies, policy by providing framework and guidelines, accounting standards setting like GHG Protocol

15.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

CRCF could represent an overarching scheme to support Insetting

- Establishing a unified framework for Carbon Farming, integrating offsetting, insetting, and CAP schemes.
- Creating a single registry to prevent double counting and improve claim tracking.
- Enhancing sustainability reporting with standardised and transparent methodologies.
- Leveraging public-private funding mechanisms to scale up insetting initiatives.

To do so, the panel session identified the following recommendations:

- Developing a universal benchmarking system for farm sustainability reporting.
- Clarifying insetting's role within the CRCF with clear rules on allocation and inventory accounting.
- Adopting a holistic sustainability approach that incorporates soil health, water conservation, and biodiversity.
- Defining the market demand for the CRCF and its role in emissions reduction efforts.

To whom: Companies, policy by providing framework and guidelines, accounting standards setting like GHG Protocol

15.3. Lessons learnt

Reduce financial and administrative burden by designing CRCF protocols based on evidence and ground-level realities.

The session highlighted key pathways to achieve this:

1. Designing CRCF protocols based on evidence and ground-level realities
2. Digital MRV Systems – The need for automated digital Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems to simplify processes and reduce time requirements.
3. Standardized Reporting – A unified reporting system where CRCF-associated certificates could serve as a foundation for other nature-based solutions.
4. Single Benchmarking System – A harmonized benchmarking system with standardized sustainability indicators for farms, aligning with the EU Commission's new [*Vision for Food and Agriculture*](#).

To whom: Farmer unions, companies, policy maker, accounting standards

15.4. Open questions

Establish clear rules for insetting, including definitions, perimeters, allocation protocols, and climate benefit claims.

Currently, there are no established rules for Scope 3 emissions and SBTi regarding insetting, particularly for rotational and multiple cropping systems. This lack of regulation leads to transparency issues.

To whom: Companies, farmer union, policymaker, standard developer

15.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Ensure Insetting Includes a Binding Reward Mechanism Between Farmers and Agri-Food Companies Insetting should establish a binding reward mechanism, such as the ‘right to report,’ to ensure fair compensation for farmers. Some protocols, like the GHG Protocol, do not specify how companies should reward farmers or on what basis, leading to transparency gaps. Key considerations include who has the right to report emissions within the value chain and how farmers are rewarded for their contributions. While some regulations already address this issue, the CRCF could serve as a framework to formalize agreements, ensuring that carbon credits are either sold from farmers to companies or structured through clear contractual arrangements

To whom: Farmer union, policymaker, agrifood-companies

15.6. Concrete steps for implementation

Mitigation of Costs & Risks for Farmers before the Start of a Project:

First, conduct an ex-ante assessment of insetting projects to evaluate risks and costs for farmers. Insetting initiatives should be financially viable for farmers, ensuring that the risks and costs they bear are properly accounted for and that they can secure a margin. An ex-ante assessment is essential to evaluate key factors such as how farmers can achieve profitability, potential risks related to carbon emission reductions should be identified in advance, and the consequences if emissions are claimed but ultimately released. Clear guidelines should be established to protect farmers from financial or regulatory liabilities.

Ensure public mechanism to support upfront costs for farmers: To ensure farmers can capture value from the insetting market, mechanisms using public funding should be established to cover the costs farmers will incur to access private sector schemes under the CRCF, such as appropriate soil analysis, GHG baselining, or benefiting from necessary technical support, all of which should be covered upfront.

To whom: Farmer unions, policymakers, companies

Session 16: Unlocking the potential of soil biodiversity: Sustainable land management, restoration, and revenue generation

Main organisers: Cà Colonna srl, Carboneg, Land Life

Session description

In the evolving landscape of Carbon Farming, soil biodiversity represents an untapped opportunity to amplify ecosystem resilience, climate adaptability, and overall environmental health. Restoring and leveraging soil biodiversity offers a transformative opportunity to enhance ecosystem services, improve land productivity, and unlock new revenue streams. This session explored how soil biodiversity can drive sustainable practices while delivering tangible economic and environmental benefits.

The session discussed how soil biodiversity underpins critical ecosystem functions such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, carbon sequestration, and plant productivity. Using real-world examples, including Land Life's biodiversity pilot in the Iberian Peninsula, it highlighted the importance of setting baselines and using innovative tools like environmental DNA (eDNA) for measuring biodiversity impact. It also examined how rewards of biodiversity-enhancing practices can support carbon sequestration.

Finally, it delved into the policy and financial mechanisms essential for scaling biodiversity restoration. By examining emerging regulatory frameworks such as the EU's Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) and Verra's Nature Framework pilot, the session explored how biodiversity metrics can complement carbon markets to create verified, qualified assets that align with market and policy demands.

Issues

- Soil biodiversity enhances ecosystem services and should be a key consideration to avoid a narrow focus on carbon. Both climate and nature need to be improved to restore planetary health.
- Biodiversity measurement is local and multifaceted, whereas carbon is global and measured with a single metric.
- Integrating biodiversity activities into carbon projects demands resources, which can reduce efficiencies and lower the return on investment.
- Current carbon credit pricing inadequately reflects biodiversity benefits, failing to sufficiently incentivize farmers, foresters, and project developers. The biodiversity market is currently too underdeveloped to offer these incentives.
- Given the rapid loss of biodiversity and its impact on ecosystem services, immediate, pragmatic action is crucial to incentivize biodiversity practices effectively.

Recommendations

16.1. Lessons learnt

1. Standardize biodiversity measurement and verification through scientifically rigorous indicators such as eDNA and site-specific baseline assessments. The practical insights gained from the Land Life Biodiversity pilot project in the Iberian Peninsula demonstrates how biodiversity initiatives can complement and elevate carbon strategies.
2. EU CRCF should recognize the unique role that carbon sequestration via reforestation plays in biodiversity and structurally support it.

To whom: EU policymakers & regulatory bodies – To integrate biodiversity metrics into regulations, Carbon credit certifiers & standard-setters – To enhance biodiversity verification and Nature Credit methodologies, Carbon credit buyers

16.2. Concrete step for implementation

Establish integrated biodiversity and carbon credit incentives to financially reward farmers for implementing biodiversity-positive agricultural practices. This should be supported by scalable programs that link biodiversity gains to economic benefits through biodiversity credit markets.

To whom: EU Commission & National Governments – To incorporate biodiversity incentives into agricultural policies, Farmers & agricultural cooperatives – To adopt biodiversity-enhancing practices and participate in credit programs.

16.3. Open questions

Create economic valuation models for soil biodiversity to support the development of biodiversity credits and sustainable finance mechanisms. This will help integrate soil biodiversity restoration into the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) while ensuring market-driven incentives for conservation.

To whom: EU Commission & Agricultural Policymakers – To incorporate soil biodiversity valuation into CRCF policies, Research Institutions & Agronomic Experts – To refine valuation models and identify high-risk ecosystems, Farmers, Landowners & Private Sector Investors – To implement soil biodiversity restoration strategies and engage in biodiversity-linked financial programs.

16.4. On biodiversity in CRCF

- Integrating carbon and biodiversity credits into a unified framework would make it simpler for customers and developers, potentially kickstarting the biodiversity market. However, this integration must uphold integrity to ensure biodiversity is appropriately valued and not diluted. For instance, consider a multi-credit bundle with separate carbon and biodiversity credits, rather than a carbon credit that superficially

claims biodiversity co-benefits without adhering to specific practices, providing measurement nor confirmed impact.

- Recognizing different degrees of biodiversity impact —ranging from minor enhancements within productive contexts to significant improvements within natural ecosystem contexts — to encourage going beyond the minimum "do no harm" standard outlined by the EU CRCF.
- Farming, timber, and natural ecosystem restoration are distinct activities that should be treated separately.

16.5. On Nature-based solutions in CRCF

- Adopting a like-for-like approach risks fragmenting the carbon market between engineered solutions (eligible for fuel-based and biogenic emissions) and nature-based solutions (limited to biogenic emissions only). This would severely limit the capital available for essential nature-based carbon projects in the EU, especially as there is no biodiversity market nor compliance framework at the moment. It is recommended not to mandate like-for-like or to do so only for a portion of fuel-based emissions.
- Clarifying the connection between the EU CRCF and the EU NRL would improve understanding among stakeholders regarding their collaborative function.
- Establishing an EU compliance framework for biodiversity restoration, targeting sectors with negative land impacts, could channel necessary capital into nature restoration. The UK's Biodiversity Net Gain, along with programs in Australia and California, could serve as models.

Session 17: Multi-stakeholder networks and participatory approaches for successful Carbon Farming and soil health monitoring – Opportunities and challenges

Main organisers: Commonland Foundation, EIT Food South, Wetlands international

Session description

This session aimed to support the ongoing development of the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation by addressing key questions about how to effectively implement Carbon Farming across landscapes involving multiple stakeholders and with a focus on different ecosystems (wetlands ecosystems and agro-ecosystems in semi-arid regions).

Three real-world case studies supported the discussion, showcasing multi-stakeholder initiatives in Carbon Farming from Southern Europe in these ecosystems.

The session explored lessons learned, challenges faced by on-the-ground actors, and the potential for Carbon Farming projects to deliver multiple benefits for both nature and local communities. In addition, the session identified knowledge gaps and offered concrete recommendations to advance the operationalisation of the CRCF framework, aiming at laying the foundation for actionable solutions that can be considered in the next stages of CRCF implementation.

Issues

- Multi-stakeholder networks for scaling Carbon Farming and achieving co-benefits
- Blended finance for Carbon Farming
- The role of mediterranean wetlands as carbon sinks

Recommendations

17.1. Lessons learnt

Framing carbon credits within the broader context of holistic restoration of landscapes and regions, while combining them with other mechanisms, contributes to establishing an effective and inclusive process towards climate resilience, rather than constituting barely a standalone solution for climate mitigation.

- Multistakeholder partnerships can facilitate scaling through a strong network, and previous stakeholder alignment having reached consensus on a common vision for the development of a landscape or region; this also facilitates conflict mitigation.

- This also enables co-benefits on a wider scale, such as community benefits, biodiversity conservation on habitat and landscape level, social benefits, such as job creation.
- Multistakeholder projects lower transition barriers by showcasing successes and sharing learnings from failures. A leverage effect is created when Carbon Farming projects are conducted as a group that shares common interests.
- Ideally this should be connected to a community or regional facility that financially supports the initial investment phase of a carbon project – the most crucial phase of a project.
- Financial risks such as high initial investments and ongoing operational costs during a Carbon Farming project may be mitigated as sharing investments in machinery and agricultural inputs lowers individual investment costs.
- EU support for regional network development can accelerate project scaling by providing capacity-building, facilitating cross-border cooperation, and ensuring fair benefit distribution. Strengthening these networks will enhance resilience, stakeholder engagement, and the effectiveness of landscape-scale Carbon Farming.

An effective multi-stakeholder network should be inclusive, transparent, and adaptive, integrating landowners, farmers, local communities, investors, policymakers, scientists, and NGOs. It should foster long-term collaboration through shared governance structures, ensuring all actors have a role in decision-making. The network should facilitate knowledge exchange, capacity-building, and technical support, aligning diverse interests with a common landscape vision. Regional coordination bodies can enhance efficiency by connecting local initiatives with national and EU-level policies. A multi-tiered governance model, integrating public and private stakeholders, ensures accountability, conflict resolution, and sustainable financing. Clear benefit-sharing mechanisms and long-term incentives, such as carbon revenues reinvested into local development, are essential to maintaining engagement and ensuring project scalability from local to landscape levels.

Create more networking opportunities for farmers on community and regional level to engage interested landowners, land users and other stakeholders in the carbon discourse

- Provide a platform for EU-wide accessible workshops on Carbon Farming projects
- This will bring practitioners, land managers, investors and other parties together
- The ideal network should consist of stakeholders along the entire Carbon Farming project value chain, including private and public stakeholders

A flexible, science-based approach is needed to account for ecosystem heterogeneity while maintaining the integrity of carbon methodologies. Multi-stakeholder networks can facilitate locally adapted methodologies by integrating regional ecological knowledge with standardized carbon accounting frameworks. Incentivizing research, pilot projects, and participatory monitoring ensures methodologies reflect diverse land-use systems. Carbon credit frameworks should incorporate ecosystem-specific baselines, rewarding

multifunctional landscapes that provide biodiversity and resilience benefits. Blended financing models combining carbon revenues with conservation payments can ensure viability across land types. Regional governance structures should guide the alignment of carbon standards with local land management needs, ensuring fair access to carbon markets while safeguarding ecological integrity. EU support for adaptive methodologies can enhance credibility and facilitate cross-border project scaling.

Stakeholder networks help to account for heterogeneity of agro-ecosystems, land use and management practices when using existing Carbon Farming practices or methodologies. Methodology developers should consider the following to ease MS network projects

- Heterogeneity in terms of different ecosystems (arable, grasslands, forestry, wetlands, etc.) require different methodologies to be combined to scale a project from single plots to landscape/regional level. A first guidance for this already exists and will be continuously improved (Commonland carbon finance chapter in the 4R guidebook, refer to online link).
- A more component-based approach vs. an activity-based approach can help to quantify elements of the carbon cycle in a more practical and ecosystem-agnostic manner. This approach is supported by current developments of quantification models involving remote sensing for which considerations should be made to be included in the current versions of methodologies as one type of quantification approach.

Multistakeholder networks help improve the accuracy of MRV and mitigate increased costs of MRV. It is beneficial to include co-benefits in a participatory MRV system on landscape or regional level

- Variability determines sample sizes, and not the size of an area. Thus, designing sampling schemes that involve a larger area can have a positive effect on sample sizes per participating land user in a larger MS project.
- Landscape or regional networks can facilitate the selection of baseline plots for dynamic baselining, by allowing stakeholders to choose a plot together instead of individual ones.
- A reduction of sampling sizes per hectare reduces costs for MRV substantially.
- Costs of sampling can also be reduced by sharing sampling efforts and costs for sampling tools.
- Co-benefits often are created on a larger scale (the positive externalities of a Carbon Farming project) and thus can be allocated more efficiently on a community level than for the individual context.

Testing grounds for refining carbon methodologies. Pilot projects serve as testing grounds for refining carbon methodologies, demonstrating real-world feasibility, and informing policy frameworks. Multi-stakeholder networks play a key role in scaling pilot findings by fostering cross-sector collaboration and ensuring practical implementation insights reach policymakers. EU-supported pilot initiatives can validate financial models, risk-sharing mechanisms, and co-benefit measurement frameworks, helping to shape future incentive

structures. Regulatory flexibility should be built into early-stage pilots to allow experimentation with innovative Carbon Farming approaches. A structured feedback loop between pilot projects and EU institutions can accelerate policy adjustments, ensuring alignment between field experience and legislative frameworks. Establishing formal channels for pilot project results to influence EU directives would enhance scalability, credibility, and investment attractiveness of Carbon Farming policies.

17.2. Lessons learnt

Funding Carbon Farming projects within the voluntary carbon market in the EU remains a challenge due to high costs and investment risks. Blended finance emerges as a strategic solution, leveraging both public and private capital to facilitate sustainable investments in the early stage of development.

- Public funding at the EU level is necessary to bridge the investment gap in the early stages.
- Strengthen public funding for early-stage development as public funds play a critical role for R&D activities, project development, and piloting new methodologies which is critical when initiating Carbon Farming projects across different landscapes.
- Leverage CAP, State Aid, and other EU Funds to overcome barriers. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget, State aid, and other EU funding mechanisms that help in covering upfront costs such as investments in technology, advisory services, and MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) tools. These costs often act as barriers to participation, especially for small-scale farmers.
- De-risk investments by increased use of guarantees - public financing can absorb early-stage risks thus increasing the amount of private sector investments available within support of wider nature restoration or regeneration efforts.
- Supporting pan-European research to collect data also on the Carbon Farming market size, volume and market potential alongside to promotion of networks and training of the Carbon Farming through EU grants (e.g. Natura 2000 payments or within EU funds calls).
- Enhanced coordination of transition funds to ensure public and private investments are implemented with robust financial risk mitigation strategies.
- Enable public funds in the form of unrestricted and flexible grant funding should be available to support multi-stakeholder landscape partnership and governance processes to catalyse development of overall nature restoration.
- Redirect environmentally harming subsidies, enhance coordination of transition funds, align public and private investments.

Currently, in the EU there are multiple funding sources and scale of incentives for the green transition within Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021–2027, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget (Pillar 1 eco-schemes and Pillar 2 rural development measures), LIFE Programme, Horizon Europe (Cluster 5, 6 including Mission Soil) and others, e.g. EAFRD, ERDF. New greener and fairer CAP envisioned a substantial allocation of budget for eco-schemes (including Carbon Farming among others) with at least 25% of the budget

for direct payments to be allocated to eco-schemes to incentivize climate and environment friendly Carbon Farming practices with a spending on eco-schemes in the period 2023-2027 of 48,5 billion Euros. Additionally, at least 35% of EAFRD funds under Pillar 2 is allocated to initiatives addressing numerous environmental and climate challenges.

- Accelerating implementation of greener and fairer Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).
- Effectively implement financial allocations for eco-schemes including Carbon Farming initiatives within national level CAP Strategic Plans.
- Foster systemic public-private investment alignment in design of dedicated blended finance mechanisms and financial instruments.
- Strengthen collaboration between government institutions, development finance institutions (DFIs), private investors and non-profit organizations within multi-stakeholder landscape partnership framework to maximize blended finance potential.
- Leverage public development banks potential, for instance EIB Group announced commitment of €3 billion in loans for agriculture and other bioeconomy activities across Europe with focus on young farmers, gender equality and green investments.
- Implement incentives that encourage nature-positive actions and efficiently support just transition within the agricultural sector.

To scale up carbon projects, develop suitable financial instruments with longer time horizons aligned with large, holistic restoration initiatives that harness diverse stakeholders that can support long-term project viability and de-risk investment for private investors.

- Support multi-stakeholder partnerships to effectively blend different financial instruments at various stages of landscape interventions over a longer time horizon.
- Enhance policy and regulatory frameworks to facilitate blended finance models and create incentives for private sector participation.
- Develop enabling platforms to streamline the implementation of national and regional development plans, ensuring vertical and horizontal policy coherence and integrating spatial planning and budgeting.
- Allocate resources to strengthen landscape partnerships that drive comprehensive and sustainable landscape restoration efforts.
- Support learning, training and knowledge-sharing and with adequate funding allocation.

Measure social and environmental impact and more process-based funding for organizations that develop standardized impact assessment frameworks to track and demonstrate the co-benefits of blended finance in carbon projects.

- Adapting a holistic landscape approach can reduce or overcome many of the barriers for successful green transition and provide numerous co-benefits. Using blended finance mechanisms, different financial instruments including ecosystem payment services, 4Return approach values environment, social and inspirational returns alongside financial returns, recognizing true value of an investment and interconnectedness aspects of a landscape to address multiple challenges regarding climate change mitigation and adaptation.

- Co-benefit is that one financed intervention is not isolated as a one-time funded project as various capital providers and revenue streams are strategically aligned with a long capital continuum time horizon.

17.3. Lessons learnt

The management and restoration of Mediterranean Wetlands have proven to be effective strategies for mitigating climate change. These wetlands naturally act as carbon sinks, storing significant carbon stocks in their sediment. Restoration and management actions further enhance their mitigation capacity, ensuring additionality, as demonstrated by the LIFE Wetlands4Climate project.

However, the high operational costs of small-scale projects present a major challenge. To improve cost-effectiveness, these initiatives need to be upscaled. Additionally, carbon credits prices remain high in the market – pilot projects in Spain indicate costs around €400 per ton of CO₂ equivalent. One of the key cost drivers is the monitoring and verification process, which requires on-site fieldwork on an annual basis. This includes defining plots and measuring carbon fluxes for every hectare of restored wetland.

To make wetland-based Carbon Farming more viable, scaling up projects and optimizing monitoring methods will be essential for reducing costs and improving accessibility to carbon markets.

17.4. Open questions

The ideal stakeholder network for scaling Carbon Farming and achieving co-benefits should be a multi-actor platform integrating: farmers/Landowners/authorities with competencies on the land, scientists, NGOs, private investors, policymakers (Regional or national Authorities), and certification bodies. Farmers or landowners need financial and technical support, while scientists ensure robust monitoring and verification. NGOs facilitate implementation and safeguard biodiversity, and private investors help scale solutions through carbon markets. Policymakers (Regional and National Authorities) must align regulations with the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), ensuring incentives and funding mechanisms. Lessons from LIFE Wetlands4Climate show that nature-based solutions, transparent carbon accounting, and multi-stakeholder collaboration are key to success. Policy support should focus on creating stable financial incentives, regulatory clarity, and streamlined MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) processes. Blended finance mechanisms should be promoted to de-risk investments, attracting private capital into Carbon Farming. Additionally, harmonized carbon accounting standards are essential to ensure credibility across different ecosystems. Policy frameworks should also support regional pilot projects, knowledge-sharing networks, and digital tools for cost-effective carbon monitoring, fostering long-term stakeholder engagement and scalability.

- Developing Biodiversity Credits – Establishing biodiversity credit systems to properly value wetland restoration co-benefits is essential. Policymakers, conservation organizations, and financial institutions must collaborate to create marketable,

science-based credit mechanisms that integrate carbon sequestration with biodiversity conservation.

- Blended Finance for Carbon Farming – A mix of public grants (CAP eco-schemes, LIFE Program) and private investment (carbon markets, green bonds) is needed to de-risk early-stage projects and attract long-term financing. Public funding should support research, baseline assessments, and MRV, while private capital scales up validated projects.
- Reducing MRV Costs – LIFE Wetlands4Climate highlights the need for investment in cost-effective MRV methodologies, including scientific research to validate proxy-based monitoring methods. Lowering MRV costs will improve scalability and investor confidence.
- Valuing Co-Benefits in Carbon Markets – Current carbon pricing undervalues ecosystem services. Recognizing biodiversity, water retention, and resilience co-benefits in carbon markets and EU climate funding would enhance financial viability and attract more investment in wetland-based Carbon Farming.

17.5. Open questions

Enhancing Monitoring and Verification Methods: The LIFE Wetlands4Climate methodology relies on direct, on-site measurements of carbon fluxes, as no proxies currently exist to scale results. The lack of scientific studies on Mediterranean wetlands and their role in climate change mitigation prevents the development of alternative verification approaches. Addressing this gap requires scientific research institutions, environmental agencies, and carbon credit certifiers to collaborate on expanding datasets and validating proxy-based monitoring approaches, and standardize methodologies, ultimately reducing MRV costs and improving accuracy.

From the LIFE Wetlands4Climate perspective, scaling carbon projects through multi-stakeholder networks can increase investment attractiveness by improving cost efficiency, data reliability, and market access. Larger-scale projects reduce MRV costs per unit by enabling shared resources, standardized methodologies, and collaborative research across multiple sites.

However, Mediterranean wetlands lack validated proxy-based MRV methods, making monitoring expensive and limiting scalability. Addressing this requires investment in scientific research, data standardization, and the development of alternative verification approaches. Public funding is crucial to bridge early-stage investment gaps, while private sector engagement can drive long-term financing through carbon markets. Strengthening policy alignment, certification frameworks, and co-benefit valuation (biodiversity, water resilience) will further enhance investor confidence and project viability.

Establish a Clear Legal and Certification Framework: The lack of an approved methodology for Mediterranean wetlands under certification standards, coupled with administrative barriers (as seen in LIFE Wetlands4Climate), has slowed progress. The CRCF should provide a clear, flexible legal framework that accommodates diverse ecosystems, including wetlands, by recognizing regional variations in carbon sequestration potential. It must also streamline

approval processes for new methodologies, ensuring faster validation and adoption while reducing bureaucratic hurdles.

Improve the CRCF Approach and Methodologies: The CRCF should explicitly recognize Mediterranean wetlands as a Carbon Farming solution, integrating hydrology-based carbon accounting to reflect their unique sequestration dynamics. The framework must set clear guidelines for methodology approval, incentivize scientific research to fill knowledge gaps, and facilitate integration with national carbon registries and EU climate policies. A more adaptive, science-driven approach will enable large-scale wetland restoration to play a key role in achieving EU climate targets while unlocking carbon market opportunities.

Session 18: Co-designing future services and a policy framework on Carbon Farming

Main organiser: ICOS

Session description

This session provided a collaborative space for participants to co-design future services aimed at supporting policymakers in carbon removal efforts. Organizers shared comparative insights on existing services related to Carbon Farming, drawing from the IRISCC (Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks) project. Additionally, a taxonomy of key features and essential data requirements for current services was presented which can serve as a foundation for developing next-generation services.

The central question guiding this session was: What future services can we envision to more effectively meet policymakers' needs using research infrastructure data?

Designed specifically for policymakers and researchers in the field of carbon removal, this session focused on leveraging research infrastructures—facilities and systems dedicated to environmental management, protection, and improvement, supported by a range of technologies addressing various ecological challenges. The goal was to foster innovative service(s) that directly respond to the evolving needs of policymakers.

Issues

- What kind of services are needed
- How they need to be implemented
- Who are the key actors in the development of the services.

Recommendations

18.1. What kind of services are needed?

Even though we identified many stakeholders and drew a map on how they relate to each other and to the future services, a common vision is that **Farmers should be at heart** in the development of new services. A consistent theme across all scenarios is the need to place farmers at the center of the agricultural system. Currently, farmers often feel marginalized, burdened by regulations, and disconnected from the policy-making processes that directly impact their livelihoods. The utopian vision flips this dynamic. Whether it's Ireland's focus on keeping farmers on the land or Portugal/Flanders highlighting farmers as key decision-makers, the message is clear: a sustainable future requires empowering farmers. Farmers in Europe are aging, with the average age nearing 60 years. This raises an important question: how can we make farming an attractive career choice for younger generations? To ensure the

future of agriculture, we need to inspire and support a new generation of enthusiastic farmers.

The potential for fraud and conflicts of interest emerged as a significant concern. From the role of assessors in the Central Europe scenario, potentially enabling fraudulent reporting to the discussion of brokers in Portugal/Flanders, it's clear that robust oversight mechanisms are essential. Independent bodies are needed to ensure that carbon credit schemes are not exploited, and that the integrity of the system is maintained.

The Irish scenario brought up an interesting point about balancing local and global markets. While the emphasis is on "insetting" – reducing emissions within the farm and food industry itself – the reality is that Ireland is a major exporter. The utopian vision must therefore create a system that is both beneficial to local communities and credible on the international stage. This may involve a multi-layered approach where farms prioritize local sales before selling carbon credits externally.

While financial compensation is undoubtedly important, the scenarios also emphasized the need to incentivize farmers through other means. Farmer networks, knowledge sharing, and recognition within their profession can all play a crucial role in motivating sustainable practices. It's about creating a culture of excellence and innovation in agriculture, where farmers are proud to be stewards of the land.

To whom: Developers of the future services

18.2. Concrete steps for implementation

The implementation needs to follow a co-design approach. This is why the first step is to identify the stakeholders that need to be involved in this process. This workshop is part of our co-design approach. This work of identifying the stakeholders is conducted during the session. We do this work as part of the EU project IRISCC, Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks.

We have developed a card game that helps us to co-design with various stakeholders in our workshop. This tool has been key in organising the discussion in the workshop. We are aiming to play this card game together with other stakeholders and in other forums (conferences, meetings or summits) in order to get comparable results.

To whom: Stakeholders identified: EU policymakers, National and local policymakers, farmers, private sector involved in the MRV and in the voluntary carbon market, research infrastructures and researchers.

18.3. Lesson learnt

The path towards the implementation of the Carbon Farming framework for Europe is complex, but the discussions on Future Utopian scenarios offer a roadmap. By prioritizing farmers, fostering transparency and trust, addressing fraud, balancing local and global markets, and confronting monopolies, Europe can create a good implementation of the carbon removal and harmonized Carbon Farming (CRCF) framework that is both

environmentally sustainable and economically viable. It's a vision that requires collaboration, innovation, and a commitment to creating a better future for all.

To whom: Policymakers, researchers, farmers, public and private sector representatives and service developers.

18.4. How to use data to ensure transparency and trust?

Another key element is data. The Central European scenario highlights the importance of centralized data management for carbon credit systems, while the Irish scenario stresses the need for long-term monitoring and research to ensure the credibility of food labeling schemes. Across the board, transparency is paramount. Farmers need to trust that systems are fair, that they are compensated adequately, and that oversight bodies are accountable. Data, when managed effectively and transparently, can be a powerful tool for building this trust.

For different MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) systems, these systems must comply with international standards, link carbon sequestration ("Carbon Farming") to agronomic strategies, and be tailored to regional contexts. They should also be developed through international collaboration involving public research institutions, the private sector, and farmers. Additionally, it is crucial to integrate this data with national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories and establish clear rules for managing farm-level data. These rules must address who owns the data, who can access it, and how it can be used effectively.

Session 19: Overcoming barriers to Carbon Farming projects financing: Bridging the gap between farmers and buyers through adequate framework and MRV tools

Main organisers: Association des Chambres d'agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique (AC3A), Agrifood, Agrosolutions, CNRS-CESBIO, Earth Observation Association, I4CE, IETA, Nataïs, Netcarbon, Regeneratio

Session description

The Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) is aiming to make a meaningful contribution to the EU's climate mitigation targets while appealing to both land users and certificates' buyers. This is not an easy match, especially for the agriculture sector where the economic model for the agriculture transition still needs to be found. In this context, this session built on real use cases to dive into the potential cases for agriculture-based CRCF certificates. It discussed the various sources of funding that should be unlocked, and to some extent stacked at farm level: voluntary private funding outside the value chain, voluntary funding from the value chain, compliance demand, public funds.

Today, the main private funding sources are voluntary: offsetting, and insetting. Both options barely allow to cover the full cost of the transition at farm level. Solutions are needed to both stack and scale them. The main barriers to financing are the Carbon Farming costs and the lack of clarity around the claims buyers can make in an MRV context, especially the risk of double-counting. Bridging the gap between farmers and certificates' buyers, this session discussed these difficulties and barriers, and explored how CRCF can solve them, to ensure that adequate funding effectively reaches the farms.

Issues

- Challenges observed for agriculture projects' financing: confusion in claims and double-counting issues, environmental integrity and project's attractiveness, cost of MRV and cost of practices vs market price, non-permanence and uncertainty of nature-based credits
- Issues for buyers in terms of claims clarity and need for precise SCOPE 3 reporting
- Opportunities provided by new MRV tools to help solve the above-mentioned issues (reporting, traceability, uncertainty...)

Recommendations

19.1. Lesson learnt

In countries like France which already have carbon certification mechanisms in place, we notice Carbon Farming projects from the agriculture sector have more difficulties than others (e.g. forestry) to access voluntary funding. Among the potential reasons for this, stakeholders bring up the attractiveness of the projects' narrative, the carbon price, but also the perceived risk of double-claiming, which is considered by many as one of the main deterrents for agriculture projects' funding. The current rules promoted by standards like the GHG Protocol or SBTi Flag require a strict allocation of carbon benefits that is hard to implement yet, which slows down the agrifood industries' commitment and prevents farmers from accessing sufficient funding. More specifically, two main issues are being reported: 1) there still is uncertainty regarding the claims around Scope 3 reporting, and 2) farmers can be prevented from combining different sources of funding from within and outside the value chain.

19.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure the Green Claims Directive provides clear and common rules for Carbon Farming projects related claims. Those rules will need to allow for coherent and transparent claims (be precise about who can claim what with such a certificate), while still being pragmatic on traceability and the need to combine different sources of funding for a unique farm in numerous situations.

More generally, clarity is needed on the end-uses for nature-based carbon removal credits. This includes rules for the use of credits in corporate environmental claims, including CSRD, but also clear views from the Commission on a potential emissions trading system for agriculture, potential recognition under CORSIA... There is also a need for clear guidance on the articulation of the CRCF with the existing voluntary carbon market standards to keep investment flowing in the sector.

The claims should transparently address buyers' expectations towards permanence, and allow CRC-F credits to compete with international private Carbon Farming supply standards. The EU CRCF's proposed durations for Carbon Farming activity (5 years) and monitoring period (another 5 years) are very short and 30 years less than the recommendation of the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM), currently implemented by leading international Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) standards' methodologies.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

Create funding mechanisms associated with the CRCF which allows the combination of different sources of funding (private-private, public-private) to cover the whole project's costs (practices, investment, risk +MRV). The rules about claims should allow for this possibility, especially when the carbon price on the voluntary market is not high enough to cover the costs. Of course, clear rules about how to deal with additionality should be

established and made transparent when combining different sources of funding (especially public-private combinations). One major feedback of our audience was the call for unified MRV for Inset and Offsetting needs such that both can be combined. Only the combination of both allows for a whole-farm transition as this is the only way to credible, long-term SOC sequestration. Funding sources that focus only on some crops or some years do not provide sufficient incentives for farmers to transform their farming system credibly.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

Set clear rules for delimiting what falls within agrofood scope 3 perimeter in Carbon Farming, especially for rotational crops, and define allocation rules for carbon removals, among the different crops of a crop rotation.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure the CRCF reaches beyond voluntary demand, all while protecting and incentivizing existing voluntary initiatives. Most carbon funding today is voluntary (offsetting or insetting): in a complicated political context, we need to find ways to ensure the additionality and sustainability of private commitments, but also develop other sources of funding which can unlock greater volumes: public funds directed to certified projects, or compliance demand for those certificates.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.6. Proposal to improve CRCF

Implementing a yearly/field scale common database (C registry) for ongoing and previous projects should also be a priority to address double counting. In addition, a solution would be to rely on a common tool for the different MRV contexts (CAP, VCM offsetting & insetting) and on blockchains to ensure traceability.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.7. Proposal to improve CRCF

Rely on geospatial data including remote sensing to reduce the cost and increase the reliability/transparency/objectivity of the C stock change assessment for the Carbon Farming project. Define standards to associate to the quality of carbon credits.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

Session 20: Financing models for a sustainable future

Main organisers: Heavy Finance, Rabobank

Session description

This session explored the financial challenges faced by farmers transitioning to regenerative agriculture, focusing on innovative financing solutions and the role of public institutions in unlocking capital. Given the urgency of addressing climate change, understanding these barriers is critical for promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

As Europe accelerates its transition to a sustainable agricultural sector, access to capital remains a significant barrier for farmers adopting regenerative practices like reduced tillage, incorporation of cover crops etc. This session addressed the financing gap, highlighting innovative solutions such as GreenLoans, which provide zero-interest loans funded by future carbon credit sales. It discussed how carbon credits can serve as collateral for financing, the need for structured and transparent carbon markets, and the transformative role of public institutions in catalyzing private investment.

Issues

- Capital barriers in regenerative farming
- Innovative Financing models
- Use of carbon credits as collateral for financing
- Importance of structured carbon markets
- Role of public institutions in unlocking capital

Recommendations

No recommendations.

Session 21: Paving the way for cohesive action on soil carbon sequestration: The role of International Initiatives in the development of MRV frameworks that meet European Carbon Farming challenges

Main organisers: 4per 1000, INRAE

Session description

The key role of increasing and protecting soil carbon stocks for climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity protection and food security is increasingly being recognized in international negotiations. While the EU with its Soil Monitoring Law, the Mission Soil and the upcoming CRCF framework is a strong global leader in the field, the topic has gained prominence all around the globe. International initiatives, like the “4 per 1000” Initiative and the Soil Carbon International Research Consortium (IRC), have been playing a crucial role to build momentum, increase collaboration and foster peer-to-peer learning. This session reflected on current political processes supporting soil carbon sequestration and explored opportunities for support for cohesive policymaking, research design and multi-stakeholder action.

Looking back at the first decade of the “4 per 1000” Initiative, the session reflected on how the global outreach of the Initiative has paved the way for current political and scientific developments around soil health and carbon sequestration in the EU and beyond. It introduced successful approaches to multi-stakeholder action and presented key findings of the regional roadmaps for Northern Europe and the Mediterranean Region.

Finally, the session reflected on existing **MRV tools and systems and presented a harmonized approach** developed under the ORCaSa project.

Issues

- Approaches to cohesive policy making across international conventions and beyond departments at European and national Scale
- Priorities for most effective policy support and multi-stakeholder action for international Initiatives
- Priorities for policy support concerning MRV frameworks and associated methodologies
- Requirements for a harmonized MRV system

Recommendations

21.1. Recommendation for action

Strengthen international multi-stakeholder cooperation and dialogue, by supporting the actions of initiatives like "4 per 1000" and the Soil Carbon International Research Consortium, to ensure the feasibility of MRV frameworks along the value chain and across regions and to improve harmonization.

21.2. Recommendation for action

Integrate environmental and social co-benefits of soil carbon sequestration into a holistic Carbon Farming approach via premiums on credits.

21.3. Recommendation for action

Improve the accessibility of carbon markets and facilitate informed decision making on Carbon Farming activities, by providing aggregated and easily accessible information on carbon market mechanisms, scientific findings and technical developments related to soil carbon sequestration, MRV, environmental and social effects, as well as benefits and risks related to different approaches.

21.4. Recommendation for action

Create a monitoring committee for existing Carbon Farming practices, their implementation and impacts, to feed decision making on the evolution of directives at European level.

21.5. Recommendation for action

Provide international guidance on the use of cost effective monitoring tools across the MRV frameworks by combining observation technologies (e.g. remote sensing, spectral measurements and automated sampling) adapted to different contexts of application and regional constraints.

Session 22: Monitoring and verification of peatland condition and improvement: Remote sensing, AI and beyond

Main organisers: AECO, National Parks and Wildlife Service, Peatland Finance Ireland, Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin

Session description

In order to achieve efficiencies of scale, there is a need for semi-automated methods to monitor peatland condition at scale to infer ecosystem service delivery such as carbon flux, water retention or biodiversity uplift. Remote Sensing (RS), Artificial Intelligence (AI), remote monitoring systems and data science/engineering can play a pivotal role, as processing pipelines can be deployed to continually fetch data to feed AI models for further inference. However, the accuracy of these outputs rely on effective ground-truthing. This leads to a series of multi-scale and multi-modal questions: how could different RS sources - e.g. satellites and unmanned aerial vehicles - be integrated for better inference, if their spatial extent greatly varies? How can these methods be used to monitor, report and validate ecosystem service delivery in a manner which ensures that sources of finance can economically support restoration? What are the most cost-effective strategies for on-the-ground monitoring to deliver credible short-term results, while generating robust datasets for training algorithms in the long term? Do these approaches comfortably sit with emergent mandatory and voluntary markets?

This session highlighted advances in remote sensing (RS), artificial intelligence (AI), and remote monitoring systems (incl. water table), emphasizing their role in peatland restoration. It addressed challenges in standardization, showcased best practices in MRV, and explored their applications to emerging standards across Europe. Importantly, by fostering dialogue among experts, practitioners, and stakeholders, it aimed to catalyze standardization, innovation and to drive the adoption of advanced technologies.

Issues

- Monitoring and quantifying peatland condition
- Remote Sensing (RS), Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support this
- MRV to support emerging standards across Europe

Recommendations

22.1 Proposal to improve CRCF

Remote sensing and artificial intelligence, increasingly, can be used effectively to derive reliable, cost-effective and scalable monitoring of peatland conditions. An approach to integrating this into CRCF methodologies should therefore be formulated.

To whom: DG CLIMA, ENV and Expert Working Group on CRCF

22.2. Recommendation for action

Delivery of quantified ecosystem services requires cost-effective and scalable monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), supporting emergent Standards in Europe (e.g. Ireland) which can offer a bundle of ecosystem services. **These bundled certificates need to be more actively included within the CRCF and nature finance more broadly.**

To whom: National responsible bodies, EU Commission DGs

22.3. Open question

How can we pragmatically apply remote sensing, artificial intelligence and other state-of-the-art monitoring techniques (especially water table depth) to existing and emergent certification systems?

To whom: DG CLIMA and National Restoration Plan national contact points.

Session 23: MRV agroforestry

Main organisers: Climate Cleanup, DEAFAL, DeFAF, ELO, EURAF, INRAE, Scave World, University of Pisa

Session description

“Soil carbon in mineral soils and agroforestry” is one of the three Carbon Farming activities being developed in the Carbon Farming Delegated Act of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework. Agroforestry has long been recommended by the IPCC for both climate mitigation and climate adaptation - e.g. IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land ([IPCC 2019](#)). It was also prominent in reports commissioned by DG Clima on operationalising Carbon Farming (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #8](#)).

This session focused on **monitoring, reporting and verification** of agroforestry Carbon Farming schemes, including environmental and social issues. It built on the EURAF typology for agroforestry practices - identifying 8 types of agroforestry (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #1](#)), and focused on agricultural land.

Recommendations were prepared to support the role of agroforestry in future voluntary carbon-farming schemes. CAP eco-schemes, investment measures and agri-environment-climate measures during the first 5 years of agroforestry plantations can kick-start their adoption into voluntary Carbon Farming schemes and help close the growing gap between GHG emissions and sequestration in rural Europe. It is suggested that Member States should register and map lines and groups of trees as “landscape features”, and this will give them a protected status and good guarantees of “permanence”.

Issues

- Access to smallholder farmers,
- Leakage,
- Liability and Insurance,
- Implementation hurdles

Recommendations

23.1. Definitions

Agroforestry should be defined in the CRCF as “**Cropland or permanent pasture parcels**, including boundaries, with more than [x%] tree-cover-density (TCD), or with a management plan where tree cover will exceed this density. The threshold TCD shall be set by Member States. **Permanent crop parcels** can be classed as agroforestry if a secondary crop or grazing is noted in the IACS-LPIS system” **Notes:** a) Member states are recommended to choose

either **5%** (FAO threshold for “other wooded land”) or **10%** (FAO threshold for “forest”) for the TCD threshold; d) IACS-LPIS “forest parcels” will not count as CRCF agroforestry, although forest grazing is a valuable management practice to reduce the risk of wildfires; c) Member States already use tree cover thresholds between 10% and 30% in their national definitions of “forest” (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#)).

Landscape features are quoted in the DGCLIMA draft methodology for Carbon Farming as “high diversity landscape features”, and are listed in Annex IV of the *Nature Restoration Regulation* as indicators of agricultural biodiversity. Unfortunately, DGENV uses a different definition of landscape features to that used in the CAP. *CAP Implementing Regulation* (L/458/463) Article 3.1 defines **landscape features** as “hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, trees rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features”. The NRR includes these categories but also adds “land lying fallow”. It uses the prefix “high diversity” without clarifying what this means! DGAGRI and DGENV, with the help of JRC and their recent *Classification of Farming Practices* ([2024](#)), should resolve the differences in definitions urgently. The authors recommend that the **DGAGRI definition is preferred**, since it has existed for much longer and because Member States already provide detailed dimensions and rules for landscape features in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#)).

Forest is defined as in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation [2018/841](#), amended for ES, SL and FI by Regulation [2023/839](#). The national thresholds conform with the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords ([2021](#)) and are used by all Member States for their annual Greenhouse Gas Inventory Reports to the UNFCCC. The single definition of forest contained in the draft Forest Monitoring Regulation ([Nov 2023](#)) is **not appropriate** for CRCF reporting, except in the 3 MS where it matches the national definition.

Agroforestation is a shorthand term for the creation of agroforestry systems. It is the parallel of afforestation, but the land remains defined as “agriculture” rather than “forest” in national cadastres and IACS systems.

23.2. Improvement of CRCF

The Carbon Farming Delegated Act should include an indicative list of Carbon Farming practices, based on the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook* (2021) and the JRC *Classification of Farming Practices* (2024).

A standardised baseline of zero for agroforestry trees younger than 6 years, suggested by DG Clima, is appropriate since the modest growth of young trees in widely spaced tree rows will be balanced by the small emissions caused by initial ground preparation and planting. Even tree-plantations with fast growth, such as poplars in the Po valley or eucalyptus in Galicia will fix less than 5% of their total biomass during the first 5 years. This availability of CAP funding for the baseline soil measurements, tree-planting and initial maintenance will “kick-start” accounting and greatly incentivise landowners.

Another type of agroforestation is protected natural regeneration of degraded wood pastures (e.g. Dehesas, Montados and Streuobst). There may be as much as 20.3 Mha of wood pastures in Europe (Pleininger et al 2015) and most are heavily degraded. Their restoration would be enhanced by a combination of CAP funding and carbon-farming certification. “Restoration of wood pastures” as a type of agroforestry will require establishment of a “project baseline” rather than a “standardised baseline” because of the presence of both mature and juvenile trees.

The second Carbon Farming methodology recommended by DG Clima is “*Tree planting on degraded and abandoned land*”. EURAF recommend that this be called “*Afforestation of degraded and abandoned land*” to avoid confusion with agroforestry (which remains as “agriculture” in CAP statistics), and to align better with existing UNFCCC and VCM methodologies for “*afforestation, reforestation and restoration*” (ARR).

23.3. Improvement of CRCF: eligible activities

In the DG Clima first MRV draft (Nov 2024), the discussion of carbon-sequestration should be completed with the statement “*or which reduce emissions from soils*”. This is particularly relevant to agroforestry – since agricultural trees can both limit N₂O emissions from the soil by uptake of surplus NO_x in reducing conditions, and reduce volatilized ammonia (NH₃) through its absorption on tree foliage. These processes should, ideally, be included in biophysical agroforestry models.

The DG Clima draft states that “*all farm activities must be monitored in case of leakage to non-certified parcels*”. EURAF feels this may dissuade farmers from applying for certification and could complicate use of the DGCLIMA geospatial carbon certification registry.

23.4. Improvement of CRCF: activity period and monitoring period

The minimum **activity period** proposed by DG Clima of 10 years is acceptable. This is the shortest period possible for an agroforestry rotation (e.g. for poplars in the Po Valley). Most rotations will be 20-50 years.

The minimum **monitoring period** for agroforestry should also be 10 years. Again, if trees are 5 years old when monitoring starts they will be 20 when monitoring stops. This is too old for some fast-growing agroforestry.

23.5. Improvement of CRCF: Total carbon removals and/or soil emission reduction

DG Clima should maintain a list of “approved” agroforestry models/tools for certification. The DigitAF project has a provisional list of list such tools in its page on Tools, Data and Projects Agroforestry projects should make projections using at least 3 different “approved” models/tools to gain an estimate of “uncertainty”.

23.6. Addressing uncertainties in conservative manner

Measure-Remeasure techniques may be unreliable in agroforestry for below ground biomass and fine root turnover because of 3-dimensional spatial variability. A modelling approach is inevitable and some existing models were recommended in the Dublin workshop ([Thissen 2025](#))

Almost all crop-management methods suggested in the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook* ([2021](#)) can be used in the crop-alleys of agroforestry systems. One exception is a 100% no till system, where a subsoiler of chisel plough will need to pass close to the tree-lines, at least every second year, to ensure that tree roots do not compete excessively with crops in the surface soil horizons.

Branch pruning increases fine root turnover in proportion to the loss of above ground living biomass and should be included in biophysical and statistical models of agroforestry.

Strong links are needed with research projects like DigitAF, Reforest, MARVIC and MRV4SOC. These can help develop allometric equations to convert tree height and diameter to above and below-ground biomass. Allometry derived from forest stands will be inaccurate because trees have different form factors and less below ground biomass. Existing databases like BAAD, GlobAllomeTree, and FigShare, Mendeley therefore need to be extended for open-grown trees.

23.7. Additionality - Financial test

In the CAP 2014-2022, across the EU, only around 5k hectares of agroforestry were planted from a target of 89k.

In the CAP 2023-2028 only 9 countries have agroforestry measures, often with very low support rates and implementation in only a few regions (IT, ES, DE). The measures include financial support for afforestation. The agroforestry component is a small part of the total,

but breakdowns are not available on the DG Agri portal. No Member State provides a complete package of support: i.e. including each of Article 31, Article 73 and Article 70.

For agroforestry-carbon-farming to succeed it is vital that 4 linked interventions are offered in all Member States:

- **Initial soil sampling and planning** - year 0, CAP Article 31 Eco Scheme
- **Planting and protection of trees** - year 1, CAP Article 73 investment Measure - possibly also Article 74 for irrigation.
- **Early years maintenance support** - years 2-5, CAP Article 70 - Agri Environment Climate annual payment
- **Adoption into a registered agroforestry Carbon Farming scheme** - from year 6 onwards, following satisfactory tree and soil monitoring.

23.8. Guarantee of permanence – Landscape features

Most Carbon Farming schemes approach the need for "permanence" of carbon removals by requiring operators to guarantee that carbon sequestration practices will be maintained for a minimum period. For afforestation (ARR) certification this assumes a given rotation period. In most countries, afforestation projects involve permanent change in land use, and carbon certification operators are required to maintain the forested areas in perpetuity. At the end of a plantation rotation, operators are required to obtain a felling licence from the forest authorities, and must regenerate the felled area, or in exceptional circumstances they can establish a similar area of forest nearby. This degree of permanence also applies to trees, lines of trees and small groups of trees which are recognised and mapped as **GAEC8 landscape features** on agricultural land.

Thus, in the LPIS systems of Member States it is important to distinguish agroforestry-carbon-farming systems where lines of trees have been formally mapped as woody landscape features (using PMEF Result Indicator 17.4) from those where trees are not mapped in this way (e.g. parkland areas with scattered trees). This legal "guarantee of permanence" could be reflected in the carbon price offered in the same way as with carbon in afforestation and reforestation projects.

Some Member States don't implement or map "Landscape Features" (e.g. FI, SE, MT). Further discussions with these Member States will be appropriate if agroforestry-carbon-farming is to be encouraged across Europe

Those Member States which map landscape features in their IACS-GSAA-LPIS systems do so in different ways.. In the CAP 2007-2014 they were recorded in a separate Ecological Focus Area layer of the LPIS as polygons or polylines (ref to Wim's paper on layers). The EFA layer (Van der Weldle, pers comm) is now being integrated in the main GSAA layer, but it is very unclear how much progress Member States are making with this.

Also unclear is the degree to which Member States make their GSAA and LPIS data available openly through their INSPIRE portals, although openness of this data has improved markedly

in the past year (Table 2), and is being exploited in the Regenfarmer/DigitAF “[LPIS aggregator](#)”

The [DigitAF](#) project is seeking to superimpose Copernicus % Tree Cover Density onto LPIS data for a range of countries in the EU ([Milestone 6 Report](#)). This will give an indication of the current extent of agroforestry and allow future planting to focus on the [detailed areas](#) and [NUTS3 provinces](#) which have the highest proportion of “tree deserts”.

The IACS-GSAA-LPIS data only contains “active farmers” whose minimum payments range between €100 and €500 and/or have minimum holding areas ranging from 0.3 ha to 4 ha (depending on the Member States). The DG CLIMA Register of Carbon Farming, which is [due to be developed by 2028](#), will need to include codes for parcels owned by smaller farmers and also forest parcels. Some form of link to cadastral codes is also possible.

Governments could underwrite the risk of accidental loss of carbon by fire or other damage to trees. This insurance option requires further investigation. An advantage of agroforestry compared to conventional afforestation is that fires are much less likely, and less damaging if they do occur ([Wolpert et al 2022](#)).

23.9. Calculation of standardized baselines

CAP GSAA and LPIS systems show the location of agroforestry parcels and woody landscape features: the latter usually in a separate Ecological Focus Area (EFA) layer. Member states vary significantly in the access they provide to this data and in the classifications used. Greater harmonisation and open data access is needed for the DG Clima geospatial parcel register of Carbon Farming parcels which is promised by 2028. Sentinel 2 data gives Tree Crown Density data at 10m resolution. This is useful for broad summaries, but agroforestry Carbon Farming needs access to <50cm resolution Orthophotos, and probably also lidar data.

Standardised baselines in the CRCF are intended to calculate the average carbon capture in an area given knowledge of local climate, soil type and cropping patterns. They could be used to measure the sequestration and emission reduction impact of a farmer against peers in similar areas. Ideally, the comparisons should be carried out using **pedoclimatic zones** (e.g. [Toth 2016](#)) rather than political areas like NUTS2 or NUTS3, but these it is not certain that these classifications exist in sufficient details. The authors initially thought that standardised baselines could be based on GSAA-LPIS Municipality (NUTS4) data, but the areas of these seem too small and variable to be of practical use in most Member States (Table 3). **Another option would be to fix a 10x10 km “bounding box” around each farm applying for carbon certification and calculate a “standardised baseline” using the average land use and soil information derived from GSAA-LPIS for the whole 10 kha box.**

23.10. Suggested agroforestry management plan

EURAF suggested in a submission to DG FISMA (EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#)) that Climate Delegated Act of the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation should reinsert the initially proposed section on sustainable agriculture. The Delegated Act should contain

sustainable management criteria for agroforestry, alongside the existing sections on forestry and paludiculture. The structure suggested for an agroforestry carbon-farming management plan was as follows.

- Location of the parcels and boundaries using codes from the national IACS/LPIS system (or equivalent);
- Location of neighbouring forest and agricultural blocks, showing habitat linkages between wooded areas and the role of ACF parcels in fire-management plans for adjacent forests;
- Baseline estimates of carbon-stocks in each certified parcel including soils and above-ground biomass;
- Management goals, design, species and predicted carbon sequestration of areas covered by trees;
- Management goals and predicted carbon sequestration of the intercropped or grazed alleys;
- Environmental context of the farm(s), including main existing and intended tree species;
- Details of access, environmental constraints, registered landscape-features and legal restrictions on land-use change;
- Details of engagement with neighbours and local stakeholders, in accordance best practice nationally;
- Assessment of agroforestry related risks, including fires, pests and diseases outbreaks and plans to mitigate these;
- Assessment of impact on food production of the farm(s) included in the plan;
- Evaluation of “co-benefits” for biodiversity
- Evaluation of “do no significant harm” (DNSH) criteria for other areas of “sustainability”.

Session 24: Carbon Farming challenges in Mediterranean agriculture: resilient project solutions and certification pathways

Main organisers: Agri Marketplace, BETA Technological Centre, CREA-AA, SLM Partners, Tetis Institute S.r.l, Università degli Studi di Genova

Session description

Carbon Farming can represent a resilient, sustainable agricultural production system offering a new green business model to generate additional revenues through regenerative agriculture and agroforestry practices. It also facilitates the adoption of carbon credits' schemes. This is extremely relevant for the Mediterranean area, marked by unique pedoclimatic conditions and low SOC content. Proper management can transform the area into a significant carbon sink, as the most carbon-depleted soils have the greatest capacity to store carbon. Mediterranean crops often face challenges from carbon-depleted soils, exacerbated by hot, dry climates and water scarcity, requiring significant efforts to restore SOC while addressing farmers' economic barriers and knowledge gaps. This session will explore solutions from Carbon Farming initiatives and their potential to harmonize CRCF at regional and European levels. These initiatives focus on increasing carbon removal and reducing GHG emissions in agricultural systems through scientifically grounded practices, aimed at evaluating and improving methods for quantifying carbon stored in agricultural soils and monitoring carbon removals.

This session shared lessons learned in project experiences, highlighting strong synergies that could be established among scientific and academic communities, consultancy experts, farmers' associations and certification bodies, despite challenges, thereby fostering an integrated approach addressing existing knowledge gaps. The establishment of a methodological and certification framework of Carbon Farming in the Mediterranean area is fundamental to producing concrete field-applicable outcomes that can guide the European Commission and stakeholders towards Europe's 2050 carbon neutrality goals.

Issues

- Carbon Farming in the Mediterranean
- Sustainable business model
- Standardisation and harmonisation of the certification framework

Recommendations

24.1. Open Question

The promotion and support of sustainable land management practices is extremely relevant for the Mediterranean, as this region is characterized by low soil organic carbon content and has a large potential to become a carbon sink if appropriately managed. Establishing a theoretical framework of Carbon Farming in the Mediterranean, quantifying both carbon sequestration in the soil and avoiding GHG emissions is very important.

To whom: Scientists, Land managers

24.2. Concrete step for implementation

Carbon Farming efforts should directly relate to the business model of the agricultural economy having a substantial impact, leading to a capitalisation based on existing models and best practices. Promoting a Mediterranean market of carbon credits generated by regenerative agriculture requires developing effective tools for the market adoption of Carbon Farming as a business model, and to bring Mediterranean carbon buyers and sellers together to benefit from a common market of carbon credits. A tailored techno-economic model is crucial for estimating the investment costs needed to transition from conventional production to a Carbon Farming model. This model should also evaluate land requirements and project the payback period, enabling key stakeholders to make informed decisions, design effective public policies, and foster engagement from the primary sector.

To whom: Business operators, Policymakers

24.3. Open Question

Carbon certification schemes for Carbon Farming practices have to be harmonized by the EC to provide trustability in the voluntary carbon market. The CRFC is trying to tackle this problem by developing a regulatory framework, but it has not yet been implemented. Perhaps, given the agro- and pedoclimatic complexity of the Mediterranean, one of the interesting questions for those responsible is “is it necessary to develop methodologies adapted to the region?”

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policymakers, Scientists, Business operators

24.4. Open Question

Establishing reliable baselines and appropriate permanence periods is crucial for Carbon Farming in agriculture. Baselines provide a reference to measure improvements in carbon sequestration, ensuring accurate assessment of climate benefits. It is important to define a protocol for agriculture to standardize the methods. Adequate permanence periods guarantee that sequestered carbon remains stored in the soil long enough to contribute to long-term climate mitigation, preventing short-term reversals and ensuring the effectiveness of Carbon Farming initiatives. To date, permanence periods are based mainly on forests, are

too long for agricultural crops, and make it difficult for farmers to approach selling carbon credits. Specific procedures should be thought of for agriculture, also based on pedo-climatic areas.

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policymakers, Scientists, Business operators

24.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

The issue of additionality in agriculture for Carbon Farming lies in ensuring that carbon sequestration practices lead to genuine, new reductions in greenhouse gas emissions beyond business-as-usual activities. If farmers are already implementing sustainable practices, it is important to reward them without requiring further improvements or monitoring the increase of carbon stock. Additionality must be assessed in a double procedure, if best practices are already implemented or if they are not. Moreover, the criteria for additionality in various certification standards can differ and may often be unclear. Therefore, it is essential to harmonize these criteria as much as possible, including the methodologies and indicators to be used. Finally, it is important to establish a timeframe for the permanence of these additional effects to maintain eligibility within a certification scheme.

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policymakers, Scientists, Business operators

24.6. Concrete steps for implementation

Social acceptance of Carbon Farming practices by farmers is fundamental to their correct implementation. However, perceptions of these production practices vary widely. Social factors influencing the adoption of Carbon Farming practices need to be assessed, to tailor recommendations and promote their adoption. One of the key issues is the lack of knowledge among farmers about what Carbon Farming entails and its implications. In this respect, knowledge exchange processes and support networks are crucial for scaling up these practices. In addition, the diversity of farmers' motivations, values and professional identities leads to different positions and predispositions towards sustainable farm management. Since farmers are not a homogeneous group, understanding the values and preferences that shape their practices is essential to effectively promote Carbon Farming.

To whom: Policymakers, Scientists, Business operators

Session 25: Opportunities and challenges in proximal sensing–based monitoring for Carbon Farming

Main organisers: University of Helsinki, Wageningen University, Yard Stick PBC

Session description

Proximal sensing technologies hold great potential for advancing Carbon Farming practices across Europe by enabling accurate, cost-effective monitoring of carbon (C) dynamics. These technologies offer significant support for the Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) of carbon sequestration. In this session, organized by CREDIBLE Focus Group 3.2 (FG3.2), we will explore how proximal sensing can enhance sustainable agriculture, particularly through precise measurement of carbon storage in soils and vegetation. By providing reliable data on soil carbon dynamics, these technologies can help land managers make informed decisions in Carbon Farming initiatives and provide the rigorous MRV required if Carbon Farming efforts will provide real economic value to land managers and project developers alike. However, challenges remain, especially around digitalization, user-friendliness, and cost-effectiveness for land managers.

The session explored various related aspects of proximal sensing for soil C and Carbon Farming from other leading soil C market stakeholders. Its aim was to foster a deeper understanding of the opportunities proximal sensing offers for Carbon Farming while addressing concepts and bottlenecks of (automated) monitoring and verification processes via proximal sensing tools.

Issues

Advancing Carbon Farming through proximal sensing technologies

- How proximal sensing tools can enable accurate and cost-effective monitoring of soil and vegetation carbon dynamics, enhancing sustainable agriculture and carbon sequestration efforts?

Challenges in implementation and adoption

- Critical challenges, including the need for improved digitalization, user-friendliness, and cost-effectiveness of proximal sensing technologies to ensure broader acceptance and usability among land managers.

Strengthening MRV protocols and economic viability

- The role of proximal sensing in strengthening MRV protocols to ensure the economic value of Carbon Farming initiatives, while addressing the bottlenecks in technology integration and market alignment.

Recommendations

25.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Proximal sensing technologies (e.g., VIS-NIR-MIR spectroscopy) provide a cost-effective and scalable measurement method for MRV (Measurement, Reporting, and Verification) of soil organic carbon (SOC), enabling more frequent, yet still accurate monitoring for Carbon Farming initiatives. Hence, relevant EU legislation (e.g., under delegated acts and implementing acts) should ensure that MRV strategies incorporate proximal sensing technologies alongside laboratory chemical analysis (used for calibration and validation).

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies

25.2. Concrete steps for implementation

EU funding should be increased to support research and innovation in proximal sensing technologies. For example, funding aimed at enhancing the accuracy of proximal sensing technologies would accelerate their adoption in MRV. Such funding could focus on building or extending open-source proximal sensing data libraries, such as those developed by ISRIC, which are required to estimate TOC. At present, most extensive libraries are privately owned.

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies

25.3. Lesson learnt

A good-but-not-perfect methodological framework should be prioritized over delayed perfection to avoid stalling progress. Verra VM0042 is an example of a well-developed rounded methodology. However, VM0042 has detailed guidelines on bulk density (BD) which potentially hinder proximal sensing-focused projects. To support Carbon Farming, a more flexible methodology could be developed to prevent valuable projects from being sidelined due to overly restrictive criteria. When an approach is peer-reviewed and published in a scientific journal this can be seen as an indicator of the quality of the approach.

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies.

Session 26: Integrating MRV methodologies and Incentives to reduce N₂O emissions in Carbon Farming

Main organisers: i-BEC, Proba

Session description

This session explored how integrating advanced tools of remote proximal sensing, with sustainable agricultural interventions can enhance monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) efforts, enabling carbon finance mechanisms.

Reducing N₂O emissions requires the adoption of practices like Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers (EEFs), which optimize nitrogen use efficiency and reduce emissions at the source. Complementary approaches, such as incorporating biostimulants and biochar, further support emission reductions while improving soil health and crop productivity. However, these advanced practices often present financial barriers for farmers. To overcome this, incentivization mechanisms like voluntary carbon market (VCM) credits and insetting frameworks within agri-food supply chains are essential. These mechanisms align corporate climate goals with sustainable agricultural practices, creating financial rewards for farmers while ensuring compliance with international carbon standards.

The session discussed a pathway for integrating state of the art MRV methodologies, innovative agricultural practices such as EEF, and robust incentivization mechanisms into Carbon Farming. By doing so, it aims to reduce N₂O emissions, enhance soil health, and deliver measurable, verifiable climate benefits that align with both farmer livelihoods and corporate sustainability objectives.

Issues

- Adoption of enhanced efficiency fertilizers to reduce fertilizer related emissions
- Standards and Baselines
- Adoption of new MRV technologies for related quantifications

Recommendations

26.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

As agriculture relies heavily on fertilizer use, which significantly contributes to global emissions, Carbon Farming must go beyond carbon sequestration to include targeted strategies for reducing N₂O emissions. Reducing N₂O emissions requires the adoption of practices like Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers (EEFs), which optimize nitrogen use efficiency and reduce emissions at the source. However, these advanced practices often present financial barriers for farmers. To overcome this, incentivization mechanisms like voluntary

carbon market (VCM) credits and insetting frameworks within agrifood supply chains are essential. These mechanisms align corporate climate goals with sustainable agricultural practices, creating financial rewards for farmers while ensuring compliance with international carbon standards.

How to get the upstream industries to play along:

Most agricultural decarbonization projects target reductions in the range of 20–30% for fertilizer-related emissions. Achieving over 50% reduction is rare and noteworthy.

Large-scale adoption of advanced technologies like CRF, nitrification inhibitors, or green ammonia-based fertilizers is still emerging, especially in coordinated efforts across supply chains.

To whom: farmers, food processors/retailers, policymakers, MRV technologies providers

26.2. Open questions

Climate resilience, particularly in the context of Carbon Farming, requires the adoption of interdisciplinary research and technological advancements to address open issues related to accuracy and scalability. These challenges directly impact the credibility, effectiveness, and operational feasibility of Carbon Farming initiatives. Current methods for measuring nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide, and methane emissions lack standardization and scalability, making it difficult to ensure reliable monitoring across different landscapes. Further work is needed to establish robust protocols that integrate advanced MRV technologies, including remote sensing, in-field sensors, and AI-supported process-based modeling.

The widespread adoption is hindered by the absence of universal frameworks for assessing the effectiveness of new technologies and practices aimed at emission reduction and soil carbon sequestration. Without standardized methodologies, stakeholders struggle to verify the impact of climate-smart agricultural practices, limiting their integration into policy and market-based mechanisms.

To whom: policymakers, businesses, government, academia

26.3. Concrete steps for implementation

The integration of low-cost, portable field-deployable sensors as part of an advanced N₂O toolkit for Monitoring and Reporting (MR) can support carbon monitoring, expanding the capabilities of traditional wet-lab approaches, enabling real-time, on-site measurement of nitrous oxide emissions, offering a scalable and cost-effective method of tracking emissions directly in the field. By complementing wet-lab testing, immediate, actionable data can be acquired to optimize agricultural practices for carbon sequestration and emissions reduction. This technology not only enhances the accuracy of environmental assessments but also facilitates more efficient, decentralized monitoring, supporting the compliance with carbon market standards and incentive schemes.

In parallel, these tools can be integrated with Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) to orchestrate a synchronized effort. NBSs are recognized as effective tools for carbon sequestration, as they mimic natural processes to address land use and management, promote human health, and enhance biodiversity. The CARBONICA HORIZON project exemplifies how such innovations can support end-users in transitioning to sustainable agricultural practices, creating a comprehensive system that links real-time data collection with sustainable land management strategies.

To whom: policymakers, businesses, government, academia

26.4. Lessons learnt

Establishing project-based baselines is essential to ensure that carbon claims are based on accurate, localized baselines and new data acquisitions, which helps prevent overestimation and ensures credibility. The use of Earth Observation technologies enables reliable monitoring of land use changes and carbon sequestration at scale, providing data necessary for verifying carbon credits. Additionally, standardized approaches are crucial for validating innovations in climate-resilient testing. Developing clear standards for assessing new agricultural practices and technologies ensures consistent evaluation, allowing for better investment and policy making. The financial viability of Carbon Farming also remains a critical challenge, as farmers and land managers often face high upfront costs with uncertain economic returns, discouraging investment in sustainable practices. To address this, new incentive mechanisms—such as VCMs—must be developed, and should be supported by reliable, scalable methodologies and cost-effective solutions that ensure accessibility and economic feasibility for all stakeholders.

To whom: Policymakers (who will be responsible for the definition of the standardized baseline) and project developers and farmers (who will be responsible for Carbon Farming implementation).

Session 27: Unlocking data for MRV: Data sharing for effective Carbon Farming

Main organisers: Agrosolutions, ELGO-DIMITRA, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Soil Capital

Session description

The digitization and automation of robust Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems within the CRCF framework are critical to scaling carbon removal activities effectively. Accurate MRV systems rely on high-quality soil carbon (meta)data and associated farm activity data, which are crucial for calibrating and validating models. However, soil carbon (meta) data is often scattered across various platforms and initiatives.

Building upon insights from the Credible FG3.4 discussion, we emphasize the critical role of long-term monitoring site (LTM) data in i) calibration, validation, and simplification of models, ii) validation of MRV approach, iii) upscaling results from local to regional level and iv) support for digitalization. One major challenge highlighted in our earlier analysis was the limited access to open data and the lack of effective data-sharing mechanisms. Similar issues were observed from the 1st European Carbon Farming Summit that soil databases that are not shared for broader application—particularly by the private sector. This highlights the urgent need for greater inter-sector transparency and collaboration.

This session expanded the scope of discussion beyond LTM data to include both public and private datasets and seek to address the challenges of data quality and accessibility. Potential solutions include promoting open access and exploring dual licensing for data sharing. Federated Learning approaches and Data-sharing platforms also present promising solutions for addressing privacy and competitive concerns.

Issues

- What data is required for farmers to claim public subsidies (e.g., under the Common Agricultural Policy) and to participate in voluntary carbon markets?
- How can we reduce the burden on farmers when reporting and collecting data for multiple purposes?
- What business models or reward systems could incentivize effective data sharing in public and private sectors?
- How do companies enable trust in data sharing along the value chain?

Recommendations

27.1. Recommendation for action

Adopt “**Collect Once, Use Many Times**” principle by utilizing user-friendly software connecting with data-sharing platforms

- Farmers face repetitive data requests from CAP, Carbon Farming projects, and scope 3 emissions, leading to fatigue and errors.
- Invest in **interoperable digital platforms** to connect existing systems via **APIs**, so that data entered once can serve multiple reporting needs.
- **Goal:** reduce administrative burden and improve data accuracy

27.2. Recommendation for action

Implement clear data sharing agreements & incentivize data exchange

- Researchers and private companies often mistrust each other over data ownership and usage rights.
- Create **standard data sharing agreement templates** (e.g., dual licensing for LTM data or including third parties in case of joint ownership of data) that define commercial vs. non-commercial use, ensure proper citations, and offer federated modelling without sharing raw data.
- Introduce a “**research commenting period**” where project developers share relevant documents with data contributors for review (e.g., within 30 days); install procedures for transparent publication of the reviews.
- Enhance trust and incentivize data exchange for maintaining LTM. A transparent environment where stakeholders feel confident about the fact that their data is used ethically and effectively.

27.3. Recommendation for action

Extend LTM networks to on-farm monitoring networks

- Current LTM sites were not specifically designed for Carbon Farming, resulting in limited representation across pedoclimatic regions, lack of certain management practices, and smaller plot sizes.
- Establish on-farm monitoring networks, including commercial farms, to capture real-life conditions relevant to Carbon Farming.
- Expand LTM design to an on-farm monitoring network with real-life data can help validate MRV tools at field scale and improve overall accuracy.

27.4. Recommendation for action

Enhance trust in data sharing along the value chain

- With diverse stakeholder interests, data-sharing arrangements must prioritize **transparency, accountability, and mutual benefits.**

- For the 3rd ECFS, we will dive deeper into secure infrastructures and privacy regulations to engage all stakeholders along the value chain for a sustainable transition.

Session 28: Baseline approaches for monitoring soil carbon removals: Public – private synergies

Main organisers: GMV, ILVO, INRAE, JRC

Session description

In the voluntary carbon markets, an activity should generate carbon removals or soil emission reductions in excess of a baseline to respect the ‘additionality’ principle. In mineral agricultural soils, the baseline represents the change of the soil carbon stock in time under the business as usual (BAU) scenario, as if farming activities under a Carbon Farming project would not have occurred. When calculating net carbon removals by farming activities, the carbon removal (or reduced emissions) achieved should then be subtracted from the baseline—a key component in Carbon Farming projects.

Existing MRV methodologies in the Voluntary Carbon Market mostly adopt baselines that are specific for a field or farm. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Regulation (CRCF), however, requires a standardised baseline rather than activity-specific baselines. These standardised baselines should be highly representative of the standard performance of comparable practices and processes in similar social, economic, environmental, regulatory and technological circumstances and take into account the geographical context, including local pedoclimatic and regulatory conditions. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the EU-funded research projects MARVIC, MRV4SOC and ORCaSa proposed several options to calculate the standardised baseline for carbon removals in mineral soil. In the Annex I of the Draft CRCF methodology for mineral soils and agroforestry that was presented to the CRCF expert group in October 2024, these options were summarised into two major groups: (a) an average change in soil carbon stocks, for example by a combination of inventory-based (LUCAS) and large scale modelling downscaled by machine learning and (b) the modelled standard practice in a region with similar pedo-climatic circumstances. The first approach provides a mean delta SOC (ton C/ha/year) for a given area under similar conditions. For the modelled practice-driven option, a hybrid “specific-standardised” approach is proposed, where the baseline is modelled using farm-specific soil data and standard regional practices as input. While those approaches underlie different interpretations of the standardised baseline concept and explore some possible methods, several others approaches are possible. These encompass the scale of applicability (EU or regional), calculation ex-ante or re-calculated ex-post, types of models and model combinations used, with or without remote sensing data assimilation.

This session reflected on the different options to calculate standardised baselines and to reflect on what the public sector can provide and what private sectors need related to their experiences in practice. Through open dialogue, the session aimed to identify differences in our methodologies, and to find collaborative solutions. Additionally, this session highlighted

the importance of regional contexts and the role of pedo-climatic and regulatory circumstances in establishing accurate and reliable baselines.

Issues

- Will the Standardised Baseline (SB) serve CRCF objectives?
- Will the SB encourage farmers to implement new sustainable farming practices?
- How can we ensure that the EU 2050 Target will fully recognise CRCF efforts?
- Will farmers that are engaged in a carbon program shift to CRCF?
- Can SB values be treated as a range (corridor) to verify the project-specific baseline?
- How can the SB serve all use cases and meet all stakeholders' objectives?
- How to ensure that the SB is properly defined so that it provides real environmental benefits?

Recommendations

28.1. Specific versus standardised baseline

Activity specific baseline:

Advantages:

- More specific for each farm
- Possible to reward reduced decomposition of OM

Disadvantages:

- Time consuming to calculate individual CO₂-plans
- Expensive soil samples

- Sensitive to interpretation
- Difficult to reward front runners who are already applying measures

Standardised baseline:

Advantages:

- Less time consuming to calculate individual CO₂-plans
- Easy to automate calculations
- Front runners can be rewarded

Suggestions:

- Choose regional standard based on modelling and soil sampling
- Go for activity-based rewarding: no need for time consuming calculations and expensive soil samples
- Focus on insetting

Challenge:

- How to set regional baselines that motivate a big group of farmers?

To choose a baseline, the discussion is: What is more important: having a strict and very reliable methodology but no farmers participating; or having a methodology that better fits farmers' practice and have more farmers participating. We should aim at the highest participation possible, because then most carbon is fixed.

28.2. Choosing multiple baselines

- Should multiple baseline types be considered, with clear guidelines on which is best suited for the MRV approach, project objectives, or farm profiles?
- Key baseline definitions and selection criteria should align on:
 - Temporal framework – Static vs. dynamic baselines.
 - Reference system – Rotational, harvest-to-harvest, or crop-specific.
 - Baseline approach – Counterfactual modelling vs. witness-site comparisons (as used in forestry and measure-and-remeasure methodologies).

28.3. A mixed approach

To address these challenges, we propose an alternative crop-specific counterfactual baseline approach. Under this method, each project year is compared to the same crop in the baseline scenario. The baseline is modelled using the same crop as in the project scenario for that year, while applying historical management practices specific to that crop. These practices are aggregated at the regional level, enabling standardization of common management practices prior to the practice change.

This approach retains field specificity by using crop-, soil-, and climate-specific data for each field while also introducing standardization through the application of regional-level

management practices. The key advantage is that it provides the most accurate representation of how practice changes affect soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by eliminating the confounding effects of crop rotation inherent in the field-specific rotational baseline. Additionally, this approach aligns more closely with farmer decision-making, as practice changes are typically implemented at the crop level rather than the field level, which may encourage broader adoption. Finally, this methodology supports the implementation of Scope 3 emissions reduction projects by emphasizing practice changes at the crop level, facilitating integration into corporate sustainability frameworks.

Session 29: (Non)-permanence and time dependency of carbon sequestration in Carbon Farming – Current accounting approaches and ways ahead

Main organisers: Agroscope, Agrosolutions, Thuenen Institute, Wageningen Environmental Research

Session description

Accrual of organic carbon in mineral soils and changes in GHG fluxes with peatland rewetting are often characterised by variable rates over time. For example, soil organic carbon sequestration tends to follow a hyperbolic shape with new steady states often reached after only a few decades. This has implications for the calculated climate effect. Perhaps even more importantly, both carbon uptake and emission savings are reversible.

Carbon certification frameworks currently address the risk of non-permanence by applying financial buffers to the amount of carbon credits calculated. This approach has limitations, especially as it does not use a scientific basis to establish the size of the buffers. In the end, the constraints emerging from the need to compare permanent and temporary carbon removals may impose excessive administrative constraints on farmers and Carbon Farming projects, hindering their implementation at scale.

This session focused on the impact of this (non) permanency issues for the carbon removal market and monitoring with the overall aim of analysing and improving existing approaches.

Issues

- What are the climate impacts of permanent vs. non-permanent sinks or removals?
- What are the implications for monitoring beyond the project period?
- How do current certification schemes deal (or not deal) with the issues of changing rates, non-permanence and additionality?
- how relevant is the “CO₂ equivalent” unit to account for climate benefit of non-permanent removals?
- Are current payment schemes and incentives suitable for dealing with non-linearities and non-permanence?

Recommendations

29.1. Proposal to improve CRCF

If the issue of non-permanence is addressed through permanency discounts, these should be based on a physics-based equivalence between the climate impacts of non-permanent and permanent removal. The absolute global warming potential based on cumulative radiative forcing could be used to calculate this equivalence on the basis of project activity and monitoring duration, and of a time horizon longer than 500 years or even 1000 years.

To whom: CRCF

29.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

If the issue of non-permanence is addressed through permanency discounts using the methodology in Recommendation 1, one should note that almost no cooling effect remains after all sequestered carbon is released. For temporary removals to be beneficial in terms of temperature change, the temporary removals must be maintained at least until global mean temperature is peaking.

To whom: CRCF

29.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

If temporary units are used to address the issue of non-permanence, a framework ensuring that **removals are constantly renewed** if the units expire (“stacking of removals”) is needed.

To whom: CRCF

29.4. Open question

Further research is needed to better characterize the amount of sequestered carbon that remains for decades/centuries if (i) the practice is stopped, (ii) the soil is disturbed, and under (iii) climate change, and combinations of all three (= what durability can we expect from carbon sequestration in soils?).

To whom: Research

29.5. Lesson learnt

The fact that carbon sequestering is a non-permanent climate mitigation option should not be a reason not to start with Carbon Farming. The radiative forcing method shows that at least a period of one or two decades of carbon removal is needed to diminish emission of CO₂ from the soil.

Land Use Change has a big influence on the carbon removal rate.

To whom: farmers, companies

Session 30: Addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking in Earth Observation-based MRV systems for Carbon Farming

Main organisers: CinSOIL GmbH, EARSC

Session description

The objective of this session was to identify the key requirements and priorities for addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking for Earth Observation-based MRV for carbon removals. This is a critical issue in light of new regulations and schemes, particularly since uncertainty in organic carbon measurements can often exceed the actual changes. Meanwhile, multiple models are emerging, and there is a pressing need for consistent, fair benchmarking across varied soils, climates, and farming practices.

Participants shared lessons on how best to engage in understanding how to validate and compare different models, leading to more credible carbon removal assessments in Carbon Farming practices. This discussion is especially timely as organizations seek reliable proof of soil carbon gains, which support both climate goals and sustainable agriculture strategies.

Issues

Uncertainty in EO-based MRV impacts credibility and adoption

- Carbon removal schemes require reliable, transparent MRV. However, uncertainty in soil organic carbon measurements often exceeds actual expectations, creating challenges for verification and market credibility. (See Recommendation 30.1)

Benchmarking MRV models across diverse landscapes is essential

- Without standardized benchmarking, MRV models produce inconsistent results across different soils, climates, and farming practices, limiting comparability and trust. (See Recommendation 30.2)

Data governance is a key barrier to EO-based MRV adoption

- The lack of clear policies on data access, ownership, and interoperability limits the ability to integrate diverse datasets into MRV models. (See Recommendation 30.3)

Uncertainty in EO-based MRV impacts credibility and adoption

- Carbon removal schemes require reliable, transparent MRV. However, uncertainty in soil organic carbon measurements often exceeds actual expectations, creating challenges for verification and market credibility. (See Recommendation 30.1)

Benchmarking MRV models across diverse landscapes is essential

- Without standardized benchmarking, MRV models produce inconsistent results across different soils, climates, and farming practices, limiting comparability and trust. (See Recommendation 30.2)

Data governance is a key barrier to EO-based MRV adoption

- The lack of clear policies on data access, ownership, and interoperability limits the ability to integrate diverse datasets into MRV models. (See Recommendation 30.3)

Recommendations

30.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Establishing reasonable uncertainty thresholds and harmonized protocols to reduce them. Aligning policy and market expectations is critical to ensure acceptance and scaling of EO-based MRV systems.

Proposed steps:

- Develop sector-specific guidelines on acceptable uncertainty thresholds that balance scientific rigor with policy and market feasibility.
- Establish best practices for integrating EO data with in-situ measurements to enhance MRV accuracy.
- Align uncertainty thresholds with global carbon market requirements and regulatory frameworks to support investment in Carbon Farming.
- Promote transparency in uncertainty reporting to build trust among carbon credit buyers, farmers, land owners and policymakers.

To whom: Policymakers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts

30.2. Recommendations for action

Developing a structured EU-wide benchmarking framework with harmonized validation datasets is necessary to ensure fair and consistent assessments.

- Create a centralized platform with dedicated funding to enable fair benchmark of MRV models across different agro-ecological zones.
- Develop harmonized validation datasets covering varied soils, climates, and land-use practices to improve model comparability.
- Ensure that benchmarking methodologies align with international standards to enhance market acceptance and regulatory compliance.
- Engage industry, research institutions, and policymakers in the co-design of the platform to ensure practical implementation and usability.

To whom: Policymakers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts

30.3. Open questions

Stronger data-sharing frameworks, balancing privacy and accessibility, are needed to facilitate cross-sector collaboration and improve MRV performance.

- Establish clear policies on data ownership, sharing, and interoperability to facilitate the integration of public and private datasets into MRV systems.
- Promote EU-wide standardization of Carbon Farming data formats to enhance usability across MRV platforms.
- Develop guidelines on ethical data use and privacy protection, ensuring farmers and landowners rights are respected.
- Foster partnerships between policymakers, researchers, and industry to create an open-access data ecosystem for Carbon Farming.
- Promote the effort of harmonizing scattered data sources, for example collaborating with EEA Copernicus in-situ program.

To whom: Policymakers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts, EU agencies

Session 31: Earth Observation for Carbon Farming: exploring existing solutions and future user needs

Main organisers: ESA SEF

Session description

This session aimed to raise awareness of Earth Observation (EO)-based tools that support Carbon Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV), providing practical insights for end-users such as land managers, farmers, and policymakers. It introduced participants to existing EO solutions and highlighted their benefits and limitations. It gathered feedback from participants to identify short-term needs, such as training, and longer-term requirements that could inform future European Space Agency (ESA) projects.

Issues

- Understanding existing EO capabilities for Carbon Farming, more specifically for MRV
- Mapping the capabilities to the different “value chain” actors (e.g. Carbon Farming projects, certification/rating agencies, farmers/land managers)
- Identifying user needs (e.g. EO products or training)

Recommendations

31.1. Lessons learned

EO is being used by actors across the Carbon Farming value chain, from carbon credit certification/standardisation bodies and carbon rating agencies, to project developers and farmers.

These actors are using EO in several different ways, for example:

- Monitor among others: crop cover and tillage, deforestation rates, burn event analysis, wetland/forest detection, land use/land cover change, vegetation indices, soil vitality and soil parameters.
- Input for baseline establishment (e.g. historical data, input for SOC assessment) in combination with in-situ data.
- Assessing risk factors before, during and after the project, on the project parcels and around the project parcels.

This helps improve MRV methodologies, leading to a more transparent and robust carbon crediting process and ultimately enhancing the credibility and efficiency of carbon markets.

Whilst using EO brings added-value, some challenges remain, among others:

- Significant computational resources and expertise are needed to handle and integrate EO data, which stakeholders may not always have access to (e.g., project developers, VVBs, etc.)
- EO data quality varies due to sensor limitations, cloud cover, and differing resolutions, impacting the precision of carbon stock assessments.
- On-the-ground measurements remain essential to validate EO/satellite data which can make the process resource-intensive.

It is important to understand the added-value EO can bring to Carbon Farming, and especially MRV methodologies, encouraging its use in the CRCF and any carbon-farming related framework and practices. However, this should be done in a realistic manner, understanding the limitations of EO/satellite data, and not as the exclusive source of data.

To whom: Actors across the value chain

31.2. Concrete steps for implementation

It is necessary to continue to foster exchanges and interactions on the use of EO throughout the value chain to identify where the needs and gaps lie, and how to address them - whether this be an issue of capacity-building or an issue of capability development on the technical side.

For the technical side, the key discussion was around what EO is useful for, and for what not. EO is very useful for many parameters, but monitoring soil organic carbon (SOC) remains difficult. Technologies on this could be key and bring significant benefits. The other technical shortcoming mentioned is a lack of in-situ data, as EO technologies cannot exist without these data to ensure accuracy and reliability.

On the capacity-building and training side, there is a lack of awareness to be addressed when it comes to farmers. To work systematically on uptake of EO solutions in the Carbon Farming domain, there must be co-design, with the users involved in development. Additionally, a key stakeholder group identified is agronomists, who are often introducing farmers to new technologies and supporting them in the uptake and integration into their activities. Additionally, the importance of a regional or local approach was highlighted. It is important to work together with local and regional associations that represent farmers or landowners.

To whom: 1) Earth observation community, i.e., ESA and other EO experts who seek to increase the uptake of EO in Carbon Farming.

Session 32: Real-life MRV challenges and solutions for the EU CRCF

Main organisers: Agreena, Seqana, Space4Good

Session description

This session aimed at sharing the real-world experiences of quantifying carbon sequestration in mineral soil and agroforestry projects. The consortium shared its collective experiences of implementing MRV across carbon removal projects under various methodologies and offered best practices for upcoming projects in the context of the EU CRCF methodology for mineral soils and agroforestry.

In particular, the session focused on three topics around (i) Quantification as discussed in the EU CRCF draft: smart soil sampling design, (ii) the quantification approach “Measure and Model”, and (iii) above-ground biomass modelling with remote sensing. It offered best practices for the EU CRCF based on industry experience.

Issues

- The current approach to MRV in EU CRCF is not scalable, as it prevents innovative high-quality approaches and technologies from being leveraged and raises too high demands for ground sampling.
- To allow the use of innovative approaches a simple yet precise and consistent approach to uncertainty estimation and deduction is needed, which is currently lacking.
- Sampling design requirements are confusing and must be simplified.

Recommendations

32.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Uncertainty Estimation and Deduction must be aligned with best practices from IPCC and existing soil carbon markets:

- a. All quantification of carbon removals via Carbon Farming must account for uncertainty and only credit conservative estimates subjected to uncertainty deductions.
- b. Project proponents shall clearly and transparently report the overall uncertainty deduction of their project, including the breakdown into its components and how they were calculated.
- c. These conservative estimates and uncertainty deductions should be based on one-sided confidence intervals (aligned with IPCC and soil carbon market standards).

- d. A minimum confidence level (e.g. 67%) must be prescribed by the policy-makers to balance the risks of under-crediting (borne by operators) and over-crediting (borne by society).
- e. When a valid and objective uncertainty estimation and deduction process (as above) is prescribed, the choice of the quantification approach and technology can be left to the project proponent to use the best technology/approach for the specific context under the condition that it complies with the uncertainty estimation and deduction to meet and document minimum requirements.

To whom: CRCF methodology authors

32.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

Sampling Design guidance must be simplified and aligned with uncertainty estimation/deduction. The only hard requirements, which must be implemented and documented are:

- Sampling design shall be design-unbiased (i.e. variant of a probability sample)
- The sample size must be at minimum large enough to allow for quantification of a conservative estimate (lower bound of one-sided Confidence Interval) with a tolerable error calculated as half of the expected SOC sequestration.

This requires ex-ante estimation of the SOC stock change and SOC Stock (change) variance, which must be well documented. In practical terms, this bare minimum sample size will allow crediting even with an uncertainty deduction as high as 99% as long as the actual SOC sequestration minus the tolerable error is greater than 0. However, project proponents are economically incentivized to take more samples than that to reduce their uncertainty deductions.

An example of one commonly used Sampling Design approach should be provided (e.g. Stratified random sampling with some guidance on how to do it). Project proponents can follow that example approach but can also deviate as long as they meet the hard requirements listed above.

To whom: CRCF methodology authors/operators/MRV providers implementing sampling designs/campaigns

32.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

Agroforestry systems require distinct MRV from forests

Agroforestry-specific and tree-species specific allometric equations or biomass conversion and expansion factors (BCEF) are needed to ensure correct calculations of carbon storage in aboveground and below-ground biomass. With this information currently lacking, certification methods often only provide guidelines based on experience from forestry, whilst tree allometry is very different in forests than in agroforestry systems. This could give huge discrepancies in the expected stored carbon and the true stored carbon. Certification

schemes should critically assess the proposed biomass calculation methods by comparing the outcomes of different calculation methods.

Field data collection protocols for agroforestry should be based on random stratified sampling, meaning that a sufficient sample size is required per predefined strata based on tree age, tree management, soil type, groundwater level, and other relevant differentiators. Previous datasets and the level of variation found in them should inform the sample size per stratum based on the standard deviation, alpha, power, and relevant difference.

To whom: to CRCF methodology authors

32.4. Lessons learnt

Allowing for innovative measurement technology (to CRCF methodology authors/ operators/ MRV providers):

The uptake of emerging technologies such as NIR field scanners for SOC or mobile laser scanning (MLS) for agroforestry should be stimulated since the cost-effectiveness of these techniques for estimating tree volume is likely to improve greatly within the next 5 to 10 years. Farmers could easily collect data with a mobile application/device, meaning low MRV costs, whilst also safeguarding the validity and coherence of the data. Current apps for measuring the diameter at breast height (DBH), such as ForestScanner, demonstrate the future potential of this technology.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.5. Lesson learnt: High Integrity Baseline

Use **multiple data sources** (historical records, field observations, primary data, remote sensing) to set the baseline. Prioritize **additionality & conservatism** in the baseline setting. Avoid “one-size-fits-all” standardization that dilutes on-farm, real change.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.6. Lesson learnt: Effective Monitoring at Scale

Integrate **satellite** with **ground truthing data collection** to ensure scalability of Carbon Farming monitoring initiatives. Automate field detection to manage broad geographic regions. What is the minimum we need to ensure we know what is happening on the field. Multiple sources for data checks. Integration of data sources will be important.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.7. Lesson learnt: Avoiding Double counting through data management

Establish **clear protocols** for data custody from field to credit issuance to avoid double counting. Incorporate **independent third-party audits** to reduce risks of fraud and guarantee the scientific rigour of applied methods. Verification tools already exist for checking field

boundaries to ensure farmers or landowners are not participating. One big challenge is that auditors are not readily available - the market is small for on-the-field audits on a project level - certifying more auditors.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.8. Lesson learnt: Measure and model as a way to demonstrate constant improvements.

Combine process-based models (e.g., RothC) with advanced remote sensing. Measure and model support annual credit issuance. Enhance economic viability (better cash flow) and scientific rigor over time. Errors are already strong - so what you feed the model is important and how it is improved over time is also important.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.9. Lesson learnt

Use a combination of field data, remote sensing, and machine learning models to minimize manual labour for collecting field data, while keeping the local accuracy high. Labor is currently a high-cost factor for agroforestry Carbon Farming MRV. Current tools like CarboCatch demonstrate the potential to reduce field data. At some point, field data is expected to merely serve as a validation of model predictions, whilst the need for field data to train models will be minimised.

To whom: CRCF team

32.10. Lesson learnt

When using remote sensing for monitoring carbon sequestration in Agroforestry, a more detailed approach to account for mixed tree-crop structures, smaller-scale variations, and dynamic land use patterns, ensuring high model accuracy is required. While using mid-resolution satellite data (e.g., 10m of Copernicus) for carbon monitoring may suffice for forestry, it lacks the fine-scale detail necessary for agroforestry monitoring. Integrating very high-resolution satellite imagery (e.g., Pleiades Neo) and LiDAR data into MRV solutions will significantly enhance the precision of agroforestry carbon accounting. In addition, it has been found that locally trained models (on the same types of systems) outperform more generalized models.

To whom: CRCF team

32.11. Concrete steps for implementation

Advocating for freely available or partially open very high-resolution (e.g. 1.3meter resolution) data is essential to improve measurement accuracy, reduce uncertainty, and enhance the credibility of Carbon Farming. This will lower costs for project developers, increase financial returns for farmers, and support broader adoption of agroforestry as a recognized climate solution. Currently, these are available in some countries, but not in all, which creates an inequality in the access to affordable, accurate models. These high-

resolution satellite images will not only benefit Carbon Farming measurements to be more accurate and more affordable, it will also support member states in monitoring other environmental/ social indicators, for climate resilience and other regulation compliance. For example, to report to the nature restoration law, improve flood and drought defense, generate insights for CAP and more. Advocating for higher-resolution data will enhance compliance with EU regulations by making monitoring more accurate, affordable, and transparent, ultimately improving trust and traceability.

To whom: Copernicus/ EU Commission

Session 33: How technology and AI is supporting the growth of efficient, high-integrity Carbon Farming markets

Main organisers: GreenO, SAS, Social Carbon Foundation, Walton Institute

Session description

The evolving landscape of Carbon Farming projects demands processes that are rigorous, transparent, inexpensive and adaptable to meet growing market needs. This interactive session explored recent advancements in the use of AI and technology to address the major challenges to rapidly scaling high integrity carbon and environmental asset markets.

Leading practitioners addressed the market challenges, what they see as possible in the future and provided tangible examples of best practice they are involved with now. The session also addressed the system blockers and enablers that should be targeted to support rapid scaling of high-integrity markets.

The aim of the session was to provide practical insights into how digital tools and AI are setting new benchmarks in streamlining processes, cutting costs, and supporting the global expansion of high-integrity carbon markets.

Issues

- **Digitization of certification methodologies:** helping project developers access, apply, and comply with standards more effectively.
- **Documentation review:** Use of AI-powered tools that enable an automated pre-screening phase to check for accuracy, completeness, and compliance to help identify potential issues early in the process, reducing human error, providing faster feedback, and preserving data integrity.
- **Real-time Monitoring:** Using AI-powered tools to automatically track and analyse farming practices, soil health, and crop performance, ensuring precise data collection on carbon sequestration.
- **Data Validation and Credibility Checks:** Data validation by cross-referencing reported practices with satellite imagery, sensor data, and weather patterns to make it possible to detect inconsistencies and flag areas requiring further investigation, all while reducing manual efforts.
- **Automated Verification:** processes that significantly reduce the time and resources required for third-party audits, ensuring that farming initiatives comply with regulatory standards and market requirements.
- **Transparent Reporting:** Built-in reporting mechanisms make the entire process - from data capture to verification - auditable, providing full transparency to regulators, investors, and buyers of carbon credits.

Recommendations

33.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Participate in digital platforms that provide transparent access to carbon credit markets, ensuring fair pricing and reducing reliance on intermediaries.

To whom: Landowners & Project Developers

33.2. Concrete steps for implementation

Leverage remote sensing & AI for real-time monitoring to enhance accuracy in measuring carbon sequestration and reduce verification costs.

To whom: Landowners & Project Developers

33.3: Proposals to improve CRCF

Standardize digital verification and data protocols to ensure interoperability across different AI tools, fostering trust and comparability in the market.

To whom: Policymakers & Regulators

33.4. Proposals to improve CRCF

Ensure AI models are transparent and explainable to avoid black-box algorithms

To whom: Technology companies

33.5. Proposals to improve CRCF

Invest in tech infrastructure that accelerates verification and reduces risks of over-crediting or fraud in voluntary carbon markets.

To whom: Investors and Credit Buyers

Session 34: Rewarding mechanisms: Insights from farmers, agri-food companies and researchers for a successful approach

Main organisers: Climate KIC, DELOITTE, European Alliance for regenerative Agriculture, INRAE

Session description

This session aimed to contribute to the critical component of the CRCF directive: what financial incentive mechanisms would be most relevant for concrete advances in Carbon Farming? For these mechanisms to be effective, they must be adapted to the contexts and challenges of the main stakeholders.

To achieve this, the session discussed the current state of knowledge on existing rewarding mechanisms to provide key elements to the European Carbon Farming community and help identify challenges and opportunities for rewarding mechanisms.

Issues

- Who finances what in the transition and how much financing is available and is it sufficient to achieve the objective?
- How can we move from monoculture funding mechanisms that target greenhouse gases to a Carbon Farming type mechanism that covers greenhouse gases and removal?
- How can public and private funding be wisely combined to get traction within value chains from agrifood companies to farmers?

Recommendations

34.1. Lessons learnt

- There are diverse rewarding mechanism types, but limited incentives to finance the transition towards economically, ecologically, and socially sustainable agricultural systems.
- Most mechanisms focus primarily on large farm structures; regional strategies should support the adoption of more sustainable farming practices, aiming to include small farmers with limited scope.
- Current supportive measures to engage farmers in the transition (both on-farm and in policies) are still insufficient.
- There is limited articulation between funding instruments (due to double counting and additionality concerns).

- Most rewarding mechanisms focus on carbon removals and emission reductions. There are limited examples that consider climate adaptation.
- There is a need for rewards that support pioneer farmers who have implemented sustainable farming practices before the development of the CRCF.

To whom: Policymakers

34.2. Recommendations for action

- All stakeholders in the food chain need clarity on objectives, methodologies, frameworks, and reporting requirements. As with the concept of Regenerative Agriculture, there is currently no clear definition for Carbon Farming.
- To succeed, future regulations must foster the convergence of all forces. These forces include food chain actors such as farmers, industrials, retailers, policymakers, and solutions providers.
- To get traction at the European level, food chain actors need a supportive context: clarity, information sharing, training, solution access, and financial resources.
- It is essential to reward not only outcomes but also efforts, especially in the agricultural sector, which is influenced by pedoclimatic conditions.

To whom: Policymakers

Session 35: Learning from research and feedback from the field: How to put in place Carbon Farming on a farm? What levers and barriers?

Main organisers: Agrosolutions, Arvalis, Climate-KIC, IDELE, INRAE, Teagasc, Terre Inovia

Session description

Several European projects (Climate Farm Demo, ClieNFarms, ORCaSa, LIFE Carbon Farming) are currently working on the topic of Carbon Farming. These projects have in common the fact of working with farmers putting in place low carbon practices. Therefore, it is interesting to give feedback from the field to illustrate the challenges that occur when talking about Carbon Farming implementation. Moreover, some of these projects can provide information on the types of practices put in place on farms.

Issues

- Assessing the feasibility and performance of Carbon Farming practices
- Ensuring access to knowledge on Carbon Farming practices
- Supporting multi-stakeholder collaboration to empower farmers in the climate transition

Recommendations

35.1. Lessons learnt

Context: There is a lot of information available on different Carbon Farming practices and carbon assessment tools, but farmers and advisors need additional skills to better understand and use these tools.

Recommendation: A structured capacity-building programme is essential to equip farmers and advisors with the skills needed to engage in Carbon Farming effectively. This program should:

- Cover both practical implementation and economic aspects (rewards, taxes, synergies between implementing Carbon Farming measures and farm profitability) as well as audit, MRV, and planning tools.
- Take a systemic and context-specific approach, integrating farm-level tools (there are no one-size-fits-all solution packages).
- Be designed with pedagogical best practices, offering flexible, time-efficient, and modular learning options to fit farmers' and advisors' schedules. Training should be

accessible, both in terms of pedagogical design and in terms of costs (time and money).

- Begin at the educational level, integrating Carbon Farming into high school and agricultural school curricula.
- Be publicly funded or supported through policy frameworks to ensure accessibility.

If costs are involved, they should be accounted for in the cost-benefit assessment of Carbon Farming projects.

To whom: EU and national governments (Ministries of agriculture, environment, education)

35.2. Lessons learnt

Context: There is already a lot of information available on different Carbon Farming practices and carbon assessment tools, but this information is scattered across different platforms in Europe. It is difficult to find a full, clear, and up-to-date knowledge repository.

Recommendation: It is important to develop a permanent and dynamic repository of trusted information on Carbon Farming practices (for example Impact4Soil, Farming For Climate), advisory tools and carbon audit tools consolidated across all European projects. Each new project dealing with this topic should feed its insights and results to the common repository, preventing duplication of efforts and fostering knowledge exchange. Permanent funding to manage the repository is then needed.

To whom: EU Farmbook, EU Commission

35.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: Farmers already have a lot of data to upload to different accounting or regulatory systems in order to get EU funds or other certificates

Recommendation: Simplify systems to lighten the administrative burden for farmers. The CRCF could help harmonise and simplify these processes. If the administrative burden is too heavy (or as heavy as for regulatory requirements), it will prevent farmers from engaging in voluntary projects.

To whom: CRCF

35.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: So far the CRCF is mainly dealing with Carbon Storage and a bit with GHG emissions from soil management. However, “Greenhouse Gas” and “Carbon Storage” Emission Reductions are sometimes antagonistic: improving one may degrade the other.

Recommendation: It is necessary to address Carbon Storage and GHG emission together in order to improve the full carbon balance of farms.

Furthermore, a multicriteria sustainability assessment should be performed, without increasing data requirements too much, in order to have a systemic view of the impact of the different practices. This should integrate economic criteria but also social ones like additional

workload as it can be unacceptable for some farmers. This should not be an eligible criterion to get the certification.

To whom: Research, CRCF

35.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: There are many existing tools across Europe to assess GHG emissions and carbon storage on farms. These tools are adapted to national contexts and have been used by advisors for many years.

Recommendation: It is essential to base Carbon Farming projects on robust tools, on one hand to assess carbon footprints, and on the other hand to evaluate the potential credits generated under different transition scenarios that can actually be implemented by farmers.

Carbon audit tools: there should be several tools (robust) proposed to carry out carbon audits on farms, and not one unique tool for all Europe. Indeed, many advisors have already used tools, adapted to the local contexts.

MRV support tools are essential for implementing Carbon Farming projects, assessing the potential credits and also to evaluate possible different scenarios and then select the “best” one. There is a need for user friendly tools to help in comparison and choice.

To whom: CRCF

35.6. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: In France, the current carbon market does not cover the break-even costs of a significant proportion of projects. Today, it can only encourage or help implement levers for the low-carbon transition.

Recommendation: It is necessary to either have a higher selling price for Carbon Credit, or supplement them with other sources of financing such as sector premium in cash crops sector.

CRCF should be aligned with the GHG protocol for carbon credits evaluation.

CRCF should allow farms to sell carbon credits and in the meantime to receive fundings from companies following SBTI rules. → Need clarification regarding double-counting.

To whom: Companies purchasing carbon credits, CRCF to allow diversified sources of fundings for the same farm.

35.7. Proposals to improve CRCF

Context: changing practices is not only a question of costs It is also a question of skills, workload, and risk.

Recommendation: regarding the Additionality aspect of the CRCF: it should not be restrained to an economic evaluation. Even if a low carbon project is cost-saving, it will not necessarily

be implemented. There are potentially heavy initial investments, but also a risk taken by the farmers and that should be taken into account.

To whom: CRCF

Session 36: What is the farmer's opinion on Carbon Farming?

Main organisers: Bioeconomy Cluster, Carbery farmers cooperative, CoopsAgroES, French Agricultural Chambers, ICOS

Session description

This session presented the work carried out within the framework of the Credible project. This included a survey of around 40 experts on farmers' current perceptions of Carbon Farming.

The results of this work were used in the farmers' panel, moderated by John Brosnan from the Irish Co-operative Organisation Society (ICOS). A French farmer, a Slovak farmer, an Irish farmer, and a representative from Carbery Co-operative shared their views and proposed solutions to improve the image of Carbon Farming within the sector.

Issues

- Barriers to farmers joining the Carbon Farming journey?
- How is integrated Carbon Farming aligned with the broader challenges and trends in the farming community?
- What role should cooperatives and farmers' associations play in enhancing benefits for farmers?

Recommendations

36.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Develop local pilot projects and success stories and network of demo farms - establishment of demonstration farms and small-scale projects in each country to showcase real-world benefits and build trust among farmers.

To whom: Policymakers through CAP measures, or LIFE Program or Horizon Program

36.2. Concrete steps for implementation

To seek synergies with eco-schemes within the CAP by promoting best practices.

This applies in both, 1) economic terms: ensuring complementary payments—within the CAP for the voluntary implementation of best practices, and within the CFCR for achieving specific results in carbon sequestration 2) technical alignment of the practices proposed

To whom: DG Agri with DG Clima

36.3. Lessons learnt

Synergies should be sought with other relevant trends that also focus on SSM sustainable soil management, such as regenerative agriculture, Carbon Farming, precision agriculture, conservation agriculture, organic farming

To whom: Big farmers, International food corporations, Farmer cooperatives

36.4. Lessons learnt

Encourage farmer cooperation and collective strategies. For small and medium-sized farmers to feel that they are meaningfully part of the benefits of Carbon Farming, they can maximise these benefits through cooperation with their peers. Cooperatives in European countries where they are established, as well as other farmer groups elsewhere, can help channel positive opinions from their members by defining joint and shared strategies, leveraging economies of scale, and providing support through technical advisors

To whom: Farmer cooperatives

Session 37: Ireland: An innovative, context specific, approach to Carbon Farming...?

Main organisers: DAFM Ireland, Climate-KIC, Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC), Irish Cooperative Organisation Society, Bord Bia, National Economic and Social Council, Environmental Protection Agency, Teagasc, Irish Strategic Investment Fund

Session description

This session brought together several farmers and experts from Ireland with the following aims:

- Highlight the approach being taken in Ireland to develop a national Carbon Farming framework.
- Identify barriers, opportunities and key stakeholder requirements for the development of a context specific national Carbon Farming framework.
- Identify key recommendations for the practical implementation of the CRCF and for the team in Ireland working on developing the national framework.

Challenges around soil health, water quality and biodiversity loss are inextricably linked to the emissions and removals challenge. Focusing solely on Carbon Farming (i.e. carbon removals in soil and above ground biomass) misses the interdependence between these ecological challenges, all of which are managed together within the farm system. This farm system operates in a broader social and ecological landscape, which is again part of a larger global food system.

Issues

- Barriers and Opportunities of a holistic approach e.g. including emissions, removals in a farm balance sheet approach with biodiversity and water quality as additional parameters
- Understanding stakeholder requirements: what are the priorities from a national Carbon Farming framework for each of these key stakeholder groups?

Recommendations

No recommendations.

Session 38: From peatlands to policy: How praxis can guide EU CRCF certification

Main organisers: Aeco, DG Clima, Greifswald University, IUCN Peatland Programme, MoorFutures, UK Carbon Code

Session description

As the EU moves toward implementing the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), peatlands are envisaged to be the first land use category in the Land Use, Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector with a published certification methodology. Even though certification for peatlands / organic soils is assumed to be easier and the process further elaborated compared to other LULUCF categories, ensuring its robustness, practicality and climatic justness remains a challenge.

This session explored how CRCF methodologies are being developed, providing insights relevant for peatlands specifically and for the evolution of the broader framework in general. It offered a platform to discuss region-specific barriers to certification and to explore potential solutions.

Issues

1. Peatlands as a model for CRCF certification

- Peatlands are expected to be the first land category with a defined certification methodology under the CRCF, making them a key test case for the framework's effectiveness.
- As one of the most carbon-dense ecosystems, peatlands play a crucial role in climate mitigation.

2. Communication strategies for CRCF policy implementation

- Communication strategies are expected to be of major importance for the CRCF implementation success. Involvement of actors at all levels will help shape the implementation and stakeholder perceptions.

3. Ensuring alignment with EU and national policies

- For CRCF certification to be effective, it must be compatible with and its units convertible into those of national GHG inventories and voluntary carbon markets.
- Several European countries already have carbon credit initiatives for peatlands in place (e.g., Germany's MoorFutures, the UK Peatland Code), and their experience should inform the development of the CRCF methodology.

- The quality (a ton is a ton) and additionality of peatland emission reductions and carbon removals must be ensured to attain confidence of carbon markets and policy frameworks.

4. Data availability and sufficiency

- The impact of data on CRCF implementation and development.

Recommendations

38.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Use the experiences from completed and ongoing peatland carbon credit projects to develop clear, standardized criteria for CRCF peatland carbon credit certification. CRCF certification must be transparent and consistent, scientifically robust and precise, and compatible with existing LULUCF reporting frameworks and the voluntary carbon market; certified reduction units must be fully fungible with, or at least convertible into, the units of these frameworks and markets.

To whom: European Commission (DG CLIMA, DG ENV), National Governments, Certification Bodies

38.2. Stakeholder Engagement & Capacity Building

Facilitate structured multi-stakeholder dialogue, ensuring that the knowledge and experiences from completed and ongoing peatland restoration and carbon certification projects are acknowledged and actively integrated into CRCF development.

To whom: EU Institutions, Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market, Farmers

38.3. Clear and transparent communication

For an effective CRCF scheme implementation, we recommend prioritizing clear communication. Keep it simple, honest, and transparent—acknowledging uncertainties is key. Adopt a regional rather than a generalized EU-wide approach, emphasizing a bottom-up strategy that empowers local stakeholders. Foster trust as a foundation and ensure early and continuous engagement throughout the process.

To whom: EU Institutions, Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market

38.4. Action-Oriented CRCF Implementation

Prioritize rewetting peatlands as soon as possible. While we might not have all the data, the overall need is clear. Begin with simple, smart strategies, then learn and adapt as needed. Avoid delays by striving for perfection—practical progress is better than inaction.

To whom: EU Institutions, European Commission (DG CLIMA, DG ENV), Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market

Session 39: Legal opportunities for Carbon Farming: From creation of a registry to the necessary streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework

Main organiser: Philp Lee

Session description

This session proposed a discussion on the legal opportunities and issues relating to Carbon Farming, including the creation of registries and the streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework to enhance climate ambition.

Issues

- The necessity of streamlining EU environmental laws to successfully implement the CRCF
- Creation of a CRCF registry

Recommendations

39.1. Policy coherence

The AGRI team in DG Clima should proactively seek to work with the ENVI team in DG Enviro in order to reconcile Carbon Farming regulation with the existing environmental laws that underpin project authorisation. At present, the two regimes apply distinct, difficult to reconcile requirements that will impede the authorisation of Carbon Farming projects.

39.2. Lesson learnt

The development of the Renewable Energy industry as provided for within RED III has demonstrated that under the existing European environmental law framework, tension arises between climate mitigation measures and traditional means of environmental protection as provided for in the environmental Directives including the Birds, Habitats, EIA and Water Framework Directives.

39.3. Open questions

To facilitate project authorisation, it is crucial that EU environmental laws impacting Carbon Farming projects are streamlined. At present, the CRCF Regulation does not recognise that it overlaps with such laws as the Birds Directive, Habitats Directive, Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive, Environmental Impact Assessment Directive and the Nature Restoration Law. All these laws contain different tests, definitions and obligations.

Article 7 of the CRCF provides that ‘an activity shall do no significant harm to the environment’. This test, borrowed from the EU Taxonomy Regulation, does not correlate with the tests for environmental assessment in the Directives listed above. These include ‘likely to have a significant effect’ and ‘negatively impact the integrity of the site’, for instance. Because the requirement for environmental assessment underpins project authorisation, this incompatibility under the law will inevitably lead to legal challenges.

The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) can only interpret the law and as such EU Commission guidance – while it would be welcomed as an interim measure – is not sufficient where the wording of the law itself is not fit for purpose. Both the definition of ‘activity’ and that of ‘no environmental harm’ need to be equated with tests in the other environmental laws. Otherwise, Carbon Farming projects will be delayed and stopped on the basis of the wording in a Regulation that was in fact designed to ‘facilitate and encourage’ such projects. Unlike traditional means of environmental protection through conservation and limitations on development, climate mitigation measures require facilities for adaptive management and provision for pilot projects in the absence of complete data.

The test of ‘shall do no environmental harm’ cannot be achieved where precise data remains unknown. Yet, postponement of these projects until such data has been gathered precludes the necessary climate mitigation.

39.4. Lessons learnt

The constraining effect of the Birds Directive as currently drafted is evident as it is sought to develop renewable energy infrastructure. This will also arise in relation to Carbon Farming. The impact of well designed, well mitigated windfarms cannot be aligned with the obligations under the Birds Directive to prohibit killing or disturbance of all wild birds. No building, in fact, can comply with this. The obligation arises because of the interaction of Article 1 and Article 5 of the Birds Directive as interpreted by the CJEU in the Swedish Logging and Finnish Wolves cases, for instance.

Similarly, where peatlands are regenerated their habitats will change, causing some birds to leave (they will be ‘disturbed’) and many others to arrive. Technically, this is a breach of the Birds Directive. Again, this illustrates tensions between climate mitigation measures and existing environmental protection laws that predate the era of required climate action.

39.5. Recommendation for action

EU Commission Guidance prepared by DG Clima (AGRI) and DG Enviro (ENVI) working together is required in order to inform Member States and prospective developers as to how these legal frameworks should be applied. Given the nature of Carbon Farming and the areas within which it can be most effectively deployed, this must encompass interplay with the Nature Restoration Law, the Natura 2000 network and wild birds in particular. How can projects be legitimately authorised in the absence of scientific certainty and complete data?

In conjunction, an update of the environmental protection directives to provide for climate mitigation should be advocated for. Adaptive management and pilot projects are an urgent

necessity for effective climate mitigation. Lessons should be learned from the approach in RED III where incomplete ‘fixes’ were inserted. The involvement of ENVI is crucial in this regard.

39.6. Recommendation for action

In conjunction with the development of interim EU Commission guidance, an update of the environmental protection directives to provide for climate mitigation should be advocated for and developed.

Adaptive management and pilot projects are an urgent necessity for effective climate mitigation. Lessons should be learned from the approach in RED III where incomplete ‘fixes’ were inserted. The involvement of ENVI is crucial in this regard to ensure that a full understanding of the environmental Directives is brought to any amendments made.

39.7. Lessons learnt

The scale of the voluntary carbon market (VCM) has been limited by registry design.

The VCM registries do not recognise ownership of credits but rather rely on deeds of representation and warranties to evidence title. Further, the VCM registries do not recognise security interests. The impact of these design decisions has been to limit institutional capital and project finance.

For the CRCF to scale, debt financiers and ‘forward’ buyers must be able to take, and enforce, security interests.

39.8. Recommendation for action

The EU’s report entitled “Scoping of the CRCF registry and minimum requirements for certification scheme registries” recommends the CRCF registry operate as a central repository rather than a fully operational registry. Future decisions on designing the CRCF registry should engage with the reasons for limited participation of institutional capital and project finance that have limited the VCM’s scale.

39.9. Recommendation for action

The Supervisory Body for the Paris Agreement Crediting Mechanism (PACM) is considering the implementation of a pledge system for Article 6.4 emission reductions within the PACM registry. This is an important example of designing a cross-jurisdictional registry.

The design of the CRCF registry should consider the analysis of the Supervisory Body in February, which considered the legal, technical and financial implications of providing functionality for the treatment of financial security interests in Article 6.4 emission reductions within the PACM registry. This involved analysing the approaches taken in the VCM (e.g. Verra) and compliance markets (e.g. New Zealand Emissions Trading Scheme).

Session 40: Why do we need direct measurement to secure Europe's Carbon Farming future?

Main organisers: AgriCarbon

Session description

In this engaging session, attendees discussed 'why direct measurement of soil carbon is essential to deliver Carbon Farming in Europe and how integration of different measurement approaches can optimise cost and confidence in carbon claims'

Issues

- Why direct measurement of soil carbon is essential to deliver Carbon Farming in Europe
- How integration of different measurement approaches can optimise cost and confidence in carbon claims'

Recommendations

40.1. Direct measurement at scale is feasible and cost-effective

The session clearly demonstrated that direct measurement of soil carbon stocks to depth has been done at scale and affordably throughout Europe. This, in effect, removes barriers to including direct measurement in soil carbon MRV to ensure carbon removal claims are real.

This capability has been made possible via recent financial investment and technological innovation, which have revolutionised soil sampling and laboratory analyses to make soil MRV affordable, rapid, and consistently high-quality. Thus, the often quoted barriers of poor quality, inconsistent soil data that are slow to produce have been removed.

40.2. A vast wealth of contemporary soil data is being generated

Various carbon-farming projects, both in the voluntary carbon market and in Scope 3 supply chains, produce substantial soil data. There is tremendous potential to harness these data sets to inform the EU's emerging carbon-removal certification framework (CRCF), enabling robust and farmer-relevant soil carbon MRV.

More research partnerships associated with CRCF are needed to continue developing accurate, affordable, and farmer-relevant soil carbon MRV.

40.3. Modelling alone risks greenwashing

The Regenerate Outcomes team's experiences illustrated the importance of having enough direct scale measurement to support reliable soil carbon changes modelling. Sufficient data is also required to demonstrate to farmers that their management practices result in real changes.

Sampling numbers (and hence costs) can be refined to reduce modelling uncertainty and support modelling predictions of soil carbon removals over time – a solely modelling-focused approach does not generate sufficient baseline or resampling direct measurement data to be confident that real (measurable) change has occurred. Therefore, a significant risk of greenwashing exists through over-reliance on modelling outcomes. Regenerate Outcomes works directly with farmers to deliver VCM and other benefit schemes to support the transition to regenerative/low-Carbon Farming.

40.4. Remote sensing is supportive but cannot replace ground truth

Remote sensing helps with qualitative assessments to support soil carbon MRV, e.g. in helping to validate claims using remote sensing tools. However, remote sensing tools are (as yet) unable to reliably predict absolute amounts or changes in soil carbon stocks for baselines or over time. Therefore, they are not reliable for use in baselining or resampling of soil carbon stocks.

Session 41: Setting the Gold Standard: Delivering shared value from reduced agricultural emissions

Main organiser: BASF

Session description

This session discussed the need and approach to develop a Gold Standard Verification Model.

Issues

- Creating a Gold Standard Model for monitoring, reporting, and verifying emission reductions
- Opportunities and challenges faced in implementing Carbon Farming projects at scale
- Identify potential areas of improvement in both implementation and certification.

Recommendations

No recommendations.

Posters

Harnessing the vast potential of RES for sustainable farming (HarvREST)

Authors: Stelios Dritsas, Laurène Lebelt, Ana Yovtcheva, Daniel Zimmer, Cecilia Burnfield

1. Introduction

The HarvREST project has been launched to address the need of enhancing the use of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) along with sustainable farming methods, aiming to help the agricultural and food industry reduce carbon emissions. The consortium of the projects consists of 17 partners from 8 countries.

2. Objective

The main objective of HarvREST is to improve the existing knowledge of options for reducing carbon emissions on farms, by maximising synergies between the integration of RES and sustainable agricultural practices.

3. Our Approach

Social engagement and Innovative Business Models

- Create multi-actor engagement strategies to foster synergies between the whole agri-food chain and energy sector.

Agricultural and environmental trade-offs

- Create a mitigation catalogue and a framework to monitor the performance of combined production (energy, food and feed).
- Methodology to assess soil quality and carbon/water footprints.

Renewable energy sources and smart energy systems

- Modeling the behavior of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and their interaction with other elements of the agro-energy system
- Forecasting algorithms and energy management systems

4. Main Outcomes

An Agricultural Virtual Power Plant (AVPP)

Capable of running diverse scenarios and farm configurations. The tool will determine the best operational procedures for a given RES solution.

A Business Model Catalogue

Containing relevant innovative business models, considering financial schemes and incentives while identifying risks.

A Decision Support System (DSS)

To make recommendations of the best RES integration solutions & operation procedures for optimized production based on data from AVPP.

Figure: Catalan Use Case agronomic field trials

PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe
TOPIC: HORIZON-DI-S-2023-CLIMATE-01-7
TYPE OF ACTION: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
PROJECT NUMBER: 101136904

Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

5. Mapping of RES integration in farms at EU level

As part of the HarvREST project, an analysis of the integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in European agriculture was conducted. This analysis maps best practices for farm decarbonization, assesses stakeholder needs and regulatory frameworks, and examines case studies in Italy, Spain, Denmark, and Norway. Key findings highlight the potential of agrivoltaics, biogas, and smart energy systems to reduce emissions while maintaining biodiversity and productivity. However, policy barriers and financial constraints remain significant challenges.

Successful RES adoption requires strategic planning, policy support, and active stakeholder engagement. Clear regulations, financial incentives, and multi-actor collaboration—including farmers, industry, and policymakers—are essential for scalable solutions. By addressing these challenges, RES can play a crucial role in sustainable agriculture and rural energy security across Europe.

6. Use Cases

	Italy	Denmark	Spain	Norway
Technologies	PV	Biogas	PV, Biogas, Storage, Electrolysers	PV, Thermal Storage, Batteries, Biogas, Hydro, Wind
Activity	Agro-Industrial, Farmers	Large scale biogas plant	Winery and dairy products	Livestock farming
Key Objective	Explore joint models for promoting RES in Agro-communities and along the food value chain	Enhance biogas planning tool for Danish farms, evaluating GHG emissions, nutrient balances, and leveraging big data.	Enhance the production management: 1. Digital management of a winery to optimise RES assets and the consideration of the impact of RES on crops. 2. Biogas production modelling from agro-residues	Development of an intelligent energy system for total GGE decarbonization

For more information visit : <https://www.harvrest.eu/>
[Linkedin.com/harvREST](https://www.linkedin.com/company/harvrest)
https://x.com/HarvREST_Eu

www.climate-kic.org
Corresponding Author: Stelios Dritsas
Email: stelios.dritsas@climate-kic.org

SUPPORTING THE TRANSITION TO CLIMATE-NEUTRAL AND CLIMATE-RESILIENT EUROPEAN FARMING

AUTHORS: Laurène Lebelt, Pernille Modvig, Daniel Zimmer, Cecilia Burnfield, Stelios Dritsas

Introduction

ClieNFarms is an Innovation Action project funded by the European Commission to support the European Green Deal. It aims to co-develop and scale up systemic, locally relevant solutions to foster climate-neutral and climate-resilient farms across Europe.

Objectives

The general goal of ClieNFarms is to co-develop and upscale systemic locally relevant solutions (organisational, financial, technical) to reach climate neutral and climate resilient sustainable farms across Europe, interactively integrating and improving existing solutions to achieve economically viable business models in farming systems by involving farmers, extension services, agri-food business, policy-makers, finance and citizens.

The Farming for Climate platform: Mobilizing the EU agricultural advisory community for Climate Smart Farming

- A response to multiple EU agricultural projects providing knowledge on climate change, mitigation, and adaptation.
- An initiative by Climate Farm Demo, Climate Smart Advisors, and ClieNFarms.
- An open-access platform for field stakeholders offering resources on Carbon Farming, including:
 - o Farming practices for climate adaptation and mitigation
 - o Climate and Carbon Assessment tools
 - o Advisory methods and tools
- A regularly updated platform, allowing users to contribute new or improved tools, practices, and methods.

Funding Scheme: Innovation Action (IA) • Topic: LC-GD-6-1-2020
Start date of project: 01 January 2022 • Duration: 48 months

INTERNATIONAL NETWORK OF FARMERS

The ClieNFarms scaling toolbox for climate-neutral farming
Solutions and tools for all stakeholders to support the adoption of climate-neutral farming at scale

 Policy Makers I want to understand ways to change policy so that it supports sustainable farming in my area/region	 Reformers, Champions, and Investors I want to mobilise, fund and support farmers in adopting carbon farming practices	 Private Companies I am looking for other companies to implement Nature-Based Solutions with us which deliver ecosystem services in our region
 Advisors and Farming Groups I want to scale sustainable farming practices through educating, training and building networks of farmers	 Farmers I want to adopt sustainable farming practices on my farm and am looking for other farmers and stakeholders to learn from and work with	 Farmers I want to adopt sustainable farming practices on my farm and am looking for solutions to test

ClieNFarms
Climate Neutral Farms

CONTACT US

Project Coordinator: Jacques-Eric Bergez
cliefarms@gmail.com

ClieNFarms synergies: Laurène Lebelt
laurene.lebelt@climate-kic.org

www.cliefarms.eu

www.climate-kic.org
Corresponding Author: Laurène Lebelt
Email: laurene.lebelt@climate-kic.org

Irish Deep Demonstration Project Flagship 3. Promote circular bioeconomy models in regions and multiple value chains

Denyse Julien, Climate-KIC

Introduction

To develop sustainable, circular and regenerative bioeconomy collaborative models and multi-sectoral value chains in Ireland, that puts rural and coastal areas, communities, regions and cities at the heart of the transition.

To support multiple objectives including:

- Reaching Ireland's agri-emissions reduction targets
- Managing natural resources sustainably particularly biodiversity and water quality
- Strengthening competitiveness through biobased industrial modernisation
- Reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources; and support food and nutrition security.

What is the Bioeconomy

The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles.

It includes and interlinks:

- land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide;
- all primary production sectors that use and produce biological resources (agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture);
- and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy and services.

(EU Bioeconomy Strategy 2018)

Flagship 3 Partnership model

Innovative coordination and support approach, building on ongoing initiatives and research to accelerate and steer circular bioeconomy action on the ground.

Irish Bioeconomy Action Plan

- 33 actions across seven pillars
- Detailed steps for delivery and have an associated timeframe for implementation as well as the government departments, their agencies, and organisation(s) responsible.
- Increasing awareness and understanding of the bioeconomy more broadly.
- Enhanced policy coordination and investment and the greater integration of the bioeconomy within sectoral policies right across Government.
- Moving biobased innovation and solutions from research to sustainable and circular industrial production with accelerated pace.
- Support greater investment in the bioeconomy.

The Conceptual Framework

- **Concept 1:** Biobased products including aiding soil regeneration through the conversion of organic waste into biochar and biobased fertilisers
 - This project focuses on addressing the climate policy need to identify unallocated emission reduction savings as identified in the Climate Action Plan 2024. Biochar was specifically identified as an option.
- **Concept 2:** Multi-value chain cooperation and cooperative agri-bioeconomy development and regional biorefineries feasibility and priming to optimally convert biomass into high-value biobased products
 - This project focuses on the valorisation of biomass flows working in collaboration with the cooperatives and feedstock providers to drive value and opportunities into the local economy.
 - Additionally, to support the ecosystem related to Bioeconomy and Biobased products linked to Farming, Forestry or Food.
- **Concept 3:** Regional & Local Authority bioeconomy governance and innovation development including the development of Urban, Regional and Local Decarbonisation Zone Bioeconomy Living Labs
 - This project is looking to develop a Governance Blueprint drawing on work done by the Robin project and potentially the Fraunhofer Institute and to test the approaches through the implementation of pilots across different Local Authorities/Regional Assemblies.

An Roinn Talmhaíochta,
Bia agus Mara
Department of Agriculture,
Food and the Marine

Deep Demonstration
Sustainable food systems in Ireland

DECARBONISING SLOVENIA

The Deep Demonstration of a Circular, Regenerative and Low-Carbon Economy

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition to a circular, regenerative, sustainable economy is no longer a choice, but a condition for successfully resolving the climate crisis.

Slovenia, along with other EU Member States, needs to significantly step up its efforts to meet the goal of net zero emissions by mid-century. This requires crucial structural, transformational and exponential changes, both rapidly and on multiple fronts simultaneously.

In response to this urgent need, the Slovenian government has been working with Climate KIC on the Deep Demonstration in Slovenia to develop pathways for a more radical transition to climate neutrality through a circular, regenerative and low-carbon economy, using a systems innovation approach.

This partnership aims to catalyse rapid decarbonisation and drive climate action and resilience through circular economy approaches, while having a prosperous society by applying the Deep Demonstration method, which is a tool for systemic change in complex landscapes

Map of Slovenia

4. TRANSFORMATION AREAS

POLICY

Enable policy innovation and experimentation through the establishment of a Policy Lab, including its structure and processes, to pilot targeted experiments in the selected value chains in collaboration with the Ministry of Public Administration.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Enable the Slovenian start-up and enterprise community to develop a strong network of partners and climate-positive entrepreneurs. This is being done through a series of ecosystem development activities in each value chain in cooperation with the Ministry of Economy, Tourism and Sport, the Slovenian Enterprise Fund and SPIRIT Slovenia Business Development Agency.

EDUCATION AND SCIENCE

Support the transformation of the education system by integrating the circular economy dimension at both levels - curriculum and organisational - to co-design pilot actions with the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Education, as well as local universities and research institutions.

FINANCE

Develop a funding strategy and capital and investment plan for the 'Circular Economy' portfolio by mapping available private and public funding opportunities and matching them with emerging innovation actions, identifying interlinks and potential gaps and opportunities to combine different funding instruments and mechanisms.

CAPABILITY DEVELOPMENT

Develop deeper systems thinking capabilities across a spectrum of organisations, stakeholders and communities and further enhance knowledge and skills in practicing systems innovation beyond the Deep Demonstration programme.

2. OBJECTIVES

- Establish a common reference framework for the 'Circular Economy' portfolio in Slovenia, building on initiatives already underway to make informed and coherent decisions on ongoing efforts, new initiatives and innovation opportunities
- Support the decarbonisation of key value chains of the Slovenian economy (built environment, mobility, food, critical raw materials).
- Spark innovation and the development of new systemic solutions in entrepreneurship, education, policy and finance.
- Enable cross-sectoral collaboration to overcome organisational silos and identify interlinked priority areas in public administration and beyond including more systemic engagement of a wider range of stakeholders.
- Empower local stakeholders through practical skills development and application of systems thinking tools to support decision making

3. KEY VALUE CHAINS

BUILT ENVIRONMENT

FOOD & AGRICULTURE

MOBILITY

CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS

4. PORTFOLIO APPROACH

A portfolio approach involves the development and dynamic management of a collection of projects, initiatives or innovation actions in a coordinated and holistic way to achieve a more significant and transformative impact on the whole system and across the four value chains

Example of visualisation for the Built environment portfolio

Web page:

<https://www.climate-kic.org/programmes/place-based-transformations/circular-slovenia/>

Contact us at:

deepdemonstrationslovenia@climate-kic.org

Green Horizons Network

Empowering farmers in transition

Authors: Saskia Keesstra, Pernille Modvig, Thanh-Tam Le, Laurene Lebelt, Stelios Dritsas, Saskia Visser

THE NETWORK

Agriculture is vital for economies, food security, and sustainability, yet farmers face challenges like limited information, collaboration, and tools. To address this, we have started a hub for knowledge sharing, capacity building, and collaboration between ambitious farmers.

OBJECTIVES

- Facilitate knowledge exchange among farmers and agricultural experts.
- Provide access to events, webinars, and farm-specific groups.
- Support farmers with tools and methods that enhance productivity and sustainability.
- Provide a training portfolio on sustainability transitions

A forum for collaboration

The GreenHorizons platform offers Discussion forums and Q&A boards to address queries and share solutions as well as a "Sparring Network" to match farmers with mentors, advisors, or peers for one-on-one guidance.

Events, trainings and Webinars

The network offers virtual and physical events, including training sessions, conferences, and farm tours.

On the platform you will find live and recorded webinars on topics ranging from crop management to financial planning.

Knowledge Hub

The GreenHorizons network gives access to a centralized repository for resources such as articles, videos, and guides on best practices, modern farming techniques, and market trends.

You will get access to the toolbox of methods, solutions and schemes to introduce and scale carbon farming practices and regularly updated content curated by experts and peer contributors.

Farm-Specific Subgroups

The network offers dedicated space for farmers with similar interests or challenges to connect and share insights. These subgroups could be based on crop types, geographic regions, or specific themes like organic farming or irrigation methods.

F1	F2	F1, F2, F3
3 RIS farmer groups	8 farmer groups across Europe	All individual farmers across Europe

Green Horizons Network:
Empowering farmers in transition

www.Climate-kic.org
Corresponding author:
Email: saskia.keesstra@climate-kic.org

In partnership with:

An Roinn Talmhaíochta,
Bia agus Mara
Department of Agriculture,
Food and the Marine

Deep Demonstration partnership of climate-resilient food systems in Ireland

THE DEEP DEMONSTRATION

OBJECTIVES

The Deep Demonstration partnership between Climate KIC and Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine is supporting the entire Irish land and agri-food value chain to identify and implement sustainable practices, so that farmers and rural communities can thrive and industries can transition to sustainable business models, all while meeting challenging climate targets.

EMISSIONS REDUCTION
BY 2030

25%

CLIMATE NEUTRALITY
BY

2050

APPROACH

- **Demand-led:** co-designing interventions with key stakeholders.
- Developing and implementing a **portfolio** of large-scale **connected interventions** in the land and agri-food system.
- Embedding rapid **'learning by doing'** to provide intelligence which will enable government and industry to make informed decisions about choices to meet climate goals.

METHODOLOGY

OUR DEEP DEMONSTRATIONS

OUR IMPACT IN IRELAND

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

- 27 core partners
- 1,000+ value chains actors involved
- 30+ strategic workshops
- 127 participants to systems innovation trainings

INSIGHTS

- Map of the Irish land and agri-food system
- 7 high-potential innovation areas
- Policy measures from 12 countries
- Key funding and financing flows
- Analysis of skills needs
- 3 key themes for narrative shift
- Cross-lessons from Slovenia and Spain

Download our reports

7 FLAGSHIP AREAS

of which 4 have been prioritised, underpinned by 275+ project ideas

- FLAGSHIP 1 | Vision 2050: re-imagine Ireland's land and agri-food system | ACTIVE
- FLAGSHIP 2 | Foster innovation and investment in new value chains to diversify the sector
- FLAGSHIP 3 | Promote circular bioeconomy models in regions and multiple value chains | ACTIVE
- FLAGSHIP 4 | Diversify incomes through a carbon farming and nature credit framework | ACTIVE
- FLAGSHIP 5 | Produce and certify climate-neutral beef
- FLAGSHIP 6 | Accelerate emission reduction and sustainability in dairy farms | ACTIVE
- FLAGSHIP 7 | Grow and diversify the tillage sector

DEVELOPING CARBON FARMING PRINCIPLES FOR IRELAND

OBJECTIVE

To support and enable the adoption and scaling of management practices within primary production that will result in Ireland achieving its climate, biodiversity and water quality targets by the end of 2030.

INSIGHTS

Significant stakeholder engagement by the National Carbon Farming Working Group, chaired by DAFM and Climate KIC

- Nation-wide public consultation survey gathering around 400 responses
- Ongoing series of bilateral engagements and workshops with almost 200 individuals

Respondents indicated they want a long-term scheme:

What should be the lifetime funding required for an initiative?

CORE CARBON PRINCIPLES

GOVERNANCE

- 1 Effective governance
- 2 Tracking
- 3 Transparency
- 4 Independent verification

EMISSIONS IMPACT

- 5 Additionality
- 6 Permanence
- 7 Quantification of outcomes
- 8 No double counting

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

- 9 Benefits and safeguards
- 10 Contribution to 2050 goals

SPECIFIC TO IRELAND

- 11 Just transition
- 12 Learning by doing

VISIT OUR WEBSITE FOR MORE INFORMATION
www.climate-kic.org/SustainableFoodIreland

SIGN UP TO OUR NEWSLETTER

Renewable horticultural substrates with compost and biochar as source of external organic matter and the link with soil friendly practices

Bart Vandecasteele^{1,*}, Jarinda Viaene¹, Rianne Visser², Amine Lataf³, Ann Cuypers³, Dries Vandamme³

¹Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), 9820 Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium, ²ECN Part of TNO, Petten 1755 ZG, The Netherlands,

³Hasselt University, Centre for Environmental Sciences (CMK), 3590 Diepenbeek, Belgium

* Presenting author: bart.vandecasteele@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Introduction Future use of C-rich external organic matter for a variety of applications including C storage in soil is expected to increase, potentially resulting in a shortage of these sources of exogenous organic matter. Using C-rich materials in a cascade is one strategy to avoid competition for these types of biomass. Green composts and wood-based biochars are examples of materials that are in most cases directly applied in the soil but that also can be used as bulk replacement for peat in horticultural substrates.

Materials and methods. Two scenarios on the use of compost or biochar in a cascade are studied: (1) In the scenario 'Green compost use in cascade' we compared the value of green composts directly used as organic soil improver versus the value as soil improver of spent horticultural substrates (i.e., growing media) with or without green compost as such, or further processed into compost.

In the scenario 'Biomass use in cascade for producing biochar' we compared the value of wood-based biochars as organic soil improver versus the value of biochars produced from spent horticultural substrates with or without green compost or biochars based on bark or straw-like fibers. The biochars produced from spent horticultural substrates represent the case of materials used in cascade, while for the other biochar types the feedstocks were directly converted into biochar.

		Green compost	Peat-based spent growing media	spent growing media with green compost	Composted Spent growing media
# Samples		16	19	15	12
Organic C	g /kg dry matter	242 a	445 c	354 b	354 b
Inorganic C	g /kg dry matter	2.3 c	0.5 a	1.1 b	0.9 b
CO ₂ release	mmol CO ₂ /kg C/h	7 b	1 a	2 a	2 a
OUR	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	6 b	2 a	2 a	2 a
C/P ratio	-	126	542 b	231 a	161 a
total CEC	cmolc/kg dry matter	41 a	97 c	63 b	73 b

Fig. 1. Comparison of 2 scenarios and **Table 1.** Characteristics for green composts, spent growing media with peat or green compost and composted spent growing media. Average values are shown. Different letters indicate the significant differences as found by one-way ANOVA and Scheffé's post-hoc test.

Fig. 2. Comparison of 2 scenarios and **Table 2.** Characteristics for biochars produced from five different feedstocks. Average values are shown. Different letters indicate the significant differences as found by one-way ANOVA and Scheffé's post-hoc test (CEC: cation exchange capacity).

		Wood-based biochar	Bark biochar	Biochar from straw-like fibers	Biochar from peat-based growing media	Biochar from growing media with green compost
# Samples		11	4	6	7	8
Organic C	g /kg dry matter	803 b	790 b	793 b	686 b	284 a
Inorganic C	g /kg dry matter	1.0 ab	0.5 a	1.2 ab	3.3 b	3.3 b
OUR	mmol O ₂ /kg OM/h	1 a	1 a	1 a	2 a	8 b
C/P ratio	-	616 cd	715 d	392 bc	279 b	81 a
total CEC	cmolc/kg dry matter	25	19	33	30	29

Results. Using green compost in cascade did not negatively affect the quality of the end products and sometimes resulted in better characteristics in terms of quality as organic soil improver (Table 1). The organic C content of the green compost was significantly lower than for the other three material groups. Green composts have a lower biological stability than the other three groups (higher values for CO₂ release rate and OUR). Using spent growing media in cascade did affect the quality of the biochar and resulted in other characteristics in terms of quality as organic soil improver than for the wood-based biochars (Table 2). The organic C content of the biochars based on spent growing media with green compost was significantly lower and the inorganic C content significantly higher than for the other types of biochar.

Discussion. Exogenous organic matter from spent growing media with green compost may result in materials with a higher added value as soil improver and source of stable C than pure green compost. Biochars produced from spent growing media have clearly different chemical characteristics than wood-based biochars, including a higher acid-buffering capacity due to the higher inorganic C content.

This research was executed within the **EJP SOIL BioCASH project**. EJP SOIL (Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862695

Reference: Vandecasteele, B., Similon, L., Moelants, J., Hofkens, M., Melis, P., & Visser, R. (2024) End-of-life stage of renewable growing media with biochar versus spent peat or mineral wool. Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-023-10315-8>

Flanders
is agriculture and fisheries

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Carbon Action MRV: Agricultural Fields' Carbon Measurement, Reporting, and Verification System

Jari Liski, Julius Vira, Olli Nevalainen and Layla Höckerstedt, Finnish Meteorological Institute

Why

- Companies and policymakers need a simple and reliable method to assess the carbon balance of agricultural fields.
- Accurate carbon assessments are essential for sustainability strategies, greenhouse gas inventories, and developing new climate and agricultural policies.
- Carbon Action, a regenerative farming initiative, has developed a carbon monitoring system to support this progress.

Our system

- Carbon Action MRV is a scalable, largely automated system to monitor agricultural fields' carbon balance (Fig. 1).
- It links satellite-based plant growth estimates with soil carbon calculations using the Yasso model.
- The system is designed for large-scale applications, analyzing hundreds or thousands of fields.

Specifications

- Open science: Transparent, fully documented, supports third-party verification
- Designed for international use: Relies on EU Copernicus Programme's satellite data, accessed via the Finnish Meteorological Institute's Arctic Space Center
- Scientific validation: Uses the Yasso soil model, which is widely used in Earth system modeling and national greenhouse gas inventories, meeting the UNFCCC and IPCC standards

How it works

Biomass

- Daily plant growth and photosynthesis are derived from satellite chlorophyll data and weather sunlight data (Fig. 2).
- These estimations are calibrated using eddy covariance stations, which continuously measure carbon dioxide fluxes between agricultural fields and the atmosphere (Figs. 3 and 4).
- Biomass is calculated daily from accumulated photosynthesis production.
- Carbon input to soil is calculated annually from the accumulated biomass, harvested yield, and organic fertilizer additions.

Soil carbon

- Soil carbon stocks and annual changes are tracked using the Yasso model, which refines the estimates with soil carbon measurements.
- The Yasso model has been developed from global soil carbon and litter decomposition datasets and has been tested extensively in diverse ecosystems (Figs. 5 and 6).

IT system

- The system is integrated into the Finnish Meteorological Institute's IT framework, supporting large-scale applications, like weather services.

Field Observatory

- The system is linked to the Field Observatory, an online platform providing real-time data from study sites (Fig. 7).

Way forward

- Carbon Action is continuously developing the MRV system by expanding research and testing applications in international and national projects (Fig. 8).
- Industry pilots: Collaborating with food companies to test supply chain usability.
- Policy support: Assisting in national greenhouse gas inventory development and result-based farmer subsidy schemes.
- The Carbon Action MRV system offers a science-based carbon estimation service for national and international stakeholders.

Fig. 1. Carbon Action MRV system for monitoring the carbon balance of agricultural fields.

Fig. 2. Carbon Action MRV system estimates biomass growth using Sentinel-2 satellite chlorophyll data and weather-based sunlight (photosynthetically active radiation, PAR) data, simulates soil carbon with the Yasso model, and incorporates farm data on harvested yield and organic inputs.

Fig. 3. Biomass calculation steps: (1) Daily photosynthesis is estimated from Sentinel-2 satellite chlorophyll index and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) using an equation developed at eddy covariance CO₂ flux measurement sites. (2) Missing satellite data are interpolated using Gaussian Process regression. (3) Photosynthesis is estimated for each day based on the interpolated data (Vira et al. 2025)

Fig. 4. Validation of photosynthesis and biomass estimates: (1) Photosynthesis estimates have a root mean squared error (RMSE) of 10–15% of the measured mean per day (a), month (b), or year (c). (2) Accumulated photosynthesis correlates with biomass measurements in annual crop and forage grass fields (Vira et al. 2025).

Fig. 5. The Yasso soil model was developed using approximately 18,000 soil carbon and litter decomposition measurements worldwide (www.fmi.fi/en/yasso).

Fig. 6. The Yasso model accurately estimates soil carbon development in agricultural fields when carbon input is reliably known. This example shows a validity test using data from Uppsala, Sweden (1956–1991) (Karhu et al. 2012).

Fig. 7. Field Observatory data showing the CO₂ flux of a renewing forage grass field in Quidja, Southern Finland (May–June 2024). During the day, carbon uptake occurs as photosynthesis exceeds respiration, while at night, carbon emissions result from respiration in the absence of photosynthesis. The measurement is sensitive to farming practices; for example, harvesting of nurse crop rye on June 15 temporarily reduced carbon uptake.

Fig. 8. Application of the Carbon Action MRV system to a carbon farming experiment on an ordinary farm. Cover crops increased soil carbon input by approximately 0.5 tons per hectare in September and October compared to the no-cover-control, representing about 10% of the annual input.

Links and references

www.bsag.fi/en/carbon-action-en/, www.fieldobservatory.org, www.fmi.fi/en/yasso
Vira et al. 2025. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.173712580.08052217/v1>
Nevalainen et al. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-11-93-2022>
Karhu et al. 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2012.06.007>
Video of MRV <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s47KImGmRg>

Contact: Finnish Meteorological Institute's Chief Scientist jari.liski@fmi.fi

CARBON ACTION

FROM PROMOTING CARBON FARMING TO SYSTEMIC CHANGE IN THE FOOD SYSTEM

The Carbon Action collaboration develops practical regenerative farming methods while studying carbon sequestration. We identify and promote farming practices that benefit farmers, the climate, biodiversity, and the Baltic Sea.

2000
following the work through the Carbon Action Club and farmer network in Finnish and Swedish.

LEAD OF THE CAP DIALOGUE INITIATIVE IN FINLAND
We actively act on the next Common Agricultural Policy. The initiative creates constructive dialogue for impactful agricultural policy.

MONITORING, REPORTING AND VERIFICATION SYSTEM
FMI is developing an MRV system to monitor soil organic carbon changes from parcel to national scales, in accordance with the IPCC Tier 3 method. It serves to:

- the Carbon Removal and Certification Framework
- the national greenhouse gas inventory
- the life-cycle assessments

video about MRV

Altogether 55 projects

over 600 trained farmers through corporate partners

FARMERS
100 pilot farms

BUSINESS

14 corporate partners

REGENERATIVE FARMING INCORPORATED IN THE COMPANY OPERATIONS

- training their staff and contract farmers
- incorporating regenerative criteria into their procurement criteria
- developing regenerative products for the market.

REGENERATIVE FARMING CRITERIA FOR FINLAND

Developed together with stakeholders

CRASH COURSE IN REGENERATIVE FARMING FI-SE-EN

A free and easy-to-use online course provides science-based knowledge on regenerative farming in an approachable format. It is aimed mainly at food system companies and offers practical tools for transitioning toward regenerative food production. The online course is based on Carbon Action research and is in use in Häme University of Applied Sciences

36 trained farmer advisors

SCIENCE
100 researchers

Long-term collaboration ensures continuation across projects

WE ARE SEEING THAT ...

Improving soil health increases resilience, and thus yield reliability in dry and wet conditions.

Healthy soil needs less inputs, such as fertilisers and pesticides.

Mixed cropping with just 2–3 plant species increases the carbon input to the soil.

Summary strategy: Maximise photosynthesis, maximise microbial activity in the soil, and minimise the disturbance of soil functions.

BSAG Baltic Sea Action Group
Coordinates the platform
Esa Vainio, Pieta Jarva, Anne Noro Ing, Julia Kajala, Kari Granholm
www.bsag.fi/en/carbon-action-en/

CARBON ACTION
Layla Höckerstedt
Carbon Action co-founder, Chair

ILMATIETIKEN LAITOS
METEOROLOGISKA INSTITUTET
FINNISH METEOROLOGICAL INSTITUTE
Saara Kankkonrinta, Jari Liski
Oversees the research collaboration

Design: nina.aittinen@nuriaatmr.com

Comparative carbon stock quantification in diverse production systems: Paving the way for sustainable agriculture

*Bhim Bahadur Ghaley (bbg@plen.ku.dk); Albert Miquel Colom Bauza (amcb@plen.ku.dk) & Vaibhav Pradip Chaudhary (ypc@plen.ku.dk)

Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences, UCPH, Højbakkegård Alle 30, Taastrup, Denmark. *Corresponding author.

Introduction: The necessity to mitigate climate change has highlighted the role of agriculture in carbon sequestration in the soil and biomass. However, there is a clear knowledge gap in quantification of total carbon stocks (TCS) in production systems under diverse management regimes and pedo-climatic zones. Our study aim to address this knowledge gap by contributing to quantification of TCS in diverse production systems in Denmark.

Objective: To quantify and compare the TCS between organic agroforestry system (AF), conventional winter wheat (CWW) and tree monoculture (TMC) in Denmark.

Materials & Methods

The carbon stocks were measured in 4 production systems. AF trees and AF alley in AF system, CWW and TMC. AF system consists of crop alleys of 50, 100, 150 and 200 m wide (Figure 1) with tree belts (AF trees) consisting of short rotation woody crops (SRWC) and detail information of AF system is provided in Ghaley and Porter (2014). Within AF, AF alley consisted of spring barley in 200 m crop alley and AF trees consisted of SWRC. TMC consists of *Salix* spp. monoculture.

Figure 1. Aerial view of AF system in Denmark.

The TCS consists of different carbon pools depending on the production system of interest. In TMC and AF trees, TCS consist of above- and belowground biomass, litter layer, and soil organic carbon stock (SOC). In AF alley and CWW, the TCS consists of SOC, root biomass carbon and carbon in ABG biomass but we did not include ABG biomass and root biomass because the leftover crop residues after harvesting and the root biomass is incorporated into the soil during ploughing and hence SOC includes leftover crop residues and root biomass.

Determination of carbon pools

Allometric equations Ghaley and Porter (2014) were used to estimate the ABG of the short rotation woody crops (SRWC). The belowground tree biomass (root system) was estimated using a Root-To-Shoot (RTS) ratio of 0.31, as recommended by the IPCC (2003) guidelines for temperate broadleaf species. The conversion of above- and below-ground dry biomass to C content was done as per IPCC (2006a) for temperate broadleaf species with 48% of the tree biomass considered as C. The litter layer was sampled and oven dried at 80°C and the C content was estimated based on its dry weight. C fraction of 0.37 is considered as per the IPCC (2006b) guidelines for litter and dead organic matter. The ABG biomass and C stock in the TMC was estimated with the Woodland Carbon Calculator (WCC 2024). SOC content was measured on fresh soil samples taken from 0-30 cm and SOC was analysed using Agrocates Soil scanner.

We are grateful for the financial support provided by REFOREST project funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number [101060635]. This funding contribution was instrumental in facilitating our data collection and analysis for abstract preparation. The views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Results

- TMC recorded the highest TCS with 243 t/ha, followed by SRWC (122 t/ha), AF alley (93.5 t/ha), and the CWW (63.6 t/ha).
- High TCS in TMC is due to high carbon pools in aboveground biomass (99.8 t C/ha), roots (30.9 t C/ha) and litter layer (5.8 t C/ha).
- Across the production systems, SOC constituted the highest carbon component viz. 63.6 t C/ha (CWW), 93.5 t C/ha (crop alley), 103.9 t/ha (SRWC), and 106.9 t/ha (TMC).
- AF systems recorded higher TCS in soil and above-below ground biomass as described by Ivezić et al., 2022 and Lorenz and Lal, 2014.

Figure 2. Carbon stocks in different components of agroforestry (AF trees and AF alley), conventional winter wheat (CWW) and tree monoculture (TMC). Where, ABG biomass: aboveground biomass; BLG biomass: belowground biomass; SOC stock: soil organic carbon

Conclusions

- The study provided robust evidence that multifunctional agroforestry systems can store higher quantity of carbon while producing food, fodder and bioenergy.
- The combination of methods, adopted in this study can be applied in other pedo-climatic zones, production systems and management regimes for quantification of TCS for informed decision-making to monitor and reward farmers in adopting carbon farming practices.
- By quantifying TCS, we can provide evidence of sustainable agricultural benefits that enhance carbon storage and mitigate climate change.

References

- Ghaley, Bhim Bahadur, and John Roy Porter. 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.02.009>
- IPCC. 2003. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/GPG_LULUCF_FULLLEN.pdf
- IPCC. 2006a. <https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/vol4.html>
- IPCC. 2006b. <https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/vol4.html>
- Ivezić, V., Lorenz, K., Lal, R., 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031296>
- Lorenz, K., Lal, R., 2014. <https://hal.science/hal-01234833v1>
- WCC. 2024. <https://www.stoodlandcarboncode.org.uk/standard-and-guidance/3-carbon-sequestration/3-3-project-carbon-sequestration>

Harnessing soil organic carbon: unlocking benefits for crop productivity and climate resilience with agroforestry systems

Albert M. Colom Bauza (amcb@plen.ku.dk), Vaibhav Pradip Chaudhary (ypc@plen.ku.dk), Bhim Bahadur Ghaley (bbg@plen.ku.dk)

Keywords: organic agroforestry, soil organic carbon, crop yield, spring barley, distance effects

INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a critical component of soil health and plays a pivotal role in the global carbon cycle. SOC is derived from decomposed plant and non-plant residues, and its presence improves soil physical, chemical and biological properties for better soil health. SOC acts as a significant carbon sink, helping to mitigate climate change by sequestering atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂). Understanding the dynamics of SOC is essential for developing sustainable agricultural practices that not only improve crop productivity but also contribute to climate resilience.

The study objective was to investigate SOC contents and evaluate its benefits on alley crop yields in a 30-year-old organic agroforestry system in Taastrup, Denmark.

Figure 1. The SRWC agroforestry system (right) is located in the east of Denmark (left).

STUDY SITE AND METHODOLOGY

The system consists of a 200 m-wide crop alley with short-rotation woody crop (SRWC) belts of willow, hazelnut and alder. The crop rotation includes spring oat, spring barley, winter wheat and a 2-year grass-clover ley, with crop residues and grass cuttings left on the field. The SRWC are coppiced every 4 years and reach an approximated height of 7 meters at the end of the rotation. Soil samples and spring barley crop cuts were taken at 8 different distances from the tree belts up to 100 m, the alley middle. The crop biomass was threshed, and the grain moisture content standardised to 14%. The soil samples were analysed with an AgroCares near-infrared scanner for soil organic matter and converted to SOC assuming a 58% carbon fraction.

The data was analysed using linear mixed effects models, with the log-transformed distance as the independent variable and a random intercept per replication.

Figure 2. Aerial overview of the alley-cropping agroforestry system. The samples were taken at 8 distances from the trees in three replications.

REFERENCES

- Van Vooren Laura et al. 2017. Ecosystem service delivery of agri-environment measures: A synthesis for hedgerows and grass strips on arable land. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagec.2017.04.015>
 Pardon et al. 2017. Trees increase soil organic carbon and nutrient availability in temperate agroforestry systems. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagec.2017.06.018>
 Cardinalael et al. 2017. Increased soil organic carbon stocks under agroforestry: A survey of six different sites in France. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagec.2016.12.011>
 Oldfield et al. 2019. Global meta-analysis of the relationship between soil organic matter and crop yields <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-5-15-2019>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SOC% was lowest near the tree belt (1.6%±0.03) and significantly increased (p<0.05), further into the alley up to 2.05%±0.15. Grain yields followed a similar trend (p<0.05), from 1666.9±353.3 to 3319.2±291.8 kg/ha. This indicated a positive correlation between the SOC content and the crop yield, with lower SOC associated to lower crop yield and vice versa.

Tree resource competition on crop yields is well documented in temperate agroforestry systems (Van Vooren Laura et al. 2017). Our study finds that these interactions drive SOC dynamics in long-term SRWC silvoarable systems:

- Trees of limited size do not significantly affect SOC on adjacent crop areas (Pardon et al. 2017).
- Tree leaf fall and root decay contributions to SOC in the vicinity of tree belts cannot compensate for the lower crop residue input (Cardinael et al. 2017).
- Increasing SOC with distance due to decaying tree-crop interactions further promotes larger amounts of crop organic inputs due to SOC positive effects on plant growth (Oldfield et al. 2019).

Figure 3. Yield and SOC evolution throughout the crop alley with distance from the SRWC belt, with estimated confidence intervals (grey) and the field observations (red).

CONCLUSIONS

The data demonstrated that yields benefit of higher SOC content, which can be attributed to better nutrient availability, soil moisture content and pH regulation. Improving SOC further mitigates climate change by actively sequestering and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. This study demonstrated the benefits of SOC and can be replicated in other areas to provide robust evidence of agroforestry for informed decision-making.

We are grateful for the financial support provided by REFOREST project funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number [101060635]. This funding contribution was instrumental in facilitating our data collection and analysis for abstract preparation. The views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Towards an Harmonised Framework for Soil Carbon Certification & Cost-efficient Monitoring, Reporting & Verification System

A Brussels-based Event With a Global Agenda

In September 2024, the Belgian capital hosted a **policy workshop on international carbon certification schemes**, organised by the ORCaSa project within the International Soil Carbon Research Consortium.

With speakers from Europe, the United States, Australia and the Pacific, the idea was to **open a dialogue** between international experts, researchers and regional experts on the monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) of changes in soil carbon stocks, **the current state and future directions** of soil carbon certification schemes.

Applications Contexts

Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs)

Agricultural policies (e.g. the CAP)

Carbon market
insetting

Carbon market
offsetting

Why a cookbook on MRV?

- 1 To access a list of the components of the MRV frameworks and the different contexts in which they are applied.
- 2 To explore different methodologies analysed for monitoring and verifying changes in SOC stocks, including some considerations on their respective limitations, advantages and disadvantages, implementation costs, building blocks, depending on the contexts in which MRV systems are implemented.
- 3 To provide guidance to entities (e.g. verifiers and auditors of carbon credits, researchers, institutes in charge of national GHG inventories, MRV developers) on the selection of appropriate methodologies for monitoring and verifying SOC stock changes depending on the MRV purposes (e.g. NDCs, voluntary carbon market, agricultural incentives) and their local context.
- 4 To assess an harmonised methodological framework for MRV of changes in SOC stocks on arable land, taking into account different building blocks (e.g. data, models) and contexts of the MRV framework (NDCs, voluntary carbon market...) and methodologies for monitoring SOC stock changes (e.g. measure-remeasure of SOC stocks, modeling).
- 5 To help entities to build, adapt, improve monitoring and verification tools or building blocks of MRV tools if current implementations are not satisfactory for their local context).

Driving Forward Soil Carbon MRV

Sustainable soil management in Parmigiano Reggiano cheese area

Arianna Pignagnoli¹, Isacco Rossi¹, Mirco Garuti¹, Alessandro Zatta^{1*}

¹ Centro Ricerche Produzioni Animali - CRPA Soc. Cons. p. A. V.le Timavo 43/2 42121 Reggio Emilia, Italy

*Corresponding author: a.zatta@crpa.it

Introduction

The European Union aims to achieve carbon neutrality before 2050 by reducing emissions and introducing climate-friendly practices to enhance carbon sequestration and storage. European agriculture impacts for a small contribution to total GHG emissions (10%), but the livestock sector accounts for 70%. The reduction of its impact by sustainable practices is essential to achieve the targets. In this context, the Zoocarbon project can contribute by demonstrating how to reduce the impact of milk production for Parmigiano Reggiano cheese through conservation agriculture practices and the valorisation of livestock effluents for renewable energy production.

Area of the Parmigiano Reggiano cheese. Italy

Methodology

Seven dairy farms for Parmigiano Reggiano cheese production with biogas plant are selected to apply agronomic practices such as the use of cover crops, permanent meadows, minimum and/or no tillage practices, optimisation of manure and digestate spreading.

Each dairy farm applies specific agronomic practices, suitable for its forage system.

Expected results

The project aims to produce **BEST PRACTICE GUIDANCE** for mitigating the environmental impact of dairy farms for Parmigiano Reggiano cheese production.

Models and geo-satellite tools

The project will **MONITOR THE SOIL ORGANIC CARBON (SOC) DYNAMICS**, by analysis of soil samples and predict SOC evolution using new and existing models and tools.

LCA – Life Cycle Assessment

The results from monitoring and modelling of soil carbon dynamics will be integrated with livestock and bioenergy production into the **ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF THE PROJECT'S PARTNER FARMS AND CARBON FOOTPRINT OF MILK.**

MANAGING DOUBLE COUNTING RISKS IN AGRICULTURAL VALUE CHAINS

LEARNING FROM A BUSINESS CASE, FOR THE CRCF

Authors JUBERA Romane, LANCKRIET Edouard

Affiliations AGROSOLUTIONS

BUSINESS CASE: HOW TO ACCOUNT FOR AND ALLOCATE EMISSION REDUCTIONS AND CARBON REMOVALS AMONG CROPS AND INDUSTRIES WITHIN A CROP ROTATION?

From a parcel level approach to a systemic approach on the whole rotation **financed by the malt industry**

WHAT CAN BE DONE ACCORDING TO EXISTING RULES?

- ❖ When several crops are cultivated (crop rotation) and bought by different buyers, how to properly allocate mitigation outcomes and especially carbon removals between crops/industries ?
- ❖ How to stack different financing mechanisms (grain premium, carbon credits, public subsidies) related to the claims arising from the allocation work ?
- ❖ How to claim, report and communicate climate benefits from interventions, respecting international standards ?

KEY TAKEAWAY AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE CRCF

How the CRCF can help accelerate this matter?

- ❖ Propose a unified rule to define, within a crop rotation, what falls within vs outside the scope 3 perimeter.
- ❖ Establish agreement on the allocation keys for GHG emissions and SOC removals by crop.
- ❖ Formulate a common understanding on claims outside the value chain.

From our perspective, the CRCF can play a crucial role in facilitating the long-term monitoring of agricultural plots and the associated GHG emissions or removals and ensuring registration in a unique registry. This will ensure robustness, transparency, and mitigate the risk of double counting.

View our webinar on double counting risks in agricultural value chains

Launching large scale carbon farming projects : feedback from the French case using CarbonExtract MRV tool

LABEL BAS CARBONE powered by carbon extract

- ✓ Implementing a carbon farming project is complex. MRV tools are essential to simplify data collection and transition scenario calculations.
- ✓ Since 2020 in France, deployment of the Label bas-carbone certification framework through tier 3 MRV tools (Measuring, Reporting and Verification)
- ✓ + More than 5,000 farms involved, including 1,482 using the CarbonExtract tool
- ✓ Baseline calculated from historical farm practices and realistic simulations based on farmers' choices

Process of implementing a carbon farming project

Training and educational challenges

- Farmers need to understand the challenges of the low-carbon transition and the different carbon farming practices. **Technical advisors are the key players in supporting farmers in this transition.**
- MRV tools can be used to test different combinations of realistic carbon farming practices according to the farmer's choices.
- Handling these tools requires training for technical advisors and farmers who work together on each farm's ideal transition pathway.

Agrosolutions designed a specific training program, hybrid remote and presential to train > 300 farm advisors in less than 3 years

> 200 input data needed to calculate the carbon footprint of farms

Analysis of the average carbon footprint of french farms and transition potential

Recommandations for the CRCF

- ✓ Based on our experience, a significant proportion of farms could generate soil emission reduction credits rather than net carbon removal credits. Indeed, most of the transition potential is to reduce soil GHG emissions. It would therefore be important to consider these soil emission reduction credits within the CRCF, as they represent a significant transition potential.

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Contact us :

Célia Ruau – crEAU@agrosolutions.com

Roxane Photinodellis – rphotinodellis@agrosolutions.com

Edouard Lanckriet – elanckriet@agrosolutions.com

FARM MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION STRATEGIES FOR SCOPE 3 REPORTING : LESSONS FROM A DECADE-LONG PROJECT

Authors LORAND Lorette, LANCKRIET Edouard

Affiliations Agrosolutions, SMAG

Agrosolutions (consultancy) and SMAG (French FMS leader) have collaborated for 10 years with agro-industries to measure and improve the environmental footprint of upstream agricultural activities (scope 3). From a very small-scale process in the early years, they have created an automated model from data collection to the production of tailor-made indicators, now used for scope 3 reporting by world leaders in agricultural value chains.

CONTEXT

FMS enable farmers to **track field operations** and can be used for scope 3 and regulatory **reporting**. Sharing farmer's data across the value chain **requires their consent**.

Challenges with **data accuracy** and **reporting** require robust processing and refinement.

Agro-industries must **accurately report their environmental impact**, based on robust and clear data.

Develop a **robust, transparent and traceable data processing chain** for Scope 3 reporting.

Ensure data quality through **structured and auditable process**.

Automate calculations for key sustainability indicators across a **large number of farms** and **various countries**.

PROCESS

- Initially, data was manually collected and processed at plot level via the FMS when available or using a tailored questionnaire otherwise.
- Data quality issues and incomplete reporting emerged :
 - Improved tracking files & preliminary data control to address these issues.
- Development of a semi-automated process :
 - Ensuring higher data reliability while allowing optimal use of FMS.

Data collection

Farmers report practices via FMS or tailor made questionnaire.

Data aggregated at the cooperative level in a unified file.

Data verification

300 control points at the practice, field, farm level. Data **completeness** and **coherence** check.

Creation of an **outliers detection** algorithm.

Data process

75 sustainability indicators

GHG emissions, yields, TFI, costs, % of soil coverage, legumes %, nitrogen efficiency...

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

TAILOR MADE INDICATORS

designed for agro-food companies and farmers cooperatives

Automated GHG emissions calculations from FMS. Data verification process.

Semi-automated calculations of specific indicators from FMS or farmers reporting.

RESULTS

- Multiple **agro-industries, biofuel companies** and **farmers cooperatives** use this tool for **scope 3 reporting** : calculating GHG emissions at plot level in different European countries (SBTi FLAG compliant).
- The data input quality and quantity increases when farmers have a coherent rewarding scheme.
- This data processing chain has been integrated into two tools: **SMAG Trace** and **Prosper**.
- Data from FMSs are sometimes **still not exploitable**, contain **insufficient information**, or **aren't interoperable**. Additional data collection files have been developed to solve this issue.
- Integrated authorisation and consent process** for sharing farmers' data with players in the value chain.

CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS

- Data processing chain and outliers detection automation have enabled the development of tools that **fully leverage the potential of FMS**.
- FMS are the most effective solution to **provide primary data for agricultural reporting** when associated with automated data quality processes.
- Processes have been **industrialised and automated** to meet the needs of industrials for multiple operations and farms in multiple countries.
- Next step: calculations of **carbon removals** and **cobenefits indicators** at plot level are being developed.

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Contact us :
Lorette LORAND - llorand@agrosolutions.com
Edouard LANCKRIET - elanckriet@agrosolutions.com

Cost and mitigation potential of transition pathways for low-carbon agriculture in France

Objectives

- Estimate, at farm scale in France, the cost and mitigation potential of several agricultural practices on arable crops & transition scenarios (combination of these practices)
- Quantify :
 - Abatement costs (€/tCO₂e)
 - Income from carbon credits (€/ha) based on tCO₂e price

Method : Data and model

Dataset based on data collected from **1,482 farms**, including soil type, weather, crop rotation, yields, and fertilizer application,...

Implementation cost :
Δ Cost before and after practice adoption
Data sources : Annual Agricultural Statistics, French Chambers of Agriculture, Eurostat

Mitigation potential :
Based on the field crops method - **Label Bas Carbone**
Carbon sequestration using equations from **Carbon Tester***, simplified version of AMG model (uncertainty assessed)

Results at farm level averaged at regional and national scales

* **carbon tester** carbon footprint simplified assessments tool

10 levers and 4 transition pathways scenarios

& 3 Scenarios of mineral fertilizer prices

Low impact on production
Low implementation costs
Low mitigation potential

High impact on production
High implementation costs
High mitigation potential

- ✓ 2023 Price
- ✓ Historical peak price over the last 20 years
- ✓ Average price from 2000 to 2023

Data sources : Eurostat

First Results - Insertion of a legume in the rotation

- ✓ **Initial state:** Legumes cover 4% of the rotation on average in our dataset
- ✓ **Implementation assumptions :**
 - Results for 3 legumes : soybean, alfalfa, protein peas
 - Increase to 15% of the rotation area
 - Fertilization eliminated on legume areas
 - 15 uN/ha reduction for the following crop

Results - National average per ha of legumes implemented :

Cost of implementation (€/ha/yr)

Scenarios mineral fertilizer prices	Soybean	Alfalfa	Protein Peas
2023 Price	817,84	530,44	713,23
Historical peak price	672,29	384,89	567,68
Average price from 2000 to 2023	942,06	654,66	837,45

Mitigation potential

2,24 tCO₂e/yr/ ha

Abatement costs : €236.62/tCO₂e/yr

Income for a carbon price of €30/tCO₂e: €67.23

Next steps

- Several valuation scenarios for newly introduced crops (e.g., legumes, hemp): multiple price market scenarios
- Estimation of costs and mitigation potential over different implementation durations
- Impact of each scenarios on biodiversity by assessing changes in biodiversity indicators before and after practices implementation

Open to new collaborations:

Possibility to support institutes/companies in developing mitigation strategies at the farm level or across agricultural supply chains

Contact us : Roxane Photinodellis rphotinodellis@agrosolutions.com ; Edouard Lanckriet - elanckriet@agrosolutions.com

Calculations of GHG emissions in agriculture according to IPCC guidelines: analysis of approaches and methods

Ilze Luksta, Krista Laktuka, Dagnija Blumberga
Institute of Energy Systems and Environment
Riga Technical University

Introduction

The agricultural sector is a significant source of GHG emissions, so accurate estimates are important for policymaking and achieving climate goals. The IPCC methodology provides an internationally recognized approach to emission estimates, which is also used in national communications. Although the Latvian report is based on this methodology, the calculation results differ, which requires an assessment of possible methodological and data interpretation differences. The estimates of enteric fermentation emissions according to the IPCC and the Latvian National inventory report were reviewed and compared.

Conclusion

The calculation of GHG emissions for cattle is based on several key energy requirements: maintenance, activity, pregnancy, growth, and lactation. Additionally, two important ratios are considered—REM (Ratio of net energy available in the diet for maintenance to digestible energy consumed) and REG (Ratio of net energy available for growth in a diet to digestible energy consumed). Data from Latvia's National Inventory Report were used in IPCC equations to recalculate emissions. Despite using identical input data, the final results differed. Possible reasons include variations in methodological assumptions, energy conversion factors, or specific adjustments applied in the National report.

Methodology

Parametr	Calculated
NE _m	45,029 MJ/day
NE _a	7,655 MJ/day
NE _l	62,914 MJ/day
NE _p	3,737 MJ/day
REM	0,52
REG	0,319

$$GE = \left[\left(\frac{NE_m + NE_a + NE_l + NE_{work} + NE_p}{REM} \right) + \left(\frac{NE_g}{REG} \right) \right] \cdot \frac{DE\%}{100}$$

$$EF = \left[\frac{GE \cdot \left(\frac{Y_m}{100} \right) \cdot 365}{55.65} \right]$$

Parametr	Calculated	LV NIR	Difference
GE (MJ/day)	342,34	357	4 % less
EF (kg CH ₄ /head/year)	146	152,2	

This work has been supported by the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility within the Project No 5.2.1.1.0/2/24//CFLA/003 "Implementation of consolidation and management changes at Riga Technical University, Liepaja University, Rezekne Academy of Technology, Latvian Maritime Academy and Liepaja Maritime College for the progress towards excellence in higher education, science and innovation" academic career doctoral grant (ID 1093).

The Role of the CRCF Regulation in the EU Regulatory and Policy Planning Framework

Krista LAKTUKA, Ilze LUKSTA, Dagnija BLUMBERGA

Riga Technical University, Institute of Energy Systems and Environment

Contact information:
Azenes iela 12/1, Rīga,
Latvia, LV-1048
E-mail: krista.laktuka@rtu.lv

Introduction

The CRCF Regulation aims to establish a voluntary EU certification framework for permanent carbon removal, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, supporting the EU's climate neutrality targets and commitments under the Paris Agreement. A single certification framework will ensure accountability, transparency and strict monitoring requirements in line with the IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. This will prevent double counting, while ensuring that carbon removals and soil emission reductions achieved at the farm level are accurately reflected in Member States' National Inventory Reports. Beyond its environmental role, the CRCF Regulation also plays a crucial role in creating new profit opportunities for farmers and foresters. This study aims to examine the wider significance of the CRCF Regulation within the existing EU policy framework and to identify its links and interactions.

Methodology

Qualitative content analysis combined with snowball sampling was used, resulting in the selection and inclusion of 31 documents, followed by the selection and search of nine keywords within the documents.

Results

Acknowledgements: This work has been supported by the Latvia's state budget Fundamental and Applied Research Project "A Policy Planning Roadmap for Carbon Farming Certification Schemes" No. lzp-2023/1-0417

LIFE Carbon Farming: Development and implementation of a result-based funding mechanism for carbon farming in EU mixed crop livestock systems

Anaïs L'Hôte¹, Juliette Ferial¹, Donal O'Brien², Bright Ketadzo²

¹ French Livestock Institute, Paris, France

²Teagasc, Environment Research Centre, Johnstown Castle, Co. Wexford

THE PROJECT AND ITS OBJECTIVES

- 2021 – 2027**
- 40 partners in 6 countries**
- 600 dairy and beef farms involved**

- 60 advisors trained to carbon audit tools and carbon certification**
- Reduction of 15% of farms carbon footprint**
- Rewarding farmers for their efforts**

A COMMON MRV METHOD

Scope considered and 3 carbon audit tools based on LCA used

Carbon Farming practices implemented

GHG emissions

- Herd management: health conditions, age at 1st calving, etc.
- Herd feeding: grazing, concentrates consumption, forages quality, etc.
- Effluents management: storage and spreading of effluents, etc.
- Crops management: fertilisation, legumes seeding, crops rotation, etc.
- Energy consumption: electricity and fuel consumption, etc.

Carbon sequestration

- Cultivated surfaces management: direct seeding, temporary grasslands, etc.
- Management of agroecological elements: permanent grasslands, agroforestry, hedgerows, etc.

Co-benefits

Steps of the farmer's project (duration of 5 years)

SUSTAINABILITY GRID

Developing a whole farm sustainability assessment methodology based on carbon audit tools and a sustainability grid including:

- 10 environmental indicators
- 5 economic indicators
- 8 social indicators
- These sustainability indicators are assessed on each farm at the beginning and at the end of the project.

ASSESSING IMPLEMENTATION COSTS FOR CARBON FARMING

Implementation costs are expressed in €/tCO₂e avoided and are composed of:

- Transition costs including:
 - Technical costs assessed thanks to partial budgets method.
 - Risk evaluation if targets are not meet.
 - Training costs and additional work needed to put in place a new practice.
- Administrative costs, i.e. all the costs related to advisory to farmers, MRV process including certification audit.

Figure: Detail of transition costs considered in the assessment of implementation costs

FUNDINGS FARMERS

Several ways for companies to fund farmers

- Offsetting of the residual emissions of a company
- Voluntary contribution to climate change mitigation
- Reduction on scope 3 (Example of Lidl: purchasing of carbon certificates from its own beef suppliers.)

Carbon credit: 41 or 43€/tCO₂ avoided, inc. 33€ for the farmer, 5€ for advisory entities, 3€ for FCAA, 2€ for Carbioz (platform to communicate on farmer's projects)

Figure: Funding farmers, making the link between the carbon farming stakeholders

NIBIO
NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE OF
BIOECONOMY RESEARCH

Carbon Farming initiatives and research in South-East Norway

Isabell Eischeid, Manon Bajard, Justine Bec

A pilot study

- 9 Carbon farmers and 7 neighbours
- In-field investigations
- Carbon stock mapping, soil health & agronomy
- In cooperation with the Norwegian agricultural extension service

Carbon stock mapping

- Predefined grid
- 3 depths (10,20,30 cm)
- Bulk density & carbon content
- 448 samples total

Analyses are ongoing...

Soil health

- Aggregate stability (4 methods)
- Microbial activity (cotton strips and teabags)
- Vess scores

Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (Vess) score range from 1 – very good structure, to 5 – poor structure. They correlate well with our wet-sieving aggregate stability measurements.

Carbon farming initiatives running for 3 years or longer tended to have higher aggregate stability compared to their neighbours.

An incubation experiment with teabags showed for the most part little difference between the carbon farmers and their neighbours.

Do you want to collaborate?

This initiative was internally funded by our institute. We would love to collaborate with similar projects across Europe, to either expand, conduct more detailed analyses, knowledge exchange and compare results. I have experience with soils, ecology, agronomy, remote sensing and long-term adaptive monitoring.

Get in touch!

isabell.eischeid@nibio.no
+4791172753
NIBIO Apelsvoll, Norway

Or find me at the conference.

EUROPEAN
CARBON FARMING
SUMMIT

Living Labs for People (LL4P) in Qingshan, China: Practice from Observers to Stakeholders

Kevin Chen*, XinXin Wang, Zhen Yan, Wei Zhang
 *Zhejiang University and International Food Policy Research Institute,
 E-mail: kchen@zju.edu.cn

Why Qingshan Village?

- Location: Yuhang District, Hangzhou City, Zhejiang Province
- Covering 45.6 square kilometers, 800+ households, 2,800+ population, 110+ new residents;
- Longwu Reservoir Small Water Source Protection Project-Drinking water quality;
- From a poverty-stricken village facing depopulation challenges to a thriving community that attracts new residents (1109) from around the world in less than a decade.
- A "Future Village" and a "Zero (Low) Carbon Village" Pilots in Zhejiang Province
- The bottom-up, adaptive rural governance development exemplifies an innovative approach to collaboration among various stakeholders, great help in constructing our Living LAB

As Observers: to see, to listen, and to feel May- July, 2024

- Key observation:**
- good ecological environment, full of bamboo;
 - new residents; full of artistic atmosphere;
 - Future coastal, Happiness, a vibrant village;
 - hotels & restaurants, local food system

Achievement:
 Clearly understand the current situation and the development status of ecology and economy in Qingshan Village

As Detectives: to discover, to explain

QUESTION 1: What's special about this village?

The Methods and data collection process

The Development Stage of Qingshan Village

2009-2014	2015-2018	2019-2021	2022-now
• Fully established after merging 3 small villages.	• Established "Good Water Future"	• Significant progress in building polycentric governance, strengthening the self-governance system, and pursuing "inclusive and quality" development.	• Selected by Zhejiang Province as a pilot for "Future Village" development, part of the province's comprehensive rural revitalization strategy, with a clear goal of achieving development and rural revitalization.
• Low income levels and scattered new urban residents and domestic and international visitors	• Established "Living Labs" and "Future Village" pilot projects, and "Nature 360°"	• Village enterprisism established to help the "Future Village" residents support farmers in stable registration and housing to increase income	• Selected by government as a pilot for "Low Carbon Village" pilot

The Transition of Qingshan's social network

The net map with key stakeholders for Qingshan

Lessons

- The bottom-up, adaptive rural governance development exemplifies an innovative approach to collaboration among various stakeholders, provides great help to construct our Living LAB
- The net mapping clearly shows Qingshan's governance and helps us understand our role in the future in helping construct the Living Labs.

As Stakeholders: to participate and to construct the rural village

Zero-Carbon Smart Farmhouse

May, 2024- Future

- A: Zero-Carbon Renovation Model for Rural Building (Life)
- B: Ecological Renovation Model for Rural Courtyards (Life)
- C: Low-Carbon Renovation Model for Farm Gardens (Production)
- D: Rice Low-Carbon Cultivation Technology Pilot Project (Production)
- E: Low-Carbon Rice Field Experimental Renovation Model (Production)
- F: Green & Organic Tea Planting Demonstration Garden (Production)
- G: Low-carbon Bamboo Forest Pilot Project (Production)

What's next? The innovations towards the Living Lab at Qingshan Village.

- Establish a green digital control brain for Qingshan Village to achieve precise carbon control, and Connect with the Household Carbon Account
- Develop a replicable and scalable low carbon and smart rural transformation plan, effectively involving all stakeholders in the countryside to create a radiating driving effect.
- Develop a series of assessment standards for green buildings, ecological gardens, and green rice fields, boom and tea garden, providing a scientific basis for ecological compensation systems and fair energy transitions in rural areas.

QUESTION 2: How do residents think about the Low-Carbon Local Food System?

(Identifying Key Factors to Achieve a Low-Carbon Local Food System)

Methodology: Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM)

Sessions	Classification	Stakeholders	N	Total
Session 1	Local Residents	Local Farmers (Crop Farmers)	2	13
		Local Farmers (Livestock Farmers)	5	
		Local Residents with no occupation or Fields	3	
Session 2	New Residents	Local residents with no occupation or Fields	2	10
		Foreigners (Overseas)	1	
Session 3	Mixed Females	New residents with no occupation or Fields	2	13
		Local residents	5	
		New residents with no occupation or Fields	1	
Session 4	Government related	Public employees	2	10
		Members of local government officials	2	
		Village committee	3	
		Government employees	1	
		Public employees	1	
		Local government officials	1	

Mental models in four sessions

Finding: Drivers of the four FCM models

Sessions	Key factors
Session 1 Local Residents	Financial support (A1)
	Knowledge (A2)
Session 2 New Residents	Publicity and Education (BC3)
	Low-carbon consciousness (BC4)
Session 3 Females	Proximity (CC2)
	Education (CC7)
Session 4 Government Related	Government support (DC1)

QUESTION 3: What's the general current low carbon practice for local residents?

Methodology

- Full sample survey with 725 households & 2200+ population survey
- July-September, 2024

Findings

- Lessons**
- Low-carbon rural fair transition issues
 - Cost-effectiveness analysis
 - Sustainability carbon reduction methods: affordable, Economic and environmental benefits; Compliance with local cultural characteristics.

Scale up at national, regional and village level

VALO. S. E. R. - VALORISATION OF THE AGRI-FOOD PRODUCTS OF THE EMILIAN SANDS

The sustainable district of food

Delta Institute for Applied Ecology -
Agronomist Gloria Minarelli, Agronomist Dania Baldoni

VALO.S.E.R. PROJECT

The VALO.S.E.R. project - Valorisation of the agri-food products of the Emilia-Romagna sands has been financed by Measure 161.01 - Operational groups of the EIP for agricultural productivity and sustainability under the RDP 2014-2020 of the Emilia-Romagna Region (Italy).

VALO.S.E.R. aims to local development, competitiveness, aggregation between companies in the sandy soil area and the dissemination of a culture of agro environmental sustainability also among consumers. The collaboration between enterprises aims at maintaining an active dialogue with institutions at the local level on the threats to the fertility and healthiness of sandy soils.

Local vegetables.

STUDY AREA

Area of the sands Emilia Romagna Region

The territory, with an extension of 18,598.70 hectares, falls within 6 local administrations in the province of Ferrara, is partly located within the Emilia-Romagna Po Delta Regional Park and in the area recognised as a UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve since 2015, its vocation is agricultural and nature tourism.

The main crops are potatoes, carrots, tomatoes, durum wheat, soft wheat and fruit nurseries.

The cultivated land is located up to more than 2 metres below sea level. Soils in the pilot area are classified as sandy since the sand content exceeds 60%. These soils are poorly structured, light and loose; they show limited water retention capacity and high permeability, low organic matter content.

AREA-RELATED CHALLENGES

The sandy soils in the study area are characterised by two criticalities:

- salinisation and ingress salinisation which causes reduced production;
- low organic matter content.

Saline ingress is caused by salty sea water, which is denser and comes into contact with coastal aquifers; this phenomenon is favoured by the lowering of the groundwater level due to the excessive use of groundwater for irrigation purposes and the pumping action carried out for land reclamation (saline wedge).

The high sand concentration and low organic carbon content of the pilot area's soils means that it is of paramount importance to implement sustainable fertility-preserving agricultural practices in advance so that healthy, sustainable and quality food can continue to be produced.

These are the challenges that farmers face in order to continue sustainable and competitive agriculture.

Sandy soil.

FARMERS' OPINIONS

A questionnaire identified the importance for farmers on the following issues:

- apply low-impact agronomic practices;
- maintain soil fertility;
- dialogue with institutions on sandy soil issues;
- define the 'sand products' brand;
- invest in soil health;
- address the threats: climate change, drought, salinisation and organic matter deficiency.

The result highlighted the importance of adopting a development model based on a 'territorial district' approach rather than an individual one.

MODEL ADOPTED: VALO.S.E.R. THE SUSTAINABILITY DISTRICT

The establishment of the 'Sustainable District', an aggregation of enterprises in the agri-food chain, followed the 4 requirements of Emilia Romagna Region Resolution No. 1816 of 28/10/2019, which regulates the recognition of Food Districts:

- Production scope: several agricultural products, tomato, potato, carrot and wheat;
- Territoriality: the enterprises operate in a well-defined territory of 6 contiguous municipalities;
- Representativeness: the District has demonstrated that it dedicates at least 30% of the cultivation for each product concerned in relation to the total area indicated (cultivated hectares);
- Governance: the business group has set up regulations to manage binding relations for those participating in the district and an Action Plan.

The partner companies of the VALO.S.E.R. project have pursued the 'Sustainable District' model as they have demonstrated that 30% of the total area involved is certified according to national and/or European standards: measures of the regional RDP integrated production, increase of organic matter, organic farming, and finally investments for water saving and pollution reduction.

Dublin 4-6 March 2025

Valuing the benefits of carbon farming beyond carbon: indicators to assess soil ecosystem services in three European case studies

Chiara De Notaris¹, Raul Zornoza², Francisco Alcán³, Andrés Rodríguez Seijo³, María Vincenza Chiriaco⁴, Linda Calciolari⁴, Ana Martínez Crucis⁵, Elena de Julian Sánchez⁶, María Catalán Balmaseda⁶, Gianluca Carboni⁷, Valentina Mereu¹

¹CMCC Foundation – Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change, Italy - chiara.denotaris@cmcc.it

²Technical University of Cartagena, Spain; ³University of Vigo, Spain; ⁴Ekoboerderij de Lingehof, The Netherlands; ⁵Fundación Global Nature, Spain; ⁶ACTYVA, Spain; ⁷Agris Sardegna, Italy

Background

According to the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation, carbon farming practices must generate co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health and the avoidance of land degradation. In addition, "Operators or groups of operators should be able to report co-benefits that contribute to the sustainability objectives beyond the minimum sustainability requirements [...] Certification methodologies should, as much as possible, incentivise the generation of co-benefits for biodiversity going beyond the minimum sustainability requirements, with a view to generating a market premium for the certified units" (CRCF Regulation (EU) 2024/3012). Developing a common methodology is challenging, and joint efforts are needed.

Two Horizon Europe projects aim at ensuring accountability of soil health and biodiversity within the EU carbon farming certification framework.

→ Indicator-based approach, where a wide set of indicators is measured in a large number of case studies, and the most sensitive are identified.

Three representative case studies from InBestSoil

Pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean (1-2) and Atlantic (3)

Land uses: Agriculture (2-3) and Forestry (1)

Practices:

- 1) Rotational grazing to improve forest (Dehesa) soil quality, since 2019
- 2) Reduced tillage, cover crops and crop rotations, since 2009
- 3) Reduced tillage, cover crops and crop rotations, since 2005

The table below includes the most sensitive indicators to discriminate between managements in the three selected case studies, grouped by ecosystem service and corresponding sustainability objective of the CRCF Regulation. All indicators can be measured based on standardized scientific methodologies and a complete list will be reported as an outcome of the projects. The ones marked with * are satellite-based.

Category	Soil ecosystem service	Sustainability objective (CRCF Regulation (EU) 2024/3012)	Most sensitive indicators		
			CS1 (Mediterranean forest)	CS2 (Mediterranean agricultural)	CS3 (Atlantic agricultural)
Provisioning	Provision of food	Climate change adaptation	-	Crop yield	na
	Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Transition to a circular economy	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)*	-	-
Regulating	Climate regulation	Climate change mitigation	Total soil organic carbon; Albedo and land surface temperature	Particulate soil organic carbon; potential soil CO2 emissions; Net primary productivity	Total soil organic carbon; particulate soil organic carbon; Net primary productivity
	Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Sustainable use and protection of water; pollution prevention and control	Total mercury; pH	-	-
	Nutrient cycling	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation; pollution prevention and control; sustainable use and protection of water	Available phosphorus; exchangeable magnesium	Total nitrogen; exchangeable ammonium; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium; cation exchange capacity	Total nitrogen; nitrates; bioavailable zinc; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium
	Flood regulation and water storage	Climate change adaptation	Bulk density; water content at field capacity	Drought Stress Index (DSI)*; water content at field capacity; mean weight diameter of soil aggregates	Drought Stress Index (DSI)*; clay content; bulk density
Supporting	Erosion control	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Vegetation cover	Vegetation cover; bare soil index	Vegetation cover; bare soil index
	Biodiversity	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Total PLFAs; Fungal Shannon Index; Fungal Chao1 Index	Total PLFAs; actinomicota biomass; bacterial abundance; Prokaryotic Simpson Index	Firmicutes abundance; bacterial abundance; Fungal Chao1 Index
	Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Soil sealing	Soil sealing	Presence of natural green elements

For more information: <https://inbestsoil.eu/>; <https://bioservices-project.eu/>; <https://soilcommunity.app/>

Using remote sensing techniques to determine above ground biomass stocks at the national scale.

Luke Farrow^a, Josephine Hornsey^b and Alex Higgins^a

^a Agri-Environment Branch, Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, Belfast, BT9 5PX, N. Ireland
^b Forest Research, Bush Estate, Roslin, EH25 9SY, Scotland

Highlights

- Goal is to deliver per-field estimates of aboveground biomass for all agricultural fields in Northern Ireland.
- AGB values derived from 16ppm LiDAR.
- Optimise hedge detection protocols chosen for use in an Irish setting.

Introduction

The Soil Nutrient Health Scheme (SNHS), a £37 million, four-year project funded by the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs, is the largest soil sampling and analysis programme ever undertaken. The project aims to measure soil nutrient status, map sub-field scale runoff risk and determine aboveground biomass (AGB) quantities for all agricultural fields in Northern Ireland (Fig 1.). This poster explores the work undertaken to develop a workflow that can estimate AGB values at a national scale. It is intended that the protocol should be applicable both nationally and internationally and will form an important part of the process of reliably monitoring AGB change through time.

Figure 1: Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland

Figure 2: (a) A rural landscape where local high points of vegetation have been identified by our protocol and (b) the other side of the same fields where a Canopy Height Model has also been added.

Workflow

We have developed a protocol that can quantify, at the national scale, per field carbon (C) and AGB quantities. The protocol uses high-resolution (16 ppm) LiDAR survey data that was collected in leaf-off conditions and freeware.

The LiDAR data is analysed to determine both the presence /absence of vegetation and the volume of space occupied by said vegetation (Fig 2). Allometric equations that have previously been derived for vegetation growing across the island of Ireland are then used to determine the aboveground biomass of each woodland area and hedge. Finally, these values are apportioned to individual fields (Fig. 3). This allows us to build a national-scale baseline for AGB and C stocks against which future surveys can be referenced.

Future works

- Verification of the accuracy of the current model against field data for vegetation presence/absence and AGB totals.
- Optimisation of hedge detection - differing characteristics of hedgerow and woodland blocks offers optimisation opportunities.
- Determination of allometric equations that best reflect Irish hedge growth patterns.
- Adoption of broadleaved and coniferous vegetation allometric equations that have been developed from vegetation that grew on the island of Ireland.
- Exploration of impacts of agroforestry on allometric equations best-suited to use in the model.
- LiDAR is expensive and challenging to collect in a maritime climate - explore the potential of radar to contribute to long-term monitoring efforts.

Figure 3: Example area of farmland and woodland showing per-field aboveground biomass totals.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA) as part of the Soil Nutrient Health Scheme.

Access further information about the SNHS here

www.afbini.gov.uk

Access further information about the SNHS here

PeatNI: Building trust in carbon emissions from intensively managed grass on peatlands in Northern Ireland

Phoebe A. Morton¹, Naomi H. Rutherford², Taro Takahashi², Suzanne Higgins¹

¹Agri-Environment Branch, Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, Newforge Lane, Belfast, Northern Ireland
²Sustainable Livestock Systems, Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, Large Park, Hillsborough, Northern Ireland

INTRODUCTION

The UK greenhouse gas (GHG) inventory suggests that one of the highest emitting categories of peatland in the UK are those which are farmed as intensive grassland. However, many of these measurements have been made in England only or derived from data measured across Europe. Given that the climate of Northern Ireland is cooler and wetter than much of England, and certainly most of Europe, it is likely that these values overestimate the carbon loss from improved grass peatlands in Northern Ireland. Under the Climate Change Act (Northern Ireland) (2022), Northern Ireland has a target to reduce GHG emissions by 48% by 2030. Therefore, a reliable and accurate baseline is needed for intensive grassland on peat to enable calculation of the potential reduction of carbon emissions under restoration scenarios and to fairly apportion realistic targets to this land use.

PROJECT AIMS

The PeatNI project aims to:

- Install eddy covariance flux towers (Figure 1), measuring carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), on six intensively managed grassland peat sites
- Monitor the carbon emissions on these six sites over at least two years
- Measure nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions on at least two of these sites to account for emissions from fertiliser, slurry or animal excreta
- Deploy GreenFeed units periodically to measure GHG emissions from animals grazing on the sites.

Overall, PeatNI aims to evaluate the GHG emissions from intensively managed grass on peatlands in Northern Ireland to obtain a country-specific (Tier 3) value for the UK Inventory and a baseline value for supporting farmers to alter management practices in order to farm for carbon conservation.

FIGURE 1: A typical eddy covariance flux tower

FIGURE 2: Map of assessed potential field sites to host an eddy covariance flux tower across Northern Ireland (blue markers), with the six most likely sites highlighted (purple with white star).

SITE SELECTION

An advert for farmers and landowners to volunteer their grassland peat sites was placed in the local farming press and distributed through various organisations. A leaflet was also printed and distributed at existing farming events, such as the Balmoral Show, project roadshows and farmers' marts.

Over 40 farmers expressed an interest in participating. PeatNI has visited 66 fields (Figure 2), which were across 36 different farms. For each field, peat extent and depth, organic matter content (by loss on ignition), whether the field was intensive grassland and the suitability of the field to host an eddy covariance flux tower were evaluated.

NORTHERN IRELAND-SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

Whilst there are challenges associated with measuring fluxes for the GHG Inventory of any country, and in siting eddy covariance flux towers more generally, there are a number of challenges that are specific to Northern Ireland.

Surrounded by trees and hedges or wind turbines

Peat depth and extent not consistent across fields

Despite these challenges, there are some fields that may be suitable. It is important to measure GHG fluxes in fields that are representative of intensive grassland on peat in Northern Ireland, rather than fields that are best suited for eddy covariance flux towers, in order to improve inventory values for Northern Ireland.

informa

SCIENCE-BASED INTEGRATED
FOREST MANAGEMENT
FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION

Strengthening Forest Carbon Certification for a Resilient Future

Author: Simeon Max, George McLoughlin, Climate-KIC and Julia Grimault, Simon Martel, I4CE

Due to their enormous potential to absorb and convert atmospheric carbon into biomass, forests are known as the Earth's largest terrestrial carbon sink. But while they help stabilize the planet's climate, forests are suffering more frequent natural disasters and disturbances due to the climate emergency, such as forest fires and pest outbreaks.

To enhance forests' resilience to climate change, boost carbon sequestration and protect biodiversity and renewable natural resources, the EU-funded **INFORMA project** is developing and implementing best **Sustainable Forest Management (SFM)** practices across Europe's five most representative biogeographical regions.

WP5 of the INFORMA project focuses on **improving forest carbon certification** in Europe by enhancing **monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV)** systems while creating favorable market conditions for carbon credit adoption. The goal is to make certification frameworks **more robust, cost-effective, and widely accepted** by private project developers, public institutions, and buyers.

The carbon sequestration capacity of European forests has declined due to factors like climate-induced disturbances such as pests, fires, and storms, and forest aging.

The challenge in certifying Improved Forest Management (IFM) projects:

- **Defining Improved Forest Management (IFM) Practices** – The broad range of practices classified as IFM creates inconsistencies in certification methodologies, making it difficult to establish clear eligibility criteria.
- **Baseline Uncertainty and Risk of Over-Crediting** – The choice of baseline scenarios significantly impacts carbon credit issuance, and overly flexible or unrealistic baselines can lead to inflated crediting.
- **Non-Permanence and Carbon Reversal Risks** – Carbon stored in forests is vulnerable to re-emission due to natural disturbances (e.g., wildfires, pests, and extreme weather), requiring robust safeguards.
- **Ensuring Sustainability Beyond Carbon Sequestration** – Certification must integrate biodiversity, water conservation, and socio-economic benefits to ensure that carbon projects deliver positive long-term environmental and social impacts.

European forests and wood products currently remove around **332MtCO₂ eq** per year (292 forest + 40 HWP), compensating for approximately **10% of the EU's total GHG emissions**

Forest Carbon Certification work is co-lead by **I4CE and Climate-KIC** with **12 partners in 8 EU countries**

INFORMA ensures that forest-specific characteristics are fully **integrated into the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF)** regulations.

Our recommendations for integrating forest carbon within carbon certification standards

- 1. Diversify Improved Forest Management (IFM) Practices in Certification**
 - Expand the range of eligible forest management practices beyond conservation-focused approaches.
 - Encourage thinning, enrichment planting, and risk management strategies that enhance resilience against disturbances like wildfires and disease.
 - Develop **science-backed methodologies** that quantify carbon impact and risk reduction effectively.
- 2. Strengthen Baseline Setting to Reduce Over-Crediting Risks**
 - Limit project developers' flexibility in choosing baselines to reduce **bias and information asymmetry**.
 - Explore **dynamic baselines**, which adjust based on real-world comparisons with similar areas without carbon projects.
 - Ensure baselines **align with actual carbon stocks** to encourage meaningful land-use changes.
- 3. Improve Carbon Permanence Measures Considering Climate Change Risks**
 - Increase buffer pool deductions to account for **higher climate risks** such as wildfires, droughts, and disease outbreaks.
 - Regularly update methodologies based on the **latest climate science**.
 - Incentivize practices that **prioritize no-regret strategies** with both short and long-term impacts on forest resilience and mitigation.
- 4. Integrate Clearer Sustainability Criteria in Certification**
 - Establish **consistent guidelines** across IFM methodologies to assess biodiversity, water conservation, and socio-economic impacts.
 - Ensure that carbon projects not only have **no negative impact** but also create **positive environmental co-benefits** (a requirement under the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework - CRCF).
 - Increase **transparency for project financiers** by standardizing sustainability indicators.

These recommendations aim to **increase trust in forest carbon certification, reduce market loopholes, and improve the credibility of forest-based carbon credits.**

OUR PARTNERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 101019039.

Stay in the loop on forest carbon certification and join our upcoming focus group discussions!

Informa-forests
@informa-forests.eu
info@informa-forests.eu

HarvREST
Greener Farming with RES

Harnessing the vast potential of RES for sustainable farming

Objective

The main objective of HarvREST is to improve the existing knowledge of options for reducing carbon emissions on farms, by maximising synergies between the integration of RES and sustainable agricultural practices.

Main outcomes of HarvREST

An Agricultural Virtual Power Plant (AVPP)

Capable of running diverse scenarios and farm configurations. The tool will determine the best operational procedures for a given RES solution.

A Decision Support System (DSS)

To make recommendations of the best RES integration solutions & operation procedures for optimized production based on data from AVPP.

A Business Model Catalogue

Containing relevant innovative business models, considering financial schemes and incentives while identifying risks.

PARTNERS

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Follow us for more info

www.harvrest.eu

[linkedin.com/harvREST](https://www.linkedin.com/company/harvrest)

[x.com/HarvREST_eu](https://twitter.com/HarvREST_eu)

informa

SCIENCE-BASED INTEGRATED
FOREST MANAGEMENT
FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION

Strengthening Forest Carbon Certification for a Resilient Future

Author: Simon Max, Climate-KIC and Julia Grimault, Simon Martel, I4CE

Due to their enormous potential to absorb and convert atmospheric carbon into biomass, forests are known as the Earth's largest terrestrial carbon sink. But while they help stabilize the planet's climate, forests are suffering more frequent natural disasters and disturbances due to the climate emergency, such as forest fires and pest outbreaks.

To enhance forests' resilience to climate change, boost carbon sequestration and protect biodiversity and renewable natural resources, the EU-funded **INFORMA project** is developing and implementing best **Sustainable Forest Management (SFM)** practices across Europe's five most representative biogeographical regions.

WP5 of the INFORMA project focuses on **improving forest carbon certification** in Europe by enhancing **monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV)** systems while creating favorable market conditions for carbon credit adoption. The goal is to make certification frameworks **more robust, cost-effective, and widely accepted** by private project developers, public institutions, and buyers.

The carbon sequestration capacity of European forests has declined due to factors like climate-induced disturbances such as pests, fires, and storms, increased harvesting and forest aging.

The challenge in certifying Improved Forest Management (IFM) projects:

- **Defining Improved Forest Management (IFM) Practices** – The broad range of practices classified as IFM creates inconsistencies in certification methodologies, making it difficult to establish clear eligibility criteria.
- **Baseline Uncertainty and Risk of Over-Crediting** – The choice of baseline scenarios significantly impacts carbon credit issuance, and overly flexible or unrealistic baselines can lead to inflated crediting.
- **Non-Permanence and Carbon Reversal Risks** – Carbon stored in forests is vulnerable to re-emission due to natural disturbances (e.g., wildfires, pests, and extreme weather), requiring robust safeguards.
- **Ensuring Sustainability Beyond Carbon Sequestration** – Certification must integrate biodiversity, water conservation, and socio-economic benefits to ensure that carbon projects deliver positive long-term environmental and social impacts.

Our recommendations for integrating forest carbon within carbon certification standards

- 1. Diversify Improved Forest Management (IFM) Practices in Certification**
 - Expand the range of eligible forest management practices beyond conservation-focused approaches.
 - Encourage thinning, enrichment planting, and risk management strategies that enhance resilience against disturbances like wildfires and disease.
 - Develop **science-backed methodologies** that quantify carbon impact and risk reduction effectively.
- 2. Strengthen Baseline Setting to Reduce Over-Crediting Risks**
 - Limit project developers' flexibility in choosing baselines to reduce **bias and information asymmetry**.
 - Explore **dynamic baselines**, which adjust based on real-world comparisons with similar areas without carbon projects.
 - Ensure baselines **align with actual carbon stocks** to encourage meaningful land-use changes.
- 3. Improve Carbon Permanence Measures Considering Climate Change Risks**
 - Increase buffer pool deductions to account for **higher climate risks** such as wildfires, droughts, and disease outbreaks.
 - Regularly update methodologies based on the **latest climate science**.
 - Incentivize practices that **prioritize no-regret strategies** with both short and long-term impacts on forest resilience and mitigation.
- 4. Integrate Clearer Sustainability Criteria in Certification**
 - Establish **consistent guidelines** across IFM methodologies to assess biodiversity, water conservation, and socio-economic impacts.
 - Ensure that carbon projects not only have **no negative impact** but also create **positive environmental co-benefits** (a requirement under the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework - CRCF).
 - Increase **transparency for project financiers** by standardizing sustainability indicators.

These recommendations aim to **increase trust in forest carbon certification, reduce market loopholes, and improve the credibility of forest-based carbon credits.**

OUR PARTNERS

Stay in the loop on forest carbon certification and join our upcoming focus group discussions!

Informa-forests
@informa-forests.eu
info@informa-forests.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 101019239.

An Earth-Observation framework for soil Carbon Sequestration Monitoring (EO4CSM) – A case study for the Netherlands

Wouter Meijninger, Jan Peter Lesschen, Chantal Hendriks Allard de Wit, Gerbert Roerink and Johnny te Roller

Introduction

Increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) content can make soils more resilient and increase overall soil fertility, but it also contributes to mitigating climate change by sequestering CO₂. The Dutch government has set a climate target of an additional SOC sequestration of 0.5 Mton CO₂ per year by 2030 in agricultural mineral soils.

Mineral soils are reported under the land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF) sector in the national inventory report on the greenhouse gas emissions (van Baren et al., 2024). In the current system, carbon fluxes are simulated using the SOC model RothC, which are now conducted at postal code level (PC), as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Annual Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) balance at PC4-level for 2018 [ton C/ha/yr].

Objective EO4CSM

EO4CSM aims to improve the current national monitoring of carbon sequestration of agricultural soils for the Netherlands (as demonstrated in Figure 1). The RothC model, will be coupled with Earth Observation (EO) data at field level, which provides more accurate and up to date information on vegetation cover, crop cover status and field management practices.

Figure 2. Annual SOC balance RothC at field level [ton C/ha/yr] for 2018.

Improvements SOC monitoring

Downscaling RothC

The RothC simulations are downscaled to field level (~500.000 fields). This introduces more spatial detail and the ability to feed the model with parcel specific data.

Vegetation cover (VC)

Static monthly VC data is replaced by Sentinel-2 (S2) based VC-data at field level. This introduces more spatial detail and allows variation between fields with the same crop and between (dry-wet) years.

Carbon input from cover crops

The C input from cover crops is updated: 1) S2 NDVI timeseries are used to detect the presence of cover crops, and corresponding growing period. 2) A hybrid crop simulation model combined with S2 fAPAR timeseries is used to determine the dry matter productivity (DMP) and final C-input from cover crops.

Carbon input from grassland

The C input from grassland is updated by deriving the grass age from the LPIS archive, which is corrected for grassland renewal activities detected with Sentinel-1 and 2 data.

Figure 3. Detection of cover crops from S2 NDVI timeseries.

Figure 4. C-input of cover crops in 2018 [kg C/ha] for arable land parcels.

Acknowledgements

This study is funded by ESA CARBON-RO: RESEARCH OPPORTUNITIES IN THE TERRESTRIAL CARBON CLUSTER. ESA contract No. 4000141140/23/E-EF

van Baren, S. A., Arets, E. J. M. M., Hendriks, C. M. J., Kramer, H., Lesschen, J.P., & Schelhaas, M. J. (2024). Greenhouse gas reporting of the LULUCF sector in the Netherlands: Methodological background, update 2024. (WOT-technical report; No. 255). WOT Natuur & Milieu. <https://doi.org/10.18174/648278>

Opportunities of wet peatland carbon farming

Building paludiculture business cases at scale

Andreas Haberl (Project manager)
Michael Succow Foundation –
Partner in the Greifswald Mire Centre
andreas.haberl@succow-stiftung.de

Elisabet Rams (Research Associate)
Michael Succow Foundation –
Partner in the Greifswald Mire Centre
elisabet.rams@succow-stiftung.de

Jan Peters (Managing Director)
Michael Succow Foundation –
Partner in the Greifswald Mire Centre
jan.peters@succow-stiftung.de

Rewetting Peatlands: A necessity for climate-neutral land use by 2050

- Achieving climate neutrality in the land-use sector by 2050 requires rewetting peatlands and a shift towards zero-drainage peatland use.
- Though covering only **3% of EU agricultural land**, drained peat soils contribute **25% of all GHG emissions** from EU agricultural sector; in peatland-rich Member States, e.g. in Baltics, even up to 71% (see Fig.1).
- A just transition needs to engage landowners and land users, recognizing their essential role in addressing climate and societal challenges.
- A **new paradigm for peatland carbon farmers** is needed:
- Cultivating renewable biomass for **carbon-neutral or carbon-negative products through paludiculture**.
- Preserving soil carbon in wet peat layers, biodiversity, water resources, and essential ecosystem services while contributing to climate change mitigation & adaptation, and human wellbeing.

Upscaling needs:

- 1) Establishing & upscaling **best paludiculture practices**;
- 2) Building a database on **ecosystem services** from paludiculture pilots;
- 3) Developing **climate-neutral value chains** for paludiculture products;
- 4) Developing **consistent agricultural policy & remuneration frameworks** in line with EU & national frameworks.

Fig. 1: Emissions from drained peatlands in the agricultural sector. Percentage of agricultural land on organic soils (inner circle) and percentage of their greenhouse gas emissions of total agricultural emissions (incl. LULUCF) (outer circle). Source: GMC 2020

Financing peatland restoration & paludiculture under the EU CRCF: Key insights & strategies

Ensured additionality and market credibility

Peatland rewetting until now remains far below what is needed. It can therefore be considered to be **additional by default**.

Emission reductions from peatland rewetting are **inherently permanent**, because –also in the case of reversal– the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere remains permanently reduced compared to the baseline.

Scaling up requires blended finance

Peatland restoration through rewetting & paludiculture must overcome key barriers to achieve implementation at scale.

→ Blended finance, **combining CAP funding, carbon markets, and national incentives**, should be developed to ensure long-term financial viability

→ Paludiculture biomass **demand must be stimulated**.

Adopt a hybrid payment model to ensure viability

Contractual agreements should **ensure upfront payments for rewetting costs** (before credit issuance), combined with result-based payments for verified emission reductions.

→ Ensure security for farmers while maintaining accountability.

Succow Stiftung

GREIFSWALD MIRE CENTRE

What is paludiculture?

Paludiculture is wet agriculture or silviculture on wet and rewetted peatland that uses spontaneously grown or cultivated above ground biomass **under conditions in which peat is conserved or even newly formed**. Therefore **permanent waterlogging** with water levels in or close to the surface (≤10 cm) during vegetation periods and avoidance of practices that harm the topsoil and root layer are essential.

Peatlands, Climate, and Paludiculture

Resources

- <https://www.moorwissen.de/index-en.html>
- <https://www.moorwissen.de/paludiculture.html>
- [Info paper on paludiculture and biodiversity](#)
- [Wetlands and methane](#)
- [Why methane emissions do not undermine peatland rewetting \(in German, please refer to page 10\)](#)

Baltic paludiculture experience

Fig. 2: EUKI Paludiculture Baltics assessed paludiculture potential, model site implementation, and living labs in the Baltics. Sites below will be part of Horizon project PaluWise.

Fig. 2a&b: The Baisogala paludiculture show case, Lithuania; 5 ha peatland rewetting & establishment of wet reed canary grass production for fodder or energy biomass.

Fig. 2c&d: Living lab on 50 ha Natura2000 wet meadows & pellet production in Rujņa river valley in Latvia.

Upscaling paludiculture tomoor.w

<https://www.tomoorrow.org/>

Germany is a forerunner in large-scale, long-term paludiculture pilots with strong business integration. Through the toMOORow initiative, 14 leading companies have formed the “Alliance of Pioneers,” committing to developing and scaling paludiculture within their operations.

At the European level, the EU HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-3 call, “Paludiculture: Large-Scale Demonstrations,” builds on this momentum. As a result, three large-scale projects will launch in 2025:

PATHWAYS2RESILIENCE

**PATHWAYS2RESILIENCE
ACCELERATES CLIMATE
ADAPTATION IN EUROPE**

€21M

allocated in sub-grants to help regions develop transformative pathways to climate resilience via **2 open calls**.

Supporting the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, the Pathways2Resilience programme will empower European regions and communities to co-design locally-led pathways towards a climate-resilient future, providing them with guidance adaptable to local needs.

100+

European regions and communities assisted in identifying locally-led climate resilience solutions.

10+

Innovation Practice Groups & Finance Innovation Lab to increase knowledge and design solutions and business models for climate adaptation and resilience.

www.pathways2resilience.eu
hello@pathways2resilience.eu

[@Pathways2Resilience](https://www.linkedin.com/company/pathways2resilience)
[@P2Resilience](https://www.facebook.com/Pathways2Resilience)

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101093942.

STANDARDISING THE SOIL

*Does the Standardised Baseline meet the objectives of the EU CRCF?
Key concerns and recommendations from soil carbon practitioners*

Tomasz Kowalczewski^{1,5}, Paul Martin^{2,5}, Max DuBuisson^{3,5}, Erica Johnson^{4,5}, et al.

¹ Green Alchemy ApS, ² ReGeneration SAS, ³ Indigo Ag Inc., ⁴ Agreena, ⁵ ISCIA

The International Soil Carbon Industry Alliance (ISCIA) brings together companies, scientists, and organizations to promote carbon farming. Our members manage millions of hectares across Europe, supporting high-integrity soil carbon sequestration projects.

Project dSOC = change in soil organic carbon (SOC) in the project scenario
Std Baseline dSOC = change in SOC with a standardised baseline
BAU Baseline dSOC = change in SOC with a project-specific baseline, assuming business as usual (BAU) management

Note: This diagram assumes that the SOC stock is increasing at a faster rate in the BAU baseline than in the standardised baseline. While this hypothetical would have different results with different assumptions, the example illustrates how these variables affect outcomes.

	Concerns	Impacts	Recommendations
Standardised Baselines	Over-reliance on standardised baseline that is misaligned with existing scientific robustness, market dynamics, and internationally recognised standards.	Diluting the concept of additionality risks over-crediting, greenwashing and undermining farmer incentives	Recognise the higher level of integrity with activity-specific baseline or ensure all baselines meet this requirement to ensure accurate, high-quality carbon credits.
Offset & Inset Use Cases	Current framework does not differentiate between offsetting (VCM) and insetting (supply chain/scope3)	Potential for double-counting and lack of guidelines for supply chain engagement.	Provide clear guidance for both intervention and inventory accounting to allow carbon unit issuance for both end-uses.

The robustness and readiness of the Standardised Baseline approach is not yet meeting the CRCF Regulation requirements.

The carbon farming methodology needs to allow project developers to choose the type of baseline for their project - whether standardized or activity-specific.

Smart Carbon Farming: Practical Solutions for CO₂ Reduction and Biodiversity

Presented by:

tgo AG, a partner in the Smart Carbon Farming Program Interreg North West Europe

1. Introduction

Carbon Farming: Practical Solutions for CO₂ Reduction and Biodiversity

- Mission: To unite sustainable CO₂ sequestration and biodiversity, creating long-term, value-stable carbon certificates.
- Why Carbon Farming?
 - Regenerates soil health and increases fertility.
 - Creates real carbon sinks for long-term climate benefits.
 - Promotes biodiversity and sustainable agricultural practices.

2. Showcase Project: Long-Term Carbon Sink in the Artland Region (Germany)

A Model for Sustainable Climate Action

- Key Approaches:
 - **Agroforestry:** Alternating rows of fast-growing poplars and perennial crops.
 - **Biodiversity:** Flowering strips around the site provide habitat for pollinators and enhance biodiversity.
 - **Pyrolysis:** Transforming poplar wood into biochar for soil improvement and energy production.
- **Outcome:** A combined approach that delivers carbon sequestration and biodiversity gains.

3. Calculating Carbon Sequestration

Scientifically Validated and Measurable Results

- **10-Hectare Model:**
 - 10% poplars, 80% silphium, 10% flower meadow.
- **CO₂ Sequestration:** 101,8 tons of CO₂ per year before Leakage
- **Accreditation:** Baseline measurements follow LCA, ACS2030 and IPCC guidelines and are validated by peer-reviewed research.

4. Market Potential

• **Inset Market:** Agricultural businesses enhance supply chain sustainability by adopting climate-neutral products.

• **Offset Market:** Companies outside agriculture (e.g., logistics, finance, and industry) can offset emissions.

5. Certification and Quality Assurance

Reliable Standards for Carbon Sequestration Scope 1, 2, 3.

- **Certifications:**
 - ISO 14064-1 and 14064-2.
 - ESG and CSRD conform
 - BC LOCK ensures traceability and quality.
- **Key Advantage:** Farmers produce verifiable carbon certificates backed by consistent baseline data.

Carbon Farming 10 ha
CO₂ reduction from the atmosphere after Leakage ca. 81 t CO₂

Possible payout at a price of EUA Futures 2/25 (80€)

ca. 6.480 €

Projection 2030: Possible payout at a price of 180 EUR/t Statement by the EU

ca. 14.580 €

6. Call to Action

SMART CARBON FARMING

11 PROJECT PARTNERS / 5 COUNTRIES
3 Local Emission actors
6 Accredited market partners
2 Accredited partners

CHALLENGES	INNOVATION	IMPACT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers need to stay competitive and live with 0% Climate Loss • Carbon Farming is cheaper, reliable monitoring solutions • Farmers lack the time, access for solutions, policy, and business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customised technologies for 3 carbon monitoring solutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N₂O spectral and radar soil moisture monitoring from drones or satellite • N₂O sensors for the measurement of GHG on field soils • Test & deploy on 1000 farms • Allow farmers to capture additional income • 25 t CO₂ farm's loss • Direct farm-to-market solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% of the 1000 farms in the agricultural sector added to the market • Validated monitoring solutions with increased efficiency & cost-effectiveness • Addition of 1000 farms to the market • 100% of the 1000 farms in the agricultural sector added to the market • 100% of the 1000 farms in the agricultural sector added to the market

Build farmer resilience capacity

- 50 Farmer-partners: 5000 ha of 4 MOOC
- Reach out to more than 25,000 farmers
- Carbon Farming Digital Innovation ecosystem

Werner-Baumbachstraße 41,
49661 Cloppenburg
Germany
Email: info@tgo.ag

Risk assessment of regenerative agriculture projects in carbon markets

BeZero

BeZero Carbon is the carbon ratings agency. We equip world-leading organisations with the knowledge, tools and confidence to make better climate decisions. We aim to scale investment in environmental markets that deliver a sustainable future.

Authors:
Michal Grucik, Eli Melissa,
Saheba Bhatnagar, Beth Roberts,
Phil Platt and Niels Andela
BeZero Carbon Ltd, London,
United Kingdom
*Corresponding author:
michal.grucik@bezerocarbon.com
eli.melissa@bezerocarbon.com

BeZero Carbon Rating

Our ratings assess the quality of carbon projects of any type, at any stage, anywhere. Ratings represent BeZero's assessment of the likelihood of a carbon credit achieving a tonne of CO₂e avoided or removed, with AAA highest and D lowest.

Soil Carbon and Agriculture sector

- Soil Carbon & Agriculture, a fast-growing sector, offers a globally significant carbon sequestration and storage opportunity.
- Regenerative Agriculture, a sub-sector of Soil Carbon & Agriculture, improves soil carbon with no-till farming and cover cropping practices.
- BeZero combines remote sensing, machine learning, and field ecology to assess carbon project risks

- globally, focusing on additionality, over-crediting, and non-permanence.
- Challenges in monitoring include scarce public datasets for identification of field boundaries and agricultural practices such as cover cropping.
- Here, we showcase our Earth observation methods for assessing cover crop and reduced till adoption using satellite data, machine learning, and time-series analysis.

- Within the derived boundaries, we extract zonal summary time series of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index and the Normalized Difference Tillage Index, from which we extract key phenological events and infer management practices.
- We map practice adoption outside the project area to establish a realistic baseline, informing our view on project additionality. The effectiveness of implementation of practices inside the project area further informs our view on carbon accounting and permanence.

Using national agricultural statistics where available

- For some geographic regions, agricultural censuses provide context on practice adoption and growing season crop type.
- Low adoption of regenerative agricultural practices in Europe bolsters the additionality of carbon projects, with notable regional differences.

Field boundary delineation

- In regions where field-level agricultural data is scarce, we are able to delineate field boundaries and determine the cash crop type in a given growing season using machine learning.
- We use a time series of spectral indices from Sentinel-2 at 10m resolution to derive a range of phenological features used in machine learning models that predict which pixels belong to the same field and crop type.

Cover crop and tillage detection

We track crop growth cycles through the timing of key phenological events and crop type data.

Summary

The Soil Carbon & Agriculture sector is primed for significant growth. At BeZero, we:

- ✓ Provide ex-ante and ex-post ratings that evaluate the efficacy of carbon projects anywhere at any stage.
- ✓ Enhance our analytical capabilities by integrating geospatial data, and machine learning to identify regenerative agriculture practices from satellite imagery.
- ✓ Continuously improve our analyses by adopting new methodologies from literature enhanced by public datasets to refine our analysis of additionality, carbon accounting, and permanence risk.

Empowering Agroforestry from Space

Tackling the challenges of agroforestry carbon farming MRV, using a scalable, trustable and easy-to-use application.

UNLOCKING POTENTIAL

Carbon farming MRV is a major bottleneck for agroforestry project developers due to costly, manual field measurements and a lack of transparency. **CarboCatch** removes these barriers, enabling the financing needed to scale agroforestry—boosting climate resilience and biodiversity while fighting climate change. Currently piloting in the Netherlands, and expanding to EU.

- **Space4Good** leverages the power of remote sensing, GIS and AI to develop solutions for social and environmental impact.
- The **Louis Bolk Institute** is the knowledge institute for sustainable agriculture, nutrition and health in the Netherlands.

- Plot based impact analysis
- User friendly application
- Biomass mapping and tracking over time
- Current & potential carbon uptake per plot
- Scalable design

Check out our platform demo

Methodology

Discussion points & Next steps

- High reliability, particularly for local models, with relative errors in CO₂ uptake per plot ranging from 1% to 14%, depending on location.
- Reduced need for field measurements, enhancing affordability and scalability.
- Agroforestry-specific modeling approach provides the most accurate results.
- Custom allometric equations tailored to agroforestry are essential for precise carbon storage estimation.
- Currently testing and calibrating the models in other parts of Europe within the context of INNO4CFIs: project funded by the European Union under GA 101115156. <https://inno4cfis.eu/>

Interested to collaborate? **Connect:**

www.space4good.com

lv@space4good.com

w.thissen@louisbolk.nl

<https://www.louisbolk.nl/>

Assessment of carbon balance in table olive farms (*Kalamata cv*) implementing agroecological & conventional farming practices

V. D. Gkissakis¹, I. Michail¹, P. Tsachansachis¹, V. Kontele¹

¹Hellenic Agricultural Organisation (ELGO) – DIMITRA, Institute of Olive Tree, Subtropical Crops and Viticulture (IOSV), Olive & horticultural crops dpt., Lakonikis 87, 24100, Kalamata, Greece

✉ gkissakis@elgo.gr

Introduction

Olive farms are **major component** of the Mediterranean basin with great potential in terms of **carbon sequestration & climate change mitigation**. Specifically, **table olive production** is an important part of the broader olive sector, especially vulnerable to climate stresses. **Agroecological approaches** in olive farming are a **main transitional pathway** for increasing agroecosystem resilience to environmental stresses.

Methodology

Four representative table olive farms (*Kalamata cv*) were studied over a two-year period in **Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece**, including two conventional farms & another two implementing agroecological practices (cover crops, organic fertilization, pruning residues integration & reduced soil management).

Farms were assessed in terms of i) **carbon inputs**, related to permanent tree structure, cover crops, pruning residues recycled, organic fertilization, leaves & flower material falling from olive tree to soil and fruit carbon accumulation ii) **carbon outputs** regarding olive fruit harvest, non-recycled pruning residues, soil erosion and soil carbon emissions.

The carbon balance in olive farms (**CBfarm**) was calculated by deducting carbon outputs from inputs, using on-site and literature data. CB of olive trees (**CBtree**) was estimated as the annual rate of carbon accumulation in permanent tree structure, while soil CB (**CBsoil**) was estimated by deducting CBtree from CBsoil.

Figure 1. Olive groves in Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece, applying agroecological farming practices

Results & discussion

Carbon balance in **agroecological olive farms was positive** with an average of 1.79 C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ while **conventional farms had a negative balance** of average of -0,45 tons C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. This was due to **negative CBsoil in conventional farms** (-0,59 compared to 1.68 tons C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ for agroecological), while **CBtree was relatively similar in both farming systems** (0.14 and 0.12 tons C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ respectively) (Figure 2). **Main C contribution** to total C inputs was due to **pruning and olive fruits** harvested for both farming systems. However, **cover crops was a major C input factor** only for agroecological olive groves (Figure 3) The above stress the **importance of agroecological farming** in mitigating climate change.

Figure 2. Carbon balance (ton C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) in conventional (Conv) & agroecological (Agroeco) table olive groves in Soil, Olive tree & whole Grove

Figure 3. Contributions (%) to total C input in conventional and agroecological table olive groves regarding cover crops, olive harvest, pruning, olive tree permanent structure and leaves, flowers and fruit loss.

Coppice with Standards (CwS) Forestry: Assessing Carbon Sequestration through High-Frequency IoT Monitoring

Authors: Jim Yates^{1,2}, Francesco Renzi^{1,2}, Shahla Asgharinia³, Riccardo Valentini^{1,2}

Department for innovations in Biological, Agri-food and Forest systems (DIBAF) Via San Camillo de Lellis 4, 01100, Viterbo, Italy (1)
 Nature 4.0 SB Srl - Via Della Chimica 7, Viterbo 01100 Italy (2)
 UNFAO - Viale delle Terme di Caracalla, 00153 Roma RM (3)

Context

Coppice with Standards (CwS) forestry combines high forest standards with a coppiced understory, traditionally valued for timber and firewood. However, its role in carbon sequestration remains underexplored.

CwS in Carbon Farming

- Supports sustainable land management & agroforestry.
- Enhances long-term carbon storage potential.
- Recognized in some national carbon certification schemes, but limited EU integration.
- CwS stands often remain underutilized or abandoned, limiting carbon revenue potential.

Policy & Regulation

- The EU Carbon Removals & Farming Regulation (EU/2024/3012) provides a voluntary carbon certification framework.
- Methodologies for CwS-based carbon sequestration require further development

Future Outlook

Integrating CwS into carbon farming strategies can unlock opportunities for carbon credits and sustainable forest management.

Objectives/Methods

Tracking Diametric Growth with IoT Sensors

This study applies high-frequency low cost IoT monitoring to detect seasonal changes in diametric growth and its role in assessing carbon sequestration within CwS systems.

Methodology

- TreeTalker+ Infrared Sensors used to track DBH and growth rates over one year.
- Data integrated with allometric functions to estimate biomass and Carbon increment.
- Avg CO2 Credit Price \$ USD for 2021 applied to fully stocked forest

IoT driven TreeTalker+ Version 3.2

An example of a Q. Cerris L. Coppice under Quasi Realtime monitoring by Treetalker +

Site location - Roccarespamani Viterbo

Carbon sequestered as a function of DBH growth from May until September 2021

CO2 fixation as a function of DBH growth from May until September 2021

Table 1. Total CO2 (T) and hypothetical credit generated applying mean Carbon Price 2024 \$USD by stems monitored in 2021

Portion of contribution to Carbon Sequestration by stem monitored by IoT Devices

- Stem growth was accurately captured in quasi real time from IoT devices.
- The average Carbon fixed in woody biomass for each stem was 21.586 kilograms or 0.02 tones.
- Using Global Average Carbon Prices in USD for 2024 this equates to approximately \$0.71 cents per stem for the year 2021.
- Extrapolated per hectare: 10,940.23 kg carbon (~10.94 tC/ha) and 40,150.25 kg CO₂ (~40.15 tCO₂/ha).
- Extrapolated per hectare: 1800stems/ha = 40.15×\$32USD = \$1,285/ha/year/2021

Key Insights

- Low cost continuous, real-time data enhances carbon sequestration estimates.
- Supports precise monitoring & verification for carbon farming.
- Demonstrates the potential of IoT-driven forestry in climate-smart land management.

Impact

IoT-enabled tracking in CwS can improve carbon credit assessments and support EU carbon farming strategies by providing high-resolution growth data.

SUPPORTING THE TRANSITION TO CLIMATE-NEUTRAL AND CLIMATE RESILIENT EUROPEAN FARMING

ClieNFarms is an Innovation Action Project funded by the European Commission, in support of the European Green Deal. It aims to co-develop and scale up locally relevant systemic solutions, to foster sustainable, climate-neutral and resilient European farms.

INTERNATIONAL NETWORK OF FARMERS

The Farming for Climate platform *Mobilizing the EU agricultural advisory community for Climate Smart Farming*

FARMING FOR CLIMATE IS:

- A RESPONSE TO MULTIPLE EU AGRICULTURAL PROJECTS PROVIDING KNOWLEDGE ON CLIMATE CHANGE, MITIGATION, AND ADAPTATION.
- AN INITIATIVE BY CLIMATE FARM DEMO, CLIMATESMARTADVISORS, CLIENFARMS AND ORGANIC CLIMATE NETWORK.
- AN OPEN-ACCESS PLATFORM FOR FIELD STAKEHOLDERS OFFERING RESOURCES ON CARBON FARMING, INCLUDING:
 - FARMING PRACTICES FOR CLIMATE ADAPTATION AND MITIGATION
 - CLIMATE AND CARBON ASSESSMENT TOOLS
 - ADVISORY METHODS AND TOOLS
- A REGULARLY UPDATED PLATFORM, ALLOWING USERS TO CONTRIBUTE NEW OR IMPROVED TOOLS, PRACTICES, AND METHODS.

HOW WILL FARMERS AND OTHER VALUE CHAIN ACTORS BENEFIT?

- 1 Estimation of GHG and C sequestration values
- 2 Answering to consumer requests
- 3 Climate neutrality solutions and new approaches
- 4 Business contacts
- 5 Increased product value
- 6 Benchmarking and business analysis

www.clieNFarms.eu

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO. 101016522

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

If You Were a French Farmer, Where Should You Start a Carbon Farming Project?

Establishing Project-Based Baselines for Robust Carbon Claims Using Earth Observation

Federica D'Acunzio, Uptoeearth GmbH, Germany, federica.dacunzio@uptoeearth.eu
Filippo Iodice, Uptoeearth GmbH, Germany, filippo.iodice@uptoeearth.eu

Background

Within the upcoming European certification framework for carbon farming, a carbon removal activity results in a net carbon removal benefit when the carbon removals above the baseline outweigh any increase in greenhouse gas emissions due to the implementation of the carbon removal activity¹. Therefore, the definition of a baseline is crucial not only to demonstrate operators' additionality, but also to set the monitoring period, to measure the activity sustainability and even more to ensure the correct accounting of carbon removal units, by avoiding double counting.

To support this, Uptoeearth GmbH (UTE) is creating a rating system based on Earth Observation (EO), which can support carbon removal quantification through the creation of a project-based baseline. The rating system has been developed under the ESA-funded Feasibility Study "SCORE – Scale for Carbon Organic Resilient Eterreal" to be implemented in agricultural, urban and coastal areas.

1 Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council Establishing A Union Certification Framework For Permanent Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming And Carbon Storage In Products, 27 November 2024, PE-CONS 9271/24 REV 1

Results

The project is going to develop an **open-source portal** providing access to:

- SCORE classification maps to be used as baseline
- Crop type maps
- Residual biomass availability maps for biochar production.

Data will be offered at plot level, upon availability.
To give you an idea of how the SCORE system works, we have developed a demo of our portal.

Imagine you are a French farmer from Île-de-France Region and need to perform a pre-assessment analysis to understand whether your plots are suitable to host carbon farming projects. Currently, this consultancy service ranges between 15.000-20.000€.

By scanning the following QR code, you will get access to the SCORE scale and understand what's your current plot condition and whether they are suitable to host carbon projects.

2 IPCC (2021), Manual for the creation of Blue Carbon projects in Europe and the Mediterranean, Oltero, M. (Ed.), 144 pages.

Methodology

The project has developed a rating system based on EO data ranging from 0 to 100, allocating a maximum of 30 points for Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stored in the past, 40 points for SOC stored in the present, and 30 points for SOC to be potentially stored in the future. The scale allows the reader to immediately visualize plot characteristics, identifying carbon-poor plots with low expectations for short-term carbon accumulation with values close to zero.

Soils with intermediate values, between 40 and 60 points, indicate medium-value soils that currently have good carbon presence and can rapidly accumulate more carbon through good agricultural practices. Values above 70 and close to 100 indicate soils saturated with carbon and in excellent condition. To simplify the system communication, it has been translated into a multi-score, using letters and colours.

Past	Present	Future	SCORE VALUE	SCORE-RATES
High SOC Content	High SOC	High SOC	70-100	A B C D E
Medium SOC Content	Medium SOC	Medium SOC	50-70	A B C D E
Low SOC Content	Low SOC	Low SOC	30-50	A B C D E
Very Low SOC Content	Very Low SOC	Very Low SOC	10-30	A B C D E
0 Points	0 Points	0 Points	0-10	A B C D E

Image 1. SCORE Rating system

Class A represents soils rich in organic carbon, with a soft, well-aggregated structure, high water retention capacity, and excellent natural fertility. They are often found in well-managed ecosystems such as permanent grasslands, forests, and humus-rich soils. They have very limited potential for carbon projects.

Class B refers to well-structured soils with a good balance of organic carbon and microbial activity. These soils typically result from regenerative agricultural practices such as crop rotation, cover cropping, and compost application. These show limited capacity for carbon projects.

Class C soils are usually cultivated with conventional farming practices, which tend to gradually reduce organic carbon content. Fertility is moderate, with decent soil aggregation but susceptibility to erosion and organic carbon loss. They are suitable for carbon projects.

Class D soils show low organic carbon, often subject to compaction, erosion, and reduced microbial activity. Typical of areas with intensive farming that does not restore organic carbon. These are well-suited for carbon projects but requiring some investment.

Class E soils are extremely poor in organic carbon, with minimal ability to retain water and nutrients. Found in desertified areas, saline soils, or regions experiencing severe environmental degradation. They are potentially viable for carbon projects but requiring significant investment.

Image 2. Examples of SCORE classification

SCORE system can be used to establish **standardised baselines** that are **representative** of standard practices, pedoclimatic and geographic context, ensuring **objectivity**, **reducing compliance and other administrative costs**.

Additionally, because of the consideration of historical time series, not only **first movers** who have performed positive action **receive recognition**, contrasting greenwashing, but also **additionality** can be identified and updated regularly.

Next steps

In addition to open-source online portal that will showcase results from SCORE project, UTE is developing several services to support carbon farming:

- SCORE classification maps to be used as baseline
- Crop type maps
- Residual biomass availability maps for biochar production
- Access to a Simulator to support farmers and project developers in selecting the best agricultural practice to apply (a free demo is available scanning the QR code, and is co-funded by Erasmus+ KA2 project FarmBox)
- Customised monitoring system
- API Key for data integration in proprietary systems.

All maps will be available at 10m of resolution and regularly updated.

Who should use SCORE and why?

- Farmers and project developers in **pre-assessment** and **monitoring** phases of carbon farming projects
- Policy makers to develop more accurate project or plot-based yet **standardised baseline** rather than regional ones with coarser resolutions
- Buyers, marketplace, brokers to invest in **more profitable** carbon farming projects or monitor their investments
- Insurance to **reduce risks** associated with carbon leakage.

Image 3. SCORE map of French region Ile-de-France

Conclusion

SCORE system has been designed to **increase trust** in Voluntary Carbon Market along the whole supply chain, valorizing caring farmers and project developers, protecting buyers investment against greenwashing, and increase the value of carbon credits, abating costs for carbon farming implementation.

SCAN THIS QR CODE AND DISCOVER IF YOU COULD HOST CARBON FARMING PROJECTS

HAVE YOUR SAY! SCAN THE QR CODE AND LEAVE YOUR FEEDBACK ON THE PROJECT

The SMURF will help the European forest-based value chain providing sustainable and profitable management and business models, a standardized Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) system and provide support structures and training for small-forest holdings.

Funded by the European Union

HOW CAN SUSTAINABLE FOREST MANAGEMENT CONTRIBUTE TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION?

WHY?

Europe's forests cover 40% of the continent's land area, with approximately 16 million forest holdings. A shift in forest management is urgently needed to address:

- Increasing natural threats (wildfires, pests, floods).
- Climate change mitigation and the growing demand for forest ecosystem services (biodiversity, water regulation).
- Rural abandonment, affecting landscape and socio-economic resilience.
- Rising demand for renewable products (construction, energy).
- Complex ownership structures, limiting sustainable management.
- Forest degradation and fragmentation, reducing ecosystem functionality.
- Obsolete management and harvesting techniques, requiring innovation.

HOW?

- Implementing innovative Integrated Forest Management (IFM) models.
- Engaging forest owners, local communities, and stakeholders.
- Promoting multi-purpose forest management (economic + environmental benefits).
- Leveraging new technologies for monitoring and decision-making.
- Applying an adaptive approach to increase resilience.
- Enhancing the profitability of sustainable forest-based activities.

WHAT?

- A comprehensive IFM 360° solution that integrates:
- Closer-to-Nature silviculture, fostering ecosystem-based management.
 - New business models for small forest holders, covering timber and non-timber products.
 - A robust PES (Payment for Ecosystem Services) framework, including:
 - Simplified and transparent carbon accounting methodology.
 - A digital marketplace ensuring traceability and fair valuation.
 - Biodiversity assessment & qualification tools.
 - A collaborative Forest Hub for knowledge exchange and stakeholder engagement.

Authors:
María Sosa (Preferred by Nature) - Pablo Rodríguez-Noriega (Preferred by Nature)
Tomás Sánchez (Cesefor Foundation) - Julia Bucso (Cesefor Foundation)

Learn more about SMURF Project:

Using multispectral satellite imagery and machine learning to automate agroforestry soil organic carbon and biodiversity prediction across Europe

Colin R. Tosh et al. The Organic Research Centre. Trent Lodge, Stroud Road, Cirencester, Gloucestershire, GL7 6JN

Machine learned models are allowing us to supply European agroforestry farmers with high-definition, farm-scale soil carbon and landscape biodiversity maps

1. Introduction

- A significant expense in nature-based carbon trading schemes comes from MRV activities¹.
- Machine learning models have the potential to learn soil carbon and other farm ecological characteristics from freely available field-derived data and satellite imagery².
- Farmers undergoing "ecological regeneration" also want easy-to-obtain ecological data to monitor how well they are doing.

2. Methods

- We have trained CNNs (convolutional neural networks) on around 40,000 Sentinel2 1C (10m) images across the EU and corresponding soil carbon and field biodiversity data from the LUCAS 2018 and GBIF databases.
- We are using these models to map living lab farms in the EU REFOREST project for soil carbon and plant biodiversity.

3. Results

- Models are not perfect but output useful ecological classification data (see Figures 1 and 2) and can certainly be improved further with the input of additional environmental variables.

4. Discussion

- CNN models trained only with landscape imagery are already producing useful mappings of farm soil carbon and other ecological characteristics.
- With further input and resources these can certainly be made more accurate.
- We predict that reliable verification of agricultural activities will be possible in the near future using the combination of satellite imagery, additional numerical landscape data, and advanced multimodal neural network models.

Figure 1. Predicted soil organic carbon across an agroforestry farm in the Czech Rep., farmed by Daniel Pitek. The map is generated from around 3000 Sentinel2 1C (10m) images sampled across the land at 50m spacing and fed through a pretrained CNN.

Figure 2. We are using image manipulation with CNNs to quantify plant biodiversity on EU farms. Plant biodiversity is calculated as an unmanipulated image then compared to an image with the farmed area replaced with a plantless landscape (here, an area of the Sahara Desert).

References

- Eklöv, K., Kurpikinas, L.M. and Yan, S., 2023. A meta-analysis of transaction costs. Aarhus University, DTU Danish Centre for Environment and Energy.
- Yongqiang, O., Fignoni, N., Dou, A. and Lischke, F., 2024. Satellite-based soil organic carbon mapping on European soils using available datasets and support sampling. Science of Remote Sensing, 6, p.100118.

Dr. Colin R. Tosh

colin.t@organicresearchcentre.com

www.organicresearchcentre.com/about-us/our-team/colin-tosh

Scan the QR code to access developer tools for the online version of the models

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”. Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

DISCLAIMER: The views expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or position of the European Union. Neither the authors nor the CREDIBLE consortium are responsible for the use which might be made of the information contained in here. **Please note that this report was prepared based on Project Credible’s Deliverable 4.2, which has not yet been approved by the European Commission and is still under review.**

EUROPEAN
CARBON FARMING
SUMMIT